

NATIVE HORDES
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Native Hordes

An Experiment in Active Disobedience

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This book is dedicated to my desire to graduate and to Beyoncé's assertion that my best revenge is my paper. To all of my advisors and mentors who provided consistent encouragement and support and who never made me feel like less than I am. To my friends and family who comforted me in times of panic and who acted as inspiration for many of the characters in this book. Without all of you, this book would just be a bunch of science with an ethical judgment thrown in at the end. Thank you for making this project possible and saving me from that fate.

Contents

1	The Awakening Iyeena	1
2	The Calling Earth	6
3	Meeting the Boss Iyeena	15
4	Sun Pulling Earth	23
5	Breaking the Surface Iyeena	29
6	Stuck in Place Earth	39
7	Home Sweet New Home Iyeena	41
8	I Won't Go Earth	54
9	The Waiting Room Iyeena	57
10	Family Glue Earth	65
11	History Lesson Iyeena	68

12 Why Me?	
Earth	80
13 Crossing Signals	
Iyeena	83
14 The Copy	
Earth	88
15 Memories	
Iyeena	94
16 Mid Fall	
Earth	104
17 Life on the Farm	
Iyeena	106
18 The Lustbader Complex	
Earth	116
19 Falling Rocks	
Iyeena	120
Appendices	135
A Habitability Test of EPIC 206032309	137
A.1 ABSTRACT	137
A.2 INTRODUCTION	137
A.3 DATA	138
A.3.1 Detrending	139
A.3.2 Removing Outliers	139
A.4 ANALYSIS	140
A.4.1 Exofast	140
A.4.2 MultiNest	141
A.4.3 Our Program	141
A.5 RESULTS	142
A.5.1 Habitability	143
A.5.2 Eccentricity	143
A.6 DISCUSSION	144
B Thirty Meter Telescope Conflict	149

1

The Awakening Iyeena

"Uhdlkj sdjkhe ohfe bge waking up gbheb ngheyd gather qurbd comfortable. We don't want lkj drc tlkjdf to be too overwhelmed." It felt like I was waking up from a really long nap, the kind that tries to draw you back into your dreams and robs you of all familiarity with your surroundings. Except, this time, I knew I really would be completely unfamiliar with my surroundings.

Disorientingly bright lights were shining through what I imagined were eyelids. When I opened them, I saw people scurrying around a white room filled with instruments that beeped and flashed, their words slipping in and out of a language I could understand as my digital memories synced up with the language center of my new physical brain.

I tried to move my head to follow the voices, which must have attracted attention because something suddenly appeared above my face, blocking out the light. All I could see was a silhouette of something that mostly looked like a head, and when it spoke, the voice was clear and authoritative, but warm. "Hello. My name is Lorana. I bguebdg nkdhhd doctor in this lab. Welcome to Iyeena. Can you sit up?"

I sat up for the first time in over 600 years, slowly, still adjusting to the way this new brain and body worked together. "What are you called on your home planet?"

I tried to say "Dakota," but my new mouth didn't yet know how to make the shapes necessary to form those sounds, so it ended up sounding more like *Te-ko-tah*.

A small smile pulled at the edge of Lorana's otherwise flat mouth. I thought it was in response to the way I had fumbled over my tongue like a baby just learning how to talk, so I expected to be laughed at or corrected. Instead, Lorana continued examining my reflexes without comment.

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They put me through a barrage of tests to make sure there hadn't been any complications with the downloading process. They checked my balance, vision, reaction time, and memory.

"What is your home planet?"

"Earth, in the region of the galaxy your people call the Scarce Sector."

"Where are you now and how did you get here?"

"I am on the planet Iyeena. Your people, the Mowleean, made contact with Earth to set up an exchange program, and I was selected to come here. Or, I guess, my consciousness was."

With each word, I got more comfortable with the way my tongue moved and the sounds I could make. The doctor doing the examination assured me that I would sound like a native Mowleean speaker in no time.

I noticed that no one mentioned how long it would be before I moved like a native Mowleean, but glancing down at my four new surprisingly human-looking limbs, I figured it couldn't be too long.

After what felt like hours of being poked, prodded, and interrogated, Lorana announced that I had passed the tests. They had enough proof that the digital information they had downloaded from my physical brain back on Earth had successfully synced with the brain of my host body here on Iyeena. They said I would have to come back for periodic checkups, but I could finally leave the lab.

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They assigned to me two aides and a tour guide – whose names I heard but couldn't repeat, and therefore never remembered – to show me around the compound. The guide walked ahead and the two aides walked on either side of me to catch me in case I fell, which they told me was common for new Visitors.

Back on Earth, I had spent a couple of weeks working with other scientists to put together a list of things to expect. We knew they would be incredibly technologically advanced – they had to be to have made contact with hundreds of other lifeforms around the Milky Way – but that knowledge alone could not have prepared me for what I saw on that tour.

The walls of the hallway were dark and rough, in stark contrast to the white, sterile walls of the lab. The guide's voice echoed off the walls, slightly distorted. I tried to figure out what they were made of, but before I could figure it out myself or ask the guide, we reached the first room on the tour. The white walls were back.

It appeared to be some kind of control room. Things that I thought were computer consoles lined the walls, operated by astronomers who each introduced themselves and told me a little bit about the observations they were running. My guide explained that the dozens of devices in this room were just some of the tools they used to remotely control the telescopes they had orbiting Iyeena out in space.

Slowly, deliberately as I learned more about how my new mouth worked, I asked if all of their telescopes were space-based. One of the technicians told me they had been using space telescopes since long before anyone in the room had been born. There was a mountain range some distance away where ancient Mowleean used to put telescopes before their technology caught up with their goals.

My guide told me that even the earliest Mowleean Thinkers had known that the atmosphere on Iyeena was too thick for telescopes to be put anywhere else without compromising the quality of the data. I asked if I would be able to go see any of the telescopes and the guide said no. Apparently, the Iyeenan sun was too active for life to survive there without the full atmosphere to protect it, so everything had been controlled remotely even when the telescopes had been in use.

Realizing that I wouldn't be able to see any Mowleean telescopes broke my astronomer's heart. I tried not to let my feelings show, but I probably wasn't very successful. I didn't know yet how to control the muscles in my face, but more importantly, I didn't know which facial expressions meant what on Iyeena.

"You can't see *those* telescopes. But we still have stuff to show you," said the guide. "Follow me."

Pretty sure I was smiling, I walked – well, I also did a fair amount of stumbling – behind the guide across the control room to a door on the other side.

Before we could reach the door, one of the astronomers reached out and grabbed my arm. I turned around to see what they had to say. "We've all told you about our research. You should tell us about yours. We were told you study sun pulling."

I thought about the research I had done and whether any of it had been on anything that could be described as sun pulling. Before I could answer, my guide put an arm around my shoulders and started to lead me out of the room. "The doctor said no questions today." I heard a collective grumble from the astronomers before the door to the control room closed.

In front of me stood a row of lockers, a wall of coats, and a doorway so large I wouldn't have been able to touch both sides at once if I stretched my arms all the way out to my sides. The guide handed me a coat and my aides

offered to help me put it on, but I waved them away and struggled through it on my own. After about a minute – at least, that’s what I think it was; I had no perception of how time moved on Iyeena – and a triumphant squeal from me, we were ready to move to the next room.

I didn’t see anything special at first. Some electronics here, some maintenance tools there. The guide explained that this was the room where they tested and repaired all of the telescope parts before they went to the top of the mountain. That explained the coats – much of the equipment needed to be kept at cold temperatures to avoid overheating and to minimize noise signatures from the instruments’ own heat.

The guide led us to the back of the room and, I swear, my jaw literally dropped.

In front of me stood a telescope that was larger than the biggest I had ever seen in person back on Earth. My head immediately filled with questions.

How old was it?

What was it made out of?

Was it fully steerable?

I didn’t get a chance to ask any of them before the guide started talking again. "This was a replacement for one of the telescopes on the mountain. We keep it here more as inspiration to strive for improvement than anything else."

I couldn’t believe it. The Mowleens had *discarded* technology way more advanced than anything that had existed on Earth when I was still there. Granted, that was over 500 years ago, but it’s still no wonder that, even back then, they had already physically visited hundreds of solar systems around the galaxy and developed techniques to digitize and record neural pathways.

I realized that my mouth was still open and closed it to ask, "Is all Mowleean technology this advanced? Or is it just in astronomy?"

Back on Earth, when I was first researching this system, I imagined that if any sentient life could possibly exist on a tidally locked planet, they would know way more about space than humans. The planet is so close to its sun that they would definitely have short years and they would likely need to live on the side of the planet where it was always nighttime. That meant the appearance of their night sky would change more quickly than it would on Earth, giving ancient Mowleens an interest in the stars way faster than ancient humans ever realized they were anything more than a smattering of pinpricks in a blanket shielding us from a world of fire.

Still looking at the telescope, the guide answered, "Astronomy is just one of the fields where we have made the most advancements, but the rest are not far behind."

That was exciting to hear, but it didn’t really make sense. I didn’t think

the Mowleens as a species were that much older than humans, so why were they so advanced in everything?

I was led through several more rooms, each with contents more impressive than the last, all related to astronomy. Some had other telescopes, one looked like a junk-yard of old telescope transport vehicles, and one held an enormous collection of artifacts they had collected from each planet they had visited. It got to the point where I had been awed and amazed so many times that nothing could do the job anymore. The guide must have seen this because the tour ended soon after my big reactions did.

The guide and my aides led me to my quarters. They assured me that someone would come by to collect me after I had had enough rest. The guide turned away without so much as a "goodnight" and walked down the hall. Before they left to follow, the aides told me how impressed they were that I had only stumbled a few times.

Proud, I smiled – I think – and walked through the door into my new home.

I looked around my room. There were no windows, just the same rough substance that the walls in the hallways were made of. A quick exploration beyond a door on the far wall revealed that it led to something like a bathroom. There was a stall with a drain in the floor and nozzles arrayed on the walls so that water would hit the showerer from the sides instead of from above. A hole in the floor reminded me that I hadn't...relieved myself all day, and that I didn't really understand how to do so when it became necessary. "Well," I thought, "that will be an adventure."

I looked around for a mirror, but couldn't find one. I hadn't seen my face yet, or most of my new body for that matter. Part of me was annoyed and part of me was dying of curiosity, but most of me was too tired to think about anything but the possibility of sleep.

I spent a few minutes trying to find the source of light in the room – a crack around the perimeter of the ceiling – and another few minutes trying to figure out how to turn it off – a foot pedal by the bed – but when I did, I crawled into the simple yet surprisingly comfy bed, ready to pass out.

Laying on my back, I noticed a soft red glow casting shadows on the walls. It was eerily beautiful, if not a little bit inconvenient for bedtime. I felt warm – warm enough that I was too comfortable to search for the source of the glow and too close to asleep to look for it even if I wanted to. Instead, I fell completely asleep marveling that this was my life now, in an alien body on a planet hundreds of light years from Earth.

2

The Calling Earth

I could tell we were getting close to where I work when the car tilted as it headed up the hill. I tried to run up it once, but it's so steep and so long that I gave up after a while and ordered a car to take me the rest of the way. I had worked at the same government-run observatory, the National Optical Astronomy Observatory, for five years. It was in the middle of what used to be a desert, but someone built a water production factory there about a decade before and people started moving in in droves. We couldn't actually use the telescopes there anymore because there's too much light pollution in the area. It's sad, really. Twenty years ago, those telescopes were used to do cutting edge research and now they're little more than tourist attractions.

The car stopped in front of the entrance to my building and the door opened automatically. Even though I knew the automated driving system didn't care how polite I was, I thanked the car because it felt wrong not to and walked inside.

I smelled the coffee as soon as I walked through the doors. Someone had just made a pot in the little kitchen that sat in the center of the square formed by all of the scientists' offices. I mentally thanked the stranger who had been smart enough to realize how cranky astronomers get without caffeine and designed the building accordingly. The smell of brewing coffee was almost enough to calm me down from the events of the morning. Almost.

I opened the door to my office, set my bag down by my chair, and grabbed my coffee mug from my desk. On my way out the door, I noticed my tracker band was flashing. I held my wrist closer to my eyes to see who was trying to ping me – Justin. Bubbles of anxiety floated up into my throat. I pressed the button that would ignore his call and walked the rest of the way to the kitchen.

The coffee settled some of the butterflies in my stomach and I felt myself relax. I stood there for about a minute, eyes closed, smelling the coffee and thinking about the day ahead. I had a meeting to get to, but that wasn't for another couple of hours – plenty of time to get some research done if I just forced myself to focus. I opened my eyes and immediately regretted it.

Hung up on the fridge, only a few feet in front of me, was an office-wide invitation to Genny's baby's first birthday party. The picture on the card was of Genny holding her baby, smiling. But there were bags under her eyes from having to get up in the middle of the night. And I couldn't help but remember all of the times Genny had come into work with dried spit-up on her shirt, only to lethargically pick at it when someone pointed it out. I did my best to shake the image out of my head and walked back to my office.

My computer was still on from the night before, with a large error message blinking across the screen that meant my code had broken down at some point. The code was part of a project I was working on to find out where within galaxies habitable planets were most likely to form. If it hadn't encountered the error, it would be done by now. But no one writes a perfect code the first – or second or third – time they try to, so I had to fix my error and start running the code all over again. I had no idea how much longer it would take, but there was plenty of other work to be done while I waited. That's the life of an astronomer: write code, debug code, find something to do while your code takes forever to run, repeat.

I decided that it was a good time to do some work on a paper I was trying to get published about a research project that had wrapped up the week before. Over the last 30 or so years, astronomy research had begun to be done in bigger and more internationally spread collaborations. It was great for the science - there were more brains from more kinds of backgrounds coming up with solutions. But it was an absolute pain to get anything done when all of my choices had to be okayed by a man in India, a woman in Spain, and a man in Australia.

Before I could actually get very far in writing the paper, an alert popped up at the top of my screen – an email from one of my research group members. *Have you finished that proposal yet?* Some of my colleagues at the observatory had noticed that it had been a couple years since I had advised anyone and were pressuring me to change that, so I spent the next hour working on a proposal to get funding to hire a student who could help with my research over the summer.

A little bit after noon, Ashley – one of the members of my galaxies research group – stuck her head in my office and reminded me that it was time for our group's working lunch. Every Friday, the six of us in the building who worked on galaxies would go to lunch in the small town at the bottom of

the observatory hill and update everyone on our research. But when we got to the restaurant, most of them wanted to talk about Genny's baby's party.

"Can you believe he's a year old, already? It seems like just yesterday we threw Genny her maternity leave party."

"I know! I'm thinking of getting him one of those toy truck sets. Do you think he'll like that?"

"Hmmm, that might be dangerous. He could choke on some of the parts."

The conversation was upsetting my stomach, so I took a big gulp of my water and turned all of my attention to the soccer game on the TV in the corner of the restaurant.

My code was done running by the time I got back. The results seemed off to me, but I had made the mistake before of doubting accurate results because of my expectations. That mistake cost me a first author paper, so I wouldn't throw anything out until I was absolutely sure it was wrong. Before I could convince myself of anything, though, my tracker beeped – I was late for my meeting. I grabbed a notebook and pen, struggled to decide whether or not I should grab one of the bottles of sweet tea from beneath my desk, decided against it, and ran out the door.

I was the last one to make it to the meeting, which didn't really surprise anyone. My usual seat at the back corner of the table – the only spot besides the head of the table where I could see everyone's faces – had been left empty for me. The Observatory Director, Tony, was sitting at the head of the table, reading messages on the holographic screen in front of him. When he noticed that all of the seats around the table were filled, he blinked the screen away and cleared his throat.

"We received a message from NASA this morning," he said, in his confident and booming voice that could make the falsest of statements sound like the truth. He paused for a few moments, took a deep breath, and continued. "Aliens have made contact with Earth."

What do you do when one sentence turns your reality into a science fiction world? I had no idea, but apparently everyone else did. The room around me exploded – well, not really, but it may as well have for all of the chaos that followed Tony's announcement. Some people were shouting, others were jumping up and down, and one man had actually started crying. And all I could do was sit there, taking it all in.

Most of the noise was directed at Tony – questions about the aliens, demands and pleas to be included in the mission, outrage that we hadn't been told sooner. Tony stood up and, with his loudest and most commanding voice, told everyone to sit down. And everyone did, like dogs who had gone out of control and been called back with an order from their obedience trainer.

"Clearly, this is surprising news for all of us." Tony sat back in his chair

at the head of the table. "But that's no reason to lose your heads. In the coming weeks, more information will be shared with everyone." He moved his eyes slowly around the circle of faces. "Now, if you think you can be productive after hearing this, go back to work. If you're too shocked to get anything done, ping a car and go home. Either way, leave this room."

I stood up to go, but saw a flashing light on my tracker band. I checked it to see who had messaged me – Tony. *Stay*, it said. I sat back down and Tony walked around the table to stand over me.

My dark brown eyes met his piercing cobalt blue ones, settled over a narrow nose and an almost-too-white smile. Tony wasn't a bad boss – he wasn't even a bad person. But every time I was alone with him, I couldn't help but think of all of the portraits that hung on the walls of this building, portraits of old white men who had directed the observatory. I thought of the ghosts of white men past whose eyes seemed to follow me everywhere I walked. Despite decades' worth of efforts in the community to "increase diversity" and "be more inclusive," the demographics of the field hadn't changed much.

I could tell he was waiting for me to say something, but when I tried to speak, it was high-pitched and squeaky. I wished for a second that I had brought that bottle of sweet tea and spent the next second clearing my throat to try and return some of its moisture.

"Way to rip off the band-aid," I said, gesturing for him to sit down.

"Well, I didn't know how else to do it."

The shock started to wear off and the questions flooded in.

What do they want?

How did they get here?

What do they look like?

But I didn't know which to ask first. I opened my mouth to ask one, whichever one came out, but Tony stopped me by putting an envelope in my hand. I looked down to see the familiar blue star-spangled circle with its red rocket tails. Why was I getting a letter from NASA? I was about to rip the envelope open, but Tony stopped me again.

"Everyone else has probably left by now. You should leave too. Don't worry about trying to keep the secret. The whole story will be on the news today. Well, everything except what's in that letter. Go home. Read it over. And if you don't come back on Monday, I'll know what you decided."

So I left the conference room, envelope in hand, and walked to my office. Part of me wanted to finish the work I was doing before I went to the meeting, to prove to myself that my whole world hadn't changed. Another part of me wanted to get the hell out of there. That second part won. I called a car with my tracker band and waited outside for it to come.

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I read the letter over and over again in the car. By the time I got home, I had its contents memorized.

Justin was surprised to see me home so early. I took advantage of his shocked silence to tell him that I didn't want to continue the fight from that morning. He started to smile and I realized he thought I was taking his side.

"No, no. We're going to continue that discussion later. But there are more important things to discuss now." He nodded and I handed him the letter. I practically mouthed the words as he read them.

Dear Mrs. Powell it began. I saw him scowl just as I had because he knew I hated it when people chose to address me formally as Mrs. instead of as Dr., especially since I hadn't taken his last name.

We are sure that you will have been informed by now of the events of the last month. An alien race calling themselves the Mowleens have traveled from their home system, what we call EPIC 206032309, and contacted several major research organizations around the world. They are proposing an exchange program.

Given your unique qualifications, we believe that you would be an excellent candidate for such a mission.

The letter went on to say how I should proceed should I want to be considered as a candidate for this exchange program. It did not give any details about the program itself or the aliens who had proposed it.

Justin read the letter a few more times before he looked up, as speechless as I had been in the meeting.

"Say something" I pleaded.

"Shit."

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Justin and I decided it would be best to talk about the letter after we had dinner. We knew it was going to be a difficult conversation and figured we shouldn't make it any worse by adding hunger to the mix.

We each took off our tracker bands and put them on the kitchen counter before we sat down to eat. The conversation was so forced since both of us were trying to avoid both our argument from this morning and the letter, so I was actually relieved when I heard one of our bands pinging in the other room.

Justin jumped up to answer the call and came back holding my band.

"Who is it?" I asked.

He looked down at the face of the band. "Peggy Wilson."

I scowled. Peggy Wilson was the most annoying neighbor I had ever had. She was always telling us our grass was too tall and when she thought we weren't looking, she would let her dog into our yard to do its business and dig up dirt. But she was also the neighbor with the best gossip, so when she called, there was a 50% chance you would be really entertained by whatever she had to say.

"Answer it." That way I wouldn't have to hear her annoying voice myself, but I would get to know what she had to say, entertaining or not.

"Hello, Mrs. Wilson. How are you?" Justin's voice was way more polite than the exasperated expression on his face. "Yes, she is home, actually." He tried to hand me the tracker band and I almost knocked my chair over as I ran to the other side of the room. "...but she's upstairs at the moment. Would you like to leave a message?" As he listened to whatever it was Peggy Wilson had to say, Justin's eyes widened and his shoulders tensed. "I'll ask her. Good night, Mrs. Wilson."

I left the corner of the room where I had been mock hiding and sat back down at the dining room table. "What did she want?" I was wary. Every conversation with Peggy Wilson was unpleasant to some degree, but Justin didn't usually have such strong reactions to them.

"She wanted to know about the aliens."

I could feel my own eyes widening. "Did she know about me? About the letter?" I could see Peggy Wilson poking her nose into our family business, pestering me about whether or not I was going to accept the position before Justin and I had a chance to talk about it ourselves.

Justin shook his head. "No, she saw it on the news and wanted your *professional report*." He said the last bit in a mockery of Mrs. Wilson's uppity accent – the one she claimed she got by living for a few years in London, but which disappeared any time she got tired or upset.

We decided it might be best to finish dinner in the living room so we could watch the news. For the next hour and a half, we got calls from curious neighbors and friends. None of them knew that I had any sort of connection to the aliens beyond being an astronomer, but they all had questions that they were sure I could answer.

"Where did the aliens come from?" Rebecca from down the street wanted to know.

"Do they have three eyes and arms growing out of their heads?" Landon, Justin's gym buddy, asked.

"They better not be here to take our jobs!" That one was from Mr. Riley, an old man who lived down the street and never said anything without yelling, not because his hearing was failing, but because he was always a little bit angry. Everyone in the neighborhood loved him, though.

The calls seemed to stop after the news team moved on to a story about a woman who died while in police custody.

Justin and I cleaned the dishes from dinner, made ourselves some tea, and went to sit in the living room with the TV off.

“Do you want to go?” he asked, breaking the tense silence that had formed.

I rubbed my face with my hand. He wasn’t just asking if I wanted to go to Washington and meet the aliens – he wanted to know if I was going to leave the planet. How do you tell your husband that you’re considering leaving him and the whole life you had built together to go live with aliens? Could he understand the sense of responsibility I felt? Did I fully understand it? “I don’t know,” I answered.

"Well, did Tony tell you how much time you had to think about it?"

I looked down into my cup of tea. Tony had told me I had until Monday. Monday was only two days away. But I knew that if I told Justin that, he would insist on having a big conversation about it right then. I wasn’t ready for that.

"A week."

Justin nodded and we stayed up for another hour, speculating about the aliens and the exchange program that the letter from NASA had mentioned. The letter had given next to no detail about what was actually going on, and the news channels didn’t have much to say either. The only way to find out more would be to respond to the letter.

Justin made it clear that he thought we should wait to make a decision until we heard more about the aliens in the news, and I wasn’t about to disagree with him, so we went to bed.

He fell asleep almost instantly. I wasn’t so lucky. I tossed and turned for about an hour, my thoughts plagued with questions. Eventually, I couldn’t take it anymore. I pulled back the covers and sneaked across the room to the door. On my way down the stairs, I was careful to avoid the creaky centers of each step – like I was in high school all over again. In the living room, I turned on a lamp, picked up the NASA letter, and dialed the number at the bottom of the page.

Someone on the other end of the line picked up after three rings. “Hello. My name is Dakota Powell. I’m calling about some sort of exchange program. . . .”

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The person I talked to said they would send a car on Monday morning to pick me up and take me to the airport where a ticket to Washington D.C.

would be waiting for me. I had a little over 48 hours to figure out how to tell the person I had once promised to devote my life to that I might have just agreed to go live the rest of my life on a different planet.

Well, I obviously couldn't sleep after that. It was about 2:00 in the morning – too early to make breakfast, but not too early for a cup of coffee and a good book. I read until sunrise, which I hadn't been awake to see in years, so I took my (third) cup of coffee out onto my porch and watched it. When it was over, I went back inside and started cooking eggs and bacon, figuring that the smell would wake Justin up. I was right.

I didn't know whether or not I was going to tell him until I heard feet pounding on the stairs. I decided to give him one more day of normalcy. He deserved that much. And, to be honest, I liked that we both felt like we had to walk on eggshells around each other. For the most part, conversation was light in a way that it hadn't been in weeks. The few Justin tried to bring up the letter, I stopped him by offering food or distracted him with a kiss.

We both slept in on Sunday, and when we did wake up, it was storming outside. Neither of us had work to do, so we made brunch and put together a list of movies to watch. It's too easy to keep a secret when you're watching a movie because you're not supposed to talk.

I kept the letter with me all day, hoping it would give me the courage to tell him before I absolutely had to, but before I knew it, we were making dinner and my time had run out.

"I'm going to Washington D.C. in the morning," I blurted as Justin pulled the garlic bread out of the refrigerator. He looked at me and I could see it in his eyes as he moved from confusion to understanding to anger and, finally, to pain.

"We were supposed to wait and make this decision together," he said, with a deep voice that meant he was trying to choke back either tears or shouting, or maybe both.

Even though his voice wasn't loud, I still flinched. This was worse than our fight from a few days ago, because this was that fight and so much more, all wrapped up into one moment. "I know. I know we were. But, babe, you don't understand. There are thousands of astronomers in the country. And they reached out to me. Me! I have to know why."

"You could have asked why on the phone." He slammed the bread down onto the kitchen counter. "No, Dakota, this is about you running away, like you do every time you have a big decision to make."

I looked down at my wedding ring and remembered the week-long impromptu trip to San Francisco I had taken after Justin proposed. I already knew I was going to say yes, but I wasn't ready to say it yet. Back then, I had been running away from something, sure. But this time, I had something

to run *to*.

"I'm not running away from you, Justin. I'm just going to see what the aliens want and why NASA wants me. This isn't me actually agreeing to leave the planet. I'm just a *candidate*, remember?" I waved the NASA letter in the air.

Justin nodded. "Okay, you're right. This is just you going to check out the deal. But what if you get picked, huh? What then?"

I tried to explain to him what this opportunity meant to me. When he asked how my work could be more important to me than him, than the possibility of starting a family together, I stumbled through an answer about how the two couldn't be compared. "I've devoted my entire life to science. To finding out what's out there. And this is my chance to see it for myself. To learn something that can make a difference on Earth!"

I hoped that he could understand, and realized that he probably couldn't. But it was late, and because I hadn't ordered it myself, the car was coming in the morning, whether he wanted it to or not. He knew me well enough to know that once I committed to something, there was almost nothing that could stop me from doing it – except my own self doubts. All he could do was let me go, and take comfort in the fact that if I ended up agreeing to leave Earth, I would insist on coming home first to say goodbye.

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We woke up early – well, it was early for me. Justin was used to waking up at 7 am. We had a quiet breakfast. When my tracker pinged at 9 to let me know the car was waiting outside, I put my dishes in the kitchen sink. I turned to Justin, who was still angry, but he wouldn't let it ruin our goodbye. He opened his arms and I fell into them, burying my face in the sweater he was wearing. I kissed him and turned away quickly – I didn't know if I was trying to prevent him from seeing the tears in my eyes or the excitement. My bags were already by the door, so I picked them up and reached for the handle.

Before I could turn it, Justin put his hand on my shoulder. "Wait, Dakota. I need to know for sure. Are you leaving because of the fight? Because we can work through that."

There were so many reasons for my leaving. One was probably more persuasive than the others. *Should I tell him?*, I thought. *No, I haven't told anyone.* I turned back around, trying to contort my face into something that looked more apologetic than determined. "There's just... something I have to learn."

I opened the door and carried my bags out to the car that was idling on the side of the road, waiting to take me to the airport.

3

Meeting the Boss Iyeena

I stood in the bathroom of my new quarters on Iyeena, staring at the hole in the floor. I didn't know where it went or how the plumbing system in the research worked, but there a familiarly uncomfortable weight in my stomach and I had to do something about it. Luckily, the Mowleean excretory system worked almost exactly the same way as the human one, at least as far as I could tell.

For the first time since being put in my new body, I removed my clothes to get into the shower. I still couldn't find a mirror, so I couldn't see my face, but I could see the rest of me.

I was tall and lean, with dark skin that was so thick I couldn't feel it when I pinched myself. All of the body parts I was used to were there: two each of legs, arms, feet, and hands. But my feet were wide and flat with three little toe nubbins, as if they were meant more for swimming than for running. My hands each had five fingers – one was opposable – but they were slightly curved and there were remnants of something that looked like webbing between them.

When I stepped into the shower stall, the door closed behind me and water started pouring from the holes in the wall that I had examined the night before. The water turned on so quickly that I didn't have time to close my eyes before it hit my face, but I soon found out that I didn't need to. My eyes had some sort of protective lid over them. I scolded myself for not paying more attention to my guides' faces on my tour of the research compound and made a mental note to carefully study the face of whoever I saw next.

As the water ran over me, I thought about the dream I had had the night before – a dream of home, of Justin and the old life that I might never see

again. But I couldn't be too sad, because I knew they weren't. For them, nothing had changed. Justin still had a wife. Earth Dakota probably didn't feel like anything was different. It was just me. Only I had to live with this change.

And if I was going to live with the change, I was going to do it right. I looked around the stall for the button or lever or pedal that would turn the water off. Before I could find it, the water stopped unexpectedly and the door to the stall opened. On instinct, I looked around for a towel, but I didn't need one. My skin seemed to have absorbed the water.

A sweet smell hit my nose when I left the bathroom. It reminded me of Sunday mornings back home, when Justin would make blueberry pancakes for breakfast and I would run down the stairs, lured by their scent. I shook the thought out of my head and went to find the source of the smell.

I looked around the bedroom, but still couldn't find anything that smelled sweet. Giving up, I started to look around the room for clothes. My old ones were piled in a soggy heap on the bathroom floor, wet from water that managed to escape the shower stall. Desperate, I opened the door a crack and peaked into the hallway to see if anyone had left anything there. I found a pile of neatly folded clothes on top of a tray. Breathing a sight of relief, I opened the door wider and bent down to pick up the tray. I realized that I was completely naked and hurried to carry the tray into my room before anyone could see me.

I set the tray down on the bed and put on the clothes – a simple pants-shirt combo, soft with a dark green color and a faint scent that reminded me of cinnamon. Left on the tray was a plate full of some spiky food I didn't recognize – not that I expected to recognize any of the food here – and a note.

The note was hard to read at first. The symbols – which I had never seen before but which this body had presumably grown up reading – kept blurring together, and when that stopped, it took a while for my new brain to make the appropriate associations with each word. I eventually figured out that the card was telling me someone would be by to pick me up when I was ready and lead me to my first meeting.

I wondered how they would know when I was ready and why they hadn't left a time. Maybe keeping strict track of time wasn't as much of a priority for the Mowleens as it was for humans? Whatever the reason, I had no way of knowing when someone would be by to pick me up, so I decided to eat the spiky food until my guide came to get me.

I had just finished the last piece of fruit – I called it fruit because it reminded me of a cross between the grapes and strawberries I ate back on Earth – when I heard a knock at my door. I stood up and walked to the

door, ready for whatever Iyeena had to show me.

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I greeted the guide with what I hoped was a warm smile. I got no reaction in return, but I was able to see, really see, a Mowleeean face for the first time. It was a beautiful balance between sharp angles (cheekbones and chins) and delicate features (soft eyes and a full mouth) that I had only seen on women back home. But that face rested atop broad, muscular shoulders and moved with a quick but confident stride, the likes of which I had only ever seen exhibited by men.

I couldn't figure out what this person was. Hell, I couldn't figure out what *I* was based on my examination in the bathroom earlier. I knew it was rude to ask a person's gender back on Earth, so I decided to err on the side of caution and assume it was rude on Iyeena as well.

I tried to strike up conversation instead. "Hi. How are you?" No response. "That good, huh. Yeah, mine too. I ate a cool spiky fruit. What are those called?" Again, the guide gave no response. "You don't know either? I guess I'll ask someone else. You don't look much like a fruit kind of..." My voice stopped abruptly. "Fruit kind of..." It happened again.

In my head, I was thinking "fruit kind of guy," but when I went to say it aloud, I couldn't. I didn't know why, so I replaced the word and moved on. "Fruit kind of person. I feel like a nice bloody steak would be more your style." I got a sort of grunt in response, and, figuring that was as much as I would get, walked the rest of the way in silence.

The guide led me down so many halls that I completely lost track of where we were. It was like being led through a maze – a maze made out of the same wet, rocky material that the walls of my room were made of. Lost in my own thoughts, I slammed into the guide, who had stopped in front of a large but simple door made out of something gold and metallic and embedded in the hallway wall. The guide knocked once, a sharp sound against the metal of the door, and walked away.

Like all of the doors I had seen so far on Iyeena, none of which had visible handles, this door opened automatically to a large room with bright white walls. My attention was caught and held by movement along the walls as softly glowing symbols swirled their way across my line of sight. The long chains of circles connected by lines looked familiar, but I couldn't figure out why.

Out of the corner of my eye, I saw something large coming toward me and turned to find a tall person standing by my side. "Hello." The person held out their arms, as if to give me a hug. "My name is Landric. I am the head Thinker here at the research compound."

Landric grasped the sides of my face in a form of greeting I hadn't yet encountered on Iyeena. I returned the gesture.

I looked around the rest of the room, wondering if this was an office, a bedroom, or some combination of both. There was a long couch in the corner, opposite a large ornate desk covered with neat stacks of paper. Landric followed my eyes around the room. "The Builders did a beautiful job with this room, didn't they? Of course, it was my design that they used to do so, but you have to admire the skill with which they executed my plan."

I nodded along, even though I didn't know exactly what Thinkers and Builders were. Landric went on to explain that this room was just an office and that most of the people who worked in this research compound lived in a residential section in a different part of the tunnel system. I had been assigned to temporary quarters in the research compound so that I could be monitored before I was sent out into the world.

Still speaking about the tunnel system and the various sections that existed therein, Landric left the room and started walking down the hallway. I had little choice but to follow.

Landric stopped in front of a door that was significantly less grandiose than the last one I had stepped through. Unsurprisingly, the door opened automatically, and I entered a room that was relatively bare except for a large oblong table in the center, surrounded by quietly chattering people and two empty seats. Landric sat in the empty seat that was at the head of the table and motioned for me to take the other empty one a few seats away.

I looked around at the 20 or so Mowleens who surrounded the table. They all had the same basic structure. Large black eyes were set back in skin the same dark reddish-brown color as my own – but which flashed green when the light hit it from certain angles – and they sat over three small slits that reminded me of nostrils. I saw one person twitch and watched as their nostrils flared. The nostril slits sat above a mouth that looked much like a human's until someone pulled back their lips – whether it was a smile, a grimace, or something else, I couldn't tell – and I saw pointy teeth lining their mouth. I couldn't see any ears, but I knew they had to exist since I'd been hearing things since I woke up on this planet. Each person in the room had a strip of hair – of various colors – that started at the top of their head and disappeared under the collar of their shirts. I reached up to see if I was sporting my own colorful mohawk. I was, and it was softer than I thought it would be, but I had no way of knowing what color it was without asking someone, and I hadn't made any friends here. Yet.

Landric called the meeting to order by banging on the table. Everyone immediately fell silent. "Welcome, Visitors," the speech began. "We are pleased to welcome you all to Iyeena, and excited for you all to share with us the knowledge from the Thinkers on your home planets."

So the people around me were part of the exchange program, too. I looked around at them again, this time thinking less about what they looked like here and more about what they may have looked like back on their respective planets.

"You all come to us from very different worlds," Landric continued. A screen had appeared on the wall at the back of the room, and pictures were flashing by as Landric spoke, showing pictures of what I believed to be the home worlds of the people sitting around me. As I looked back and forth between the screen and their faces, I saw eyes widen in recognition and lips curl with pangs of homesickness.

"One of you even comes from a planet around a mid-temperature star, way hotter than the typical cool star like the Iyeenan sun. So welcome to average." I felt my own twinge of nostalgia when I realized Landric was talking about me. The star that Iyeena orbited is about half the temperature of Earth's sun, but Earth's solar system is actually probably pretty rare. Most stars in the galaxy are much cooler than Earth's sun.

"You each come to us as experts in different fields: biology, geology, astronomy, chemistry, which is my own area of expertise." At this last one, Landric gave a smug smile, as if chemistry were the ultimate science and the rest of us were just playing at being scientists in our joke fields. Suddenly, the symbols I had seen scrawled over the walls in Landric's office made sense. They were drawings of organic molecules, like I had seen in my college chem class. "We're in the medical sector now," Landric continued, "but each field has its own space. You each should have been given a tour of the sector that specializes in your own fields when you arrived here. Now you will all get a chance to tour the other sectors and get a small taste of all the research Iyeena has to offer."

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There were two other astronomers in the group of Visitors I found myself in. We were joined by three others: a chemist and two biologists. Once everyone was split into groups, we were led away by a guard toward the first stop on our grueling tour of all eight sectors of the entire research compound.

The group was quiet at first, but conversation started to pick up as we made our way to our first destination: the biology sector. Luckily, this tour guide, whose name sounded like Ju-lee-ay, was much more talkative than the one who had led me to Landric's office.

I had so many questions. Where did they get their food? Did they use a kind of currency? What about government? But Juleeay was already answering one of the other Visitors' question about Landric's position in the compound.

"...in charge of everything – not just in the research compound but everywhere. Of course there are others who work with ka to help form and enforce policies, but ka is one of the brightest Thinkers on Iyeena. What good is a leader if ka cannot think?"

Juleeay kept mentioning a person named Ka, but I hadn't heard the name yet during my time on Iyeena, so I asked "Juleeay, who is Ka?"

"What do you mean?"

"You said people work with Ka to make policies. I thought Landric was in charge."

"Yes. Landric is in charge. Ka is a great Thinker."

"So Ka is Landric?" I asked, thinking that it must be Landric's official title.

"No."

"Then who is..."

I was frustrated when I started the sentence and even more frustrated when I couldn't finish it. I was trying to ask "who is he," but the word wouldn't come out of my mouth, just like before. I thought about why this would be happening. Why could I think certain words, but not say them?

"Ka is not a person. Ka is what we say to talk *about* a person."

Of course! Ka wasn't a name. It was a Mowleean word that my brain wasn't translating into English because an English equivalent didn't exist. Now I also understood what was happening to my words on their way from my brain to my mouth.

I was more or less thinking in English, my native language. When I spoke, the language center of my physical Mowleean brain chose the words that most appropriately matched what I was thinking. That meant that if I were to think of a word or concept that didn't exist in Mowleean, I wouldn't be able to speak it. And if a Mowleean said a word that didn't reflect a concept that existed on Earth, it would just sound like gibberish to me. I couldn't say "guy" or "he" in Mowleean, because those things didn't exist – at least, not in the same way they existed back on Earth – and I'm sure I would find more things I couldn't say out loud as I spent more time on Iyeena.

One more mystery solved, I tuned back in to Juleeay's responses to the other Visitors' questions. I learned so many things! Most of the tunnels that made up the compound were old lava tubes left over from violent volcano activity long, long ago. Life on Iyeena had begun underwater – the only place where it would be protected from their star's high magnetic activity – and

only emerged onto land fairly recently, which explained the webbed fingers and flat feet. If my memory of aquatic biology on Earth served me well, it also explained why they didn't have words to differentiate between genders. Back home, it's not uncommon for marine animals to be hermaphroditic – to be able to change their sex based on certain conditions. It certainly explained why I hadn't been able to find any defining sex characteristics in the shower. And trust me, I looked.

One of the biologists asked how long the average Mowleean lifespan was. "About 50 burn-throughs," replied Juleeay. The rest of us looked at ka with confused looks on our faces, so ka continued to explain that Mowleens kept track of time using an asteroid that regularly appeared every so often, like Halley's Comet back on Earth. I had no idea how long a burn-through was, but I was awed by this method of keeping time and by the time I regained my composure, someone else was asking a question.

Soon, we arrived at the entrance to the biology sector. They showed us the zoology section first and I was too busy staring at animals, some of which I was sure I wouldn't even be able to create in my dreams, to ask questions. There were winged animals that reminded me of birds back on Earth, except they didn't have beaks. There were animals that walked on three legs, creatures designed to look like they had several pairs of eyes, entire groups of animals with protective shielding and spikes running down their backs. I could have spent hours exploring, but Juleeay called that it was time to move on before I had time to explore even half of what was there.

We spent the rest of the day visiting each of the eight sectors, always seeming to spend more time travelling between the sectors than we ever spent exploring inside them. By the end of the day, everything seemed to blur together and I was so overwhelmed by information that I couldn't have told the difference between a Mowleean particle accelerator and a core of rock drilled from Iyeena's surface if I tried.

The only sector that really stood out to me as strange was the first one: the biology sector. In all of the other sectors, Juleeay had let us Visitors explore wherever we wanted to. There were no doors we couldn't open and no turns we couldn't take, provided we stayed within shouting distance of Juleeay so we didn't get too lost. But in the biology sector, there were several tunnels marked as off-limits. When the chemist asked Juleeay about them, ka mumbled something about dangerous pathogens and ushered us back into the grand tunnel that connected all of the sectors in the research compound.

Juleeay led our group back to the meeting room where we had all met. Landric was there, waiting for all of the groups to return so that ka – now that I knew about "ka," my interactions with people could be so much less distracted and confused – could tell us Visitors what happened next.

“The next time we meet, you will be led from your temporary quarters here in the research compound back to this room. From here, you will be led outside of the tunnels to the Iyeenan surface. Now go get some rest. There are busy times ahead.”

I wanted to laugh at the idea that I would have the energy to do anything but rest, but, ironically, I didn't even have the energy to do that. I followed the same taciturn guide who had led me to Landric's office back through the maze that led to my quarters.

Once inside, I shed my clothes, stepped on the pedal by the bed that turned off the lights in the ceiling, and crawled beneath a feathery thing that I assumed was a blanket. Before I fell asleep, I spared a second to wonder how long I had actually been awake. I had no sense of how time passed here. Maybe I would understand more after the next tour, when I actually got to see the Iyeenan sun.

4

Sun Pulling Earth

My first week and a half at NASA were full of interviews and training sessions with the Mowleeanans.

I wasn't able to actually meet them because they were communicating with us remotely from wherever they had stationed themselves to observe us, but there was plenty of communicating. We talked about my research and they tried to answer my questions about Mowleean history and culture. Those sessions never really worked because they just talked about different technological advancements their scientists had made. They never responded when I asked about religion, art, or social structure. I eventually gave up on asking and vowed to learn as much as I could once I actually got to Iyeena.

I asked once why it was called an exchange program. Were the Mowleeanans planning on leaving someone here? How could they if they couldn't even set foot on our planet? Apparently, it was an exchange of information, not of people. I was going there to share my expertise and to gather theirs. In turn, the Mowleeanans were leaving some of their technology on Earth for scientists to study, and I would tell them more when I came back.

The interviews were fun. The Mowleeanans' contact with Earth had brought astronomy to the forefront of the public's eye. Talk show hosts had cancelled appointments with major celebrities to make time for me, and they actually wanted to hear about the science! About my results and conclusions, not just my love life or where I bought my clothes.

I talked about my college thesis work more times in those 10 days than I had in all of the 15 years since I had written it. My first interviewer, a talk show host who was so well known that she had her own perfume line and cookbook – not that I could understand how those two business franchises fit together – even got her hands on an old print version of my thesis and

invited me onto her show to talk about it.

The show was called Chick Chat. On the day we filmed – in front of a live audience, might I add – the set was space themed, with planets depicted on the screen behind us as they whizzed around their host stars. Before I knew it, the cameraman was counting down from 5. I was about to be on TV.

"Welcome to Chick Chat," she started after the theme music faded away. "I'm your host, Shannon Sessions, and I'm sitting here today with the country's most famous astronomer, Dakota Powell!" The crowd cheered. "If you don't already know who Dakota is, then clearly you've been living under a rock for the last week." The crowd laughed. "But just in case, Dakota here has been selected to represent Earth on the first ever mission to an alien planet. What's it called again, Dakota?"

She turned to me and smiled. And in that moment, when I knew I had to speak – there was no alternative – everything was okay. "Iyeena," I said with a smile. "And I'm just a candidate for the mission. The Mowleean also contacted Russia and China, so we'll just have to wait and see who they choose."

"How could they choose anyone but you?!" There was a murmur of agreement from the crowd.

"Well," Shannon said, leaning toward me like we were the closest of friends, "before we get to the science, we want to learn about you. What do you like? What are you about? Who *is* Dakota Powell?"

The crowd was silent, waiting for my response, and if I'm not mistaken, they had leaned toward me too.

"Uhhh, I'm from Oregon. Right outside of Portland, so there weren't really enough stars for me to know astronomy was a thing until I went to college. I found it pretty late, really. Just stumbled into an intro class and the rest is history. I'm actually more interested in galaxies now, but my college advisor really wanted me to study exo..."

Shannon laughed, interrupting me. "Oh, Dakota! I asked you who you are and you started talking about work? You know what they say, all work and no play..." The crowd thought this was hilarious, the awkward but well-meaning scientist who devoted her life to her work. "What do you do for fun? Is there a man in the picture? Or a woman?!" Then, to the audience, "We don't judge." *Wink.*

I looked down at my hands, embarrassed that I hadn't thought to mention Justin, but Shannon played it off to the crowd as shyness. "Oh, there is someone! Tell us! It's just us girls here." *Winning smile.*

"I have a husband, actually. His name is Justin." The crowd loved that. Some people actually chanted for a photo of the two of us to come onto the

screen, but I hadn't thought to give the studio one.

Shannon quieted them down and apologized for not having a picture to show them. "And what does Justin think about all this? Does he brag about you to all of his work friends?"

I didn't know what to tell her. Clearly I couldn't tell her the truth, that Justin and I had been fighting for weeks before I got NASA's letter and that he hadn't wanted me to come here. I looked down at my hands in my lap, letting my hair hide some of my face from the crowd. Lucky for me, Shannon was either a very nice woman or very good at her job – or both – and saved me from having to say anything at all.

"Just look at her, ladies. So in love she can't even speak. Let's move on before she's so lost in thoughts of her blissful marriage that we can't get anything else out of her."

The crowd laughed, and Shannon laughed with them, long enough for me to compose myself. "So, I hear you were chosen for this mission because you wrote your senior thesis on this planet when you were in college." I nodded. "In fact," she said, reaching beneath her chair, "I have a copy of your thesis right here."

She held the book out to me and I just stared at it. "Do you want me to read from it?" I definitely would have, but it didn't seem like the most entertaining thing to do on a live talk show. Even professional astronomers would be bored by that.

The ridiculousness of my question seemed to catch Shannon off guard. "Oh, goodness, no! Viewers are pinging in their questions for you as we speak."

I nodded and finally accepted the offered book, figuring it would give me something to do with my hands while I answered the questions. I had always been pretty comfortable with speaking in public as long as I got to plan what I was going to say, but you can't really plan for questions. They're too out of your control.

But there was nothing I could do about it in that moment, so I met Shannon's eyes and smiled. "Well, let's not keep them waiting!"

Shannon laughed and directed my attention to the screen behind us, where a video started playing.

"Hi, Shannon! Hi, Dakota! My name's Morgan." It looked like Morgan was sitting in a kitchen and I could hear the sound of pots clanging in the background. "Dakota, my boyfriend and I have been talking all week about what the aliens look like. He's convinced they're tiny grey creatures with huge heads. Please tell me he's wrong!"

The screen went dark and Shannon turned to me, waiting for my answer.

"Uh, well, I haven't actually met the Mowleens because they can't survive our atmosphere. Something about too much nitrogen in the air. So I don't know what they look like."

I shot Shannon an apologetic look. I knew it wasn't the most exciting answer, but I couldn't lie.

"Surely you must have some idea what they look like!" Shannon pointed to the copy of my thesis resting in my lap. "What does the science tell you?"

I looked over into the wings of the stage where Charles was standing to watch the interview. Of course I had my theories about what the Mowleens would look like, but was I really allowed to say them out loud on television? Charles nodded, giving his permission. I cleared my throat before I answered.

"Okay, so the most important thing to know is that the planet is tidally locked to its sun, so the..."

"Woah, woah, woah!" Shannon interrupted. "Dakota, you're going to have to explain that. Tidally locked?"

"Right. Okay, so, a planet is tidally locked when one side of the planet is always facing its sun. And it's not just planets! The moon is tidally locked to the Earth. It happens because the gravity of the bigger object will pull on the smaller one in different directions until it eventually reaches that equilibrium."

I held up my fists and moved one around the other, pulling it back and forth as if it were becoming tidally locked. Then I realized it wasn't a very helpful visual aid and let my hands fall back into my lap, wishing I had a video to show on the screen behind me.

Shannon encouraged me to keep going.

"So, the planet – Iyeena – is tidally locked to its sun. The side facing the sun would be way too hot to host life, so the Mowleens likely live on the side where it's always nighttime."

"And what does that have to do with their appearance?"

"Well, Shannon. You know those fish who live so deep in the ocean that the light can't reach them? What are they called? With the... the thing?" I dangled my hand in front of my face, then put it away when I realized I was making a fool of myself on national television.

Shannon shook her head, clueless, and turned to the audience. "Do any of you know?"

The cameramen turned to scan the faces of the audience. Someone yelled out, "Angler fish!"

I pointed to where I thought the answer had come from. "Yes! The angler fish! I imagine the Mowleens have something like that little lightbulb dangling in front of their face." The crowd laughed at that. "And it has to be pretty cold on that side of the planet, since it doesn't get any sun. So I

also imagine that they're covered in fur." I looked into the camera. "Morgan, to answer your question, I think the Mowleens look like really furry angler fish."

Cathleen from Colorado wanted to know if the Mowleens could read minds. I said they hadn't done anything to make me think they could.

Justina from Texas wanted to know how they found us. I told her they had intercepted some of our earliest radio broadcasts and followed the signal back to Earth.

Isabella from Ohio asked what they ate. I laughed and said "Hopefully not humans" before I realized my mistake and tried to take it back. "No, no! I'm sure they have their own source of food on Iyeena. If they didn't, they wouldn't have survived long enough to contact us." That seemed to calm the crowd down, but I stayed away from evil alien jokes for the rest of the interview.

When the hour was up, Shannon thanked me for coming on the show and asked if I would sign her copy of my thesis. I did and waved goodbye to the crowd as I left the stage.

Charles met me backstage. "Isn't there some NASA policy against pulling answers out of my butt when it comes to aliens?"

He shook his head. "No one watching that show is ever going to meet the Mowleens, so they have no way of ever finding out if you were wrong. You could have said they were giant flying centipedes who shot laser beams out of their five eyes and we would have backed you up. But thanks for keeping it pretty reasonable."

I stood in shock and watched as Charles walked away before I ran to catch up. He was my ride back to headquarters.

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I got so wrapped up in the excitement, so distracted by my – and by my science's – newfound fame that I forgot to call home. I almost forgot I had a home to call until my tracker pinged the night after my interview on Chick Chat.

I answered the ping. When I heard Justin's voice on the other end, I felt something tighten in my chest. "Hey, Kota," he said with such bitterness in his voice. The tight feeling in my chest was guilt. Guilt at forgetting to call my husband. Guilt at putting my work first. Guilt at not feeling guilty before this moment.

I apologized for not calling sooner and started to tell him what I'd been doing and what I'd learned. But he didn't want to hear any of it. "When are you coming home?"

I paused. With all of the questions I had asked since coming to Washington, the one thing I hadn't asked was when I would get to go home to my family. "I don't know," I answered.

My tracker pinged again, leaving behind nothing but the sound of silence.

5

Breaking the Surface Iyeena

It didn't take me as long to get ready because I knew how things worked. The water in the shower didn't surprise me, and there were clothes and food piled outside my chamber door again when I was done. The clothes felt just like the ones I had worn before, but they were charcoal grey instead of green. The food was the same spiky red fruit, and I didn't have to waste any time trying to figure out which parts were edible and which weren't. I wondered if this fruit was the only kind of food they had on Iyeena since I hadn't eaten anything else since I woke up.

As I was cracking open one of the last fruits, I heard a knock at my door and jumped up to answer it.

When I opened the door, I was excited to see Juleeay standing there instead of the silent guard who had led me around the compound before. I looked past Juleeay and saw four other people standing behind ka, all of whom I recognized as other Visitors. Looking more closely at their faces, I recognized one of them as one of the other astronomers and fell into step with ka as Juleeay led us away from my door.

"Hi, my name's Teer," the other astronomer said, holding out the three middle fingers on ka left hand and moving as if ka meant to touch them to my forehead. Surprised, I stepped back. Teer looked down in embarrassment and ka hand dropped to ka side. "Sorry, that's how we greet people where I'm from."

"No, it's okay! I was just surprised." I held out the three middle fingers on my own left hand and reached out to touch Teer's forehead. Teer bared ka top teeth in what I interpreted as a smile. I then held out my right hand and motioned for ka to grasp it in a handshake. "This is how we greet people where I'm from," I explained. Then I let go and gripped ka head the way

Landric had gripped mine when we first met. "And I think this is how they greet each other here." Teer smiled again and we both ran to catch up with the rest of the group before they turned and we lost track of them forever in this maze.

I tried to keep track of where Juleeay was leading us, but we took so many turns and passed so many identical patches of wall that we could have been going in circles for all I knew. Still, not even that could diminish my excitement because we were on our way to the Iyeenan surface.

Teer and I passed the time by exchanging descriptions of our home planets. Ka was from a planet that ka called Odahi, a large but underpopulated planet with harsh weather and giant crops. At least, that's how Teer described it. I wondered if it was that the crops were actually that large or if Teer's people were just tiny, but I didn't want to ask in case it was an offensive question.

Before I completely ruled out asking but after I had grown tired of walking, Juleeay stopped in front of a rather unimpressive door. No, it was more of a hatch, really. It was small and made out of a dull silvery metal and the handle that Juleeay pulled to open it was giant lever like the kind I would find on the door of a walk-in freezer back on Earth.

The door opened and I caught my first whiff of fresh Iyeenan air. It was warm, dry, and smelled faintly of fish.

I walked away from the door and looked around. I don't know what I was expecting, but the sight – thrilling though it was – didn't surprise me.

Everything was red. Or maybe it's better to say that everything had a red light shining on it. I looked to my right and caught my first glimpse of the Iyeenan sun. It looked just like the setting sun back on Earth – big and red – except it was *huge*. Even hidden behind mountains and clouds, I could tell it would take up so much more space on the sky than the sun did back home, which made sense since Iyeena was closer to its sun than Earth was to its.

I realized then what my expectation had been. The Iyeenan sun is what astronomers on Earth call an M dwarf star. It's cooler, smaller, dimmer, and – most importantly – redder than Earth's sun, so I had expected everything to look red. And it did! But not because the star was an M dwarf – because it was sunset.

Every star has its own spectrum – a measurement of how much energy the star emits at different wavelengths. Humans evolved to see in the range of wavelengths where Earth's sun emits the most energy. That's what we call the visual range. Of course the Mowleean would have done the same! To my old human eyes, everything on Iyeena would have looked really red all the time, but to my new Mowleean ones, everything looked normal. My

visual range had simply shifted further down the spectrum.

It was frustrating to have to figure this kind of stuff out on my own. I could have asked Juleeay to explain some if it, but ka wouldn't have been able to give me clear answers. It would have been like trying to learn a foreign language from someone who didn't speak my native one. Still, it was exciting when I did manage to figure something out. So, satisfied, I turned my attention back to the land around me.

In front of me was a giant plain of what I can only describe as grit. Plants sprouted from the ground, but they were few and far between. Off into the distance, close enough that I would have been able to walk to it but far enough that I would have complained about doing so, I could see steam rising up from a small lake. Patches of light moved lazily across the plane, and when I looked up, I saw that they were the result of a few gaps between giant, fluffy clouds that all but covered the sky.

Between the clouds, I tried to find a moon in the sunset sky, but I couldn't find anything. Many astronomers back on Earth were convinced that moons were crucial to a planet's habitability. A few astronomers even devoted their lives to hunting for moons around other planets. Right before I left, David Kipping had discovered his first potentially habitable exomoon.

Juleeay walked up behind me. "This whole plane used to be a lake that stretched all the way to where the door is," ka said. "Legends say this is where my people first emerged from the water." I turned, hoping ka would say more about the legend, but ka wouldn't meet my eyes. "We're not supposed to believe the legends, though." Juleeay turned to walk away, but I called out to ka.

"Wait!" I looked up. "Do you have a..." I knew the answer to the question as soon as I couldn't ask it. The Mowleean didn't have a word for "moon," so clearly they didn't have one. I couldn't wait to take that knowledge back home! I realized Juleeay was staring at me, waiting for me to finish asking my question. "Never mind." I smiled. Juleeay cocked ka head to the side – a kind of Mowleean shrug? – and walked away, the ground crunching beneath the special shoes that we had all put on before we left the compound.

Far beyond the lake, I could see a mountain range, but it was blurry, like I was looking through a cloud of smog. I turned back toward the door to the compound to see where the other Visitors had gone. Two of them – I thought I remembered Landric introducing them as chemists the day before – were crouching together, examining the grit as one of them let it flow through ka fingers. The third – a botanist maybe, or a biologist? – was slowly making ka way to one of the few plants that had managed to survive in this environment. I saw Teer standing alone several steps away, gazing out toward the mountains, and went to stand next to ka.

"You see that really tall one?" I nodded. "That's where they used to put all of their telescopes."

I squinted, trying to see if I could make out any telescope outlines. I thought I saw one, a shape that looked too smooth, too planned to be part of the natural mountain skyline. "They must be so far away! I can barely make them out."

Teer turned to me. "It's the atmosphere. It's so thick it makes it hard to see that far away." Ka elbowed me in the side. "I heard you studied this planet back on yours. What, you mean to tell me you didn't know anything about its atmosphere? What kind of lazy research do they do back on Earth, anyway?"

I laughed – well, I think I laughed – at the irony of the situation. It sounded more like a gurgling purr in my chest than the raucous "ha ha ha" I was used to. A few years after I graduated from college, a telescope was launched into orbit, the James Webb Space Telescope. JWST was supposed to study the atmospheres of habitable exoplanets, but because my research in college had concluded that this planet wasn't habitable, no one ever tried to study it with JWST data. Oh, how wrong I had been.

"Back when I was studying this planet," I said, "we didn't have the technology to see the atmospheres of planets as small and as far away as Iyeena. We didn't even think life would be able to form here." I looked at Teer. "But if the Odahians have any tricks up their sleeves to make sure they never make that kind of mistake, I'd love to hear about it." Ka returned my gurgling purr but didn't tell me anything about how to better study planet atmospheres. I didn't really mind.

Juleeay called all of the Visitors together near the entrance to the compound, but before ka could say what ka wanted to say, one of the chemists pointed toward a mountain range in the opposite direction from the ones Teer and I had just been looking at. I realized we were surrounded on three sides by mountains. "What's beyond those?" the chemist asked.

Following the chemist's finger, Juleeay turned around. "I don't know. You'd have to ask a Getter." All of the Visitors looked at each other to see if anyone knew what she was talking about. None of us did. Juleeay kept talking. "But the highest peak in that range is actually really special. It's the volcano that formed the oldest caverns and tunnels in the compound. Legend says the first Mowleens found those caves and expanded the tunnel system as their population grew."

I wondered what legend it was that Juleeay kept mentioning and why no one had talked about it before. More than that, why had Juleeay acted earlier like ka was breaking some sort of rule by talking about the legend?

Juleeay started fidgeting uncomfortably and turned all of our attention

to the setting sun. "We're actually really lucky that we were able to explore the surface at all. We had to wait for the sun to fall behind the mountains."

"What do you mean?" I asked. "How long are your..." I was trying to ask how long an Iyeenan day was, but my inability to say the last word told me that the Mowleean didn't have a concept of what a day was. How did they keep track of time? How did they know when to wake up? I had never occurred to me that something as simple as a day was a consequence of being born on a planet with a steady rotation speed. Unlike "ka," this loss in translation was far from convenient, and I decided that every time I woke up, it would be a new day, even if I couldn't call it that out loud.

I started over. "How often does the sun set behind the mountains?"

"It changes," Juleeay said. "It happens less and less frequently." I waited for more of an explanation, but when it became clear that none was coming, I nodded and Juleeay continued. "A few cycles ago..."

This time, Teer interrupted. "Cycles?"

I looked at Juleeay, hoping and expecting to get a glimpse of what annoyance looked like on a Mowleean face. Anyone else would have been irked that we were asking so many questions, but the toothy grimace I had started to recognize as a Mowleean smile never left ka face.

"Every time Iyeena travels once around the sun, a cycle has passed. There are nearly 400 cycles in a single burn-through."

Teer probably thanked Juleeay, but I didn't hear it because I was working through some math in my head. I remembered from my research that Iyeena orbited its sun about once every four Earth days. That meant that one burn-through was a little more than four Earth years, so the average Mowleean lifespan was 200 Earth years! So many of my questions were closer to being answered now – how the Mowleean had been able to become so scientifically advanced, how they had managed to put together a centuries-lasting interplanetary exchange program. Excited about this fact but not wanting to miss too much of what Juleeay had to say, I turned my attention back to ka.

"...saying, a few cycles ago, a large meteorite landed just beyond that mountain range. It took the Getters a full cycle to retrieve it and bring it back, but the Builders certainly were pleased."

The Visitor who may or may not have been a biologist spoke up. "Is that all they do, the Getters? Go and... get things?"

Juleeay's smile faltered for a fraction of a moment. "What do you mean 'all they do'?" The Getters may not make the things we use everyday, and they're certainly not responsible for coming up with the ideas that keep our society running. But what they do is important. Without them, the Builders wouldn't have anything to work with and the Thinkers would have nothing

more than thoughts to show for their troubles. We would be nowhere without the Getters, and people in this compound would do well to remember that."

Not sure how to respond to Juleeay's sudden and completely unexpected show of any emotion other than pure joy, we Visitors grumbled some sort of collective response and looked anywhere but at ka. Sensing our discomfort, Juleeay announced that it was getting dark and then ushered us through the door and back into the compound.

As I was walking through the doorway, I noticed something scratched into the lintel. It looked like a triangle with a vertical line running down the middle.

The rest of the group was already several steps ahead of me. Teer looked back and motioned for me to hurry up. I didn't want to be stranded here in one of the outermost reaches of the compound, so I had no choice but to run and catch up.

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Juleeay had been given instructions to take all of us back to the medical sector for one of the checkups Lorana had warned me about.

We were all separated and sent to our own doctors. I was happy to see a familiar face after all of the new ones I had seen while walking around the compound and greeted Lorana when ka walked to the desk where I was waiting. Ka smiled and touched my head in what I had come to think of as a Mowleean greeting. "I'm surprised you remember me."

I felt my stomach give its now-familiar gurgling purr and met Lorana's eye. "I don't know how I could forget the first alien I'd ever seen," I said, almost without thinking. Lorana broke eye contact and I realized what I had said. "That didn't come out..."

"I know," ka said reassuringly. "I'm not offended. It's just that you're the alien here, not me."

I nodded and waited silently for Lorana to fetch ka assistants so they could start running their tests.

All in all, it was exactly like a regular checkup I would get back on Earth. They tested the normal things – vitals, senses, memory, etc. – and took a few fluids. The only difference was the fact that my brain was connected to some machine the entire time. When I asked one of Lorana's assistants what it was for, all I got was some vague answer about needing to monitor my download. I didn't understand why they were monitoring my brain download now when everything had been running smoothly ever since I got here, but after getting a few more unhelpful answers to my questions, I kind of gave up.

At the end of my visit, Lorana handed me a letter with an official-looking stamp on it and told me someone would be asking for it later. Leading me

to the door, ka asked the (apparently) universally obligatory "Do you have any questions?"

Almost as a reflex, I shook my head no, but as Lorana turned away I realized it was borderline irresponsible of me to turn down information when I was alone on a planet light years away from home. "Actually, I have a ton. Do you have time to sit?"

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Moments later, I was in Lorana's private office, with the same bright white walls and harsh lighting as the rest of the lab. Lorana gestured for me to sit in one of the chairs. I sat. Ka didn't. I asked myself whether or not it was rude to be the only one in the room in a seat. Then, since I didn't know the customs here, I asked myself if I was tired enough to need a seat. The answer was no, which seemed strange. I looked up and realized that Lorana had been watching me the whole time I had been caught up in my mind, thinking. I mean, of course ka was watching me. There wasn't really anything else in the office to catch and hold anyone's attention. I didn't know if Mowleens could blush, but if they could, I'm sure I was blushing all the way to wherever my ears were.

Not wanting to keep Lorana waiting any longer than I already had, I blurted out, "Why aren't I tired?" I felt myself blush even more. "I mean, how long have I been here, on Iyeena?"

"A cycle and a half."

I nodded along and was about to move on before I realized what that meant. "A cycle and a half?!" That was more than six Earth days. "But I've only slept twice! I've only eaten a handful of fruit things! How am I not exhausted and starving?"

Lorana blinked slowly and thoroughly, as if, up until this moment, every other blink I had ever seen on everybody else hadn't quite done the job. I actually looked at Lorana then and saw that everything about ka seemed intentional. Ka shoulders were held back and ka arms were kept open, almost inviting, as if to seem non-threatening. Ka face was soft, but attentive. Everything about Lorana screamed – subtly, but unmistakably, once you knew it was there – purpose.

"I've read that people on your planet can't go long without rest. Mowleens typically sleep only once per cycle. The length of that sleep varies from person to person, and there are no typical rest times since we live underground and have no natural light source to tie us to any specific rhythm. You have actually been sleeping more than is typical for my people because your brain has been under a considerable amount of stress, adapting to the download."

I nodded to show that I was understanding and absorbing the information.

"As for food, Mowleean typically eat several times between rest periods. We have been feeding you rambuut, a kind of superfood we developed that releases energy slowly enough that you only need to eat once or twice per cycle. It's not a sustainable eating pattern in the long run, but Landric insists we feed it to Visitors when they first arrive so as not to waste your time."

I couldn't be sure, but I thought ka voice was a bit deeper and more... venomous than it had been before, and the room felt a little warmer. I had more questions, but I suddenly felt uncomfortable, enclosed in this tiny space with a person who, for some reason unbeknownst to me, was now looking at me as if ka was personally offended by my presence.

I stood up and made my way toward the door to Lorana's office. "That was all you wanted to know?"

One hand on the door, I thought of saying yes, but I was curious and I figured it was a harmless enough question, so I asked "Where are my ears?"

Lorana reached out ka hand. It took everything I had not to flinch away. "Right here," ka said, touching a spot near the base of my neck, almost covered by my strip of hair.

Ka finger was so warm I whelped in surprise and practically ran out the door into the lab. Lorana's assistants looked up at me but I avoided eye contact and made my way to the dark hallway where a guard was waiting to take me back to my quarters.

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Once inside my room, I opened the letter Lorana had given me. I read it slowly since it took longer for my hybrid brain to translate text into concepts than sounds. The gist of it was that I was healthy enough to enter the greater Mowleean society.

I didn't know what I was supposed to do. Wait in my room until someone came to take me to my new home? Deliver the letter to someone to let them know I was ready to go? I figured it couldn't be the latter since the guard had brought me back to my room and I doubted I was allowed to go gallivanting alone through the halls of the research sector.

But I'm awful at both following rules and entertaining myself, so I chose to gallivant. It's not like I had anything to pack, anyway. Though I did keep the letter with me.

I read once that bats always turn left when they exit their caves, so I decided to turn left every time I had to choose a direction. At least that way, I figured, I'd eventually end up back at my quarters. I didn't see anything

interesting for a long time. Just dark rocky tunnels and the occasional rivulet running down a wall. Eventually, I lost track of the number of left turns I had taken, but I knew it was more than three and I still hadn't made it back to my quarters.

After some time, I had stopped to examine a particularly large rivulet. It was flowing from a noticeable crack in the wall and I could feel a slight breeze coming from it. I thought I heard voices coming from it, too, but decided I must have been hearing things when there was nothing but silence and a steady *drip-drip* for the span of several shallow breaths. I started to walk away, but the voices came back when I turned my head. I realized my mistake and pressed the back of my head to the wall instead of the side of my face, where I was used to my ears being. I could hear the voices clearly now.

"...going to make your move?" the first voice said, raising in pitch at the end so I knew it was a question.

"Give us time," said the second voice. Even after ricocheting off of all the jagged rocky edges, it still sounded smooth as butter. That saying had ever made sense to me before that moment, but I understood it then. The way that second voice just flowed into my ear and settled itself in, making itself right at home – smooth as butter was the only way to describe it. "Even if we had a fully formed plan, we can't make a move until we're sure it's the right thing to do."

"How will you know it's the right thing to do?" The second voice sounded almost whiny. "What more do you need? Can't you see what they're doing to these..."

Too late, I heard the footsteps coming down the hallway. "What are you doing here?" asked the guard.

"Exploring?" I answered, a pathetic tremor in my voice. Apparently I wasn't pathetic enough to take pity on, or maybe pity wasn't a thing on this planet. Either way, the guard grabbed my arm and led me back in the direction I had come from.

Great, I thought. I couldn't even make it two whole cycles without getting in trouble.

The guard brought me to Landric's office and knocked on the door. When Landric answered, ka smiled until ka saw what ka must have recognized as guilt on my face. "What happened?"

The guard told ka that I had been found wandering unsupervised through the compound. Landric nodded along, then stepped aside to let me through and sent the guard on ka way.

"Am I in trouble?" I asked before the door was even closed. "I mean, no one ever actually said we couldn't leave our rooms."

"True, very true," Landric said, walking toward the couch in the corner of the room. I didn't know whether I was supposed to follow, so I stayed put and turned to track ka as ka moved. "Still, it is dangerous to go walking around the research sectors by yourself. There are so many different experiments going on. We wouldn't want you getting hurt, would we?" I shook my head. "Exactly. Now, we can't send you home this soon. We've barely learned anything from you, so that would make this whole thing a complete waste." Being sent home was the worst thing I could imagine. I had things to learn from the Mowleens, things that would make a difference on Earth. I must have looked terrified because I heard a gurgling purr. "I'm joking, of course! We wouldn't send you home just for being curious. That's part of why we brought you here in the first place!" I breathed an audible sigh of relief. Or rather, a hard puff of air left my nostril slits. "But still, we have to do something. You're about to go out into the world, beyond constant – oh, I guess not constant enough, huh – supervision that you have here. We can't have you wandering off alone and getting yourself hurt or lost. What can we do, what can we do? Ah!"

Landric stood up and moved across the room to the desk. Ka pressed a button and I heard a beep sound. "Hello, Landric!" It was Juleeay's voice.

"Juleeay, could you come to my office, please?"

"Sure thing!" *Beep.*

As we waited for Juleeay to arrive, a silence formed that was uncomfortable for me, but probably not for Landric.

Landric explained the situation and asked Juleeay what precautions should be taken to keep someone as adventurous as me safe in the residential sector. Juleeay thought for a moment. "What about a roommate?"

Landric agreed that that would probably do the trick.

"Great!" said Juleeay.

And that's how I ended up with my first strange roommate since college.

6

Stuck in Place Earth

I couldn't remember the last time I had come to work on a Saturday. Then again, I couldn't remember the last time I had wanted to be out of my house on a Saturday.

As my simulation ran, I sat back in my chair with my feet propped on my desk, fuming.

"I want to have a baby," he said. Over breakfast! Who drops that kind of word bomb over omelettes?

I wasn't ready for a baby. I didn't even know if I wanted to live in Arizona for the rest of my life. We couldn't move if we had a baby. What if I wanted to travel? And it would completely derail my long-term research plan. I had watched my friends get pregnant – months of weight gain and not being able to find a comfortable sleeping position? Plus, you know, actually giving birth. Oh no, pregnancy was not for me.

My computer beeped, interrupting my mental rant to let me know that my simulation had finished running.

Before I could understand my research on habitable planets forming in other parts of the galaxy, I had to understand how and why the Earth formed where it did. For the last few months, I had been working with a team of collaborators from around the world to simulate Earth's formation and evolution under different conditions.

I took my feet off the desk and scooted my chair closer to look at the results. My code returned a table of values, listing physical and orbital parameters for Earth at different ages.

The results were pretty much what I and my collaborators expected them to be, which was a good thing because it meant our hypothesis wasn't totally wrong... yet. I was just about to close the table and send it off to my

collaborators when I noticed something in the column that described Earth's characteristics a thousand years from now.

The values in that column listed Earth's year and its day as nearly identical. My simulation was telling me that it was possible for Earth to become tidally locked to the sun in as little as 2000 years.

No, that can't be possible, I thought to myself. But we hadn't found any bugs in the code in months. The only other option was that the results were from a physically unrealistic simulation. We were testing Earth's formation under all sorts of conditions, even ones that probably couldn't happen in our solar neighborhood.

I checked the parameters I had input into the simulation. They were all pretty realistic. The thing that was most unlike the conditions that actually exist in our solar system – and even that wasn't too much of a stretch from the realm of possibility – was increased asteroid activity.

Most of me still didn't want to believe it was possible, but I also didn't want my simulation to be completely wrong. So I went to the board and worked through every scenario I could think of that would lead to Earth becoming tidally locked.

Stepping back from the board, I didn't know what to feel. Happy that my simulations were running smoothly or terrified that there was a small but non-zero chance of Earth becoming uninhabitable in only a couple thousand years?

Then another, equally troubling question came to mind: should I tell my collaborators? I had seen people in the astronomical community lose all credibility when they published radical results – even theorists. Did I really want to be the person who announced to the world that I thought Earth was going to become uninhabitable in less time than it took the Ancient Egyptian state to crumble? Hell, no!

I already had the results table waiting in the queue to be sent to my collaborators. With my hand hovering over the send button, I considered all of the possible consequences of my actions.

If I didn't tell anyone, people could die. I didn't know of anyone else in the world doing this kind of research, and none of my collaborators had access to my code, so there was no guarantee that anyone else would figure it out.

But if I did tell people and I ended up being wrong, I would be humiliated. I'd be a laughing stock at conferences. And if I ended up being right, people would hate me instead of just laugh at me. No one likes the bearer of apocalyptic news.

I removed the table from the queue and gathered my stuff to go home, ping-ponging for a car as I left my office.

7

Home Sweet New Home Iyeena

Sometime after my meeting with Landric and Juleeay, I found myself standing in my new house and looking out through a window over the cliff edge that dropped off a few paces away.

The building itself was pretty nice to look at from the outside. It looked natural, almost like it had been crudely carved from the rock that it sat upon. The inside, though, was so high-tech that I was instantly reminded where I was and who my hosts were. It was one of about 20 or so houses similar to it on the top of several tiers that had been carved out of the rock, each with its own collection of buildings as far as I could tell.

Each house on the top tier was home to one of the Visitors. Well, each house except mine, which was home to two. Juleeay had suggested I live with Fogella, the Visitor from my tour of the Iyeenan surface who I thought might have been a biologist. I asked ka what ka studied and ka said there wasn't a word for it on Iyeena, but that it had something to do with how people on ka planet reproduced. Ka was quiet, with a mousy brown hair strip and bright eyes. But ka smiled often and always had something nice to say. Ka would make an excellent roommate.

We had been dropped off rather unceremoniously in our new house. Neither of us had any personal effects, so we didn't have to spend any time unpacking and stowing things away. We took a look around the house and were happy to find what we figured was a fully stocked Mowleean kitchen. Neither of us knew what normal Mowleean eating practices or dishes were, so we decided to play it by ear, eat when we were hungry, and trust that our hosts wouldn't have provided us with anything poisonous. We were also happy to find two separate bedrooms that each held a trunk full of clothes.

It didn't take us long to work our way through the house. And I don't

know how Fogella felt, but I couldn't get comfortable in it. Maybe it was too new or too clean or too foreign. Maybe I just wasn't ready to call it home yet. Whatever it was, I was ready to get out.

"Hey, Fogella, I'm going to go visit my friend Teer's house. You know, see if it looks the same on the inside as ours."

Fogella fidgeted, uncomfortable. Landric had probably told ka to keep watch over me, but I had made it pretty clear that I wanted to go alone.

"I'll be totally safe." I pointed out the window. "Look, there are guards standing out there. I can't possibly get into any trouble as I walk across the plain."

There really wasn't any reason for ka to doubt me, so Fogella said ka would see me later. I made sure to walk at a normal pace as I left the house.

The front of our house faced the center of the large semi-circle formed by all the Visitors' houses. I decided to call this tier Visitors' Village. I walked to Teer's house across the plain, noting the subtle differences between the houses' appearances, because they were the only kind of differences to notice. It was clear that the people who built them had been following a single plan, but had had to bend to the will of the rock in some places. Visitors Village reminded me a little of the suburban gated communities that existed back on Earth, and I felt trapped.

Teer answered ka door on the second knock. "Can I come in?" Ka opened the door wider and gestured for me to come inside. "Wow," I said, looking around. "This looks... exactly like my house." I felt and heard my stomach give the gurgling purr that was becoming more and more familiar as a laugh.

I smelled something coming from the kitchen and followed the scent. "What are you making?" I turned back to look at Teer.

"I have no idea. I was hungry, so I just threw things in a bowl and cooked it." Ka offered me some and I took it, realizing how hungry I was. The rambuut must have broken down in my system.

We walked into the next room. I wasn't exactly sure what it was supposed to be used for. It had a flower garden in one corner, a small pool of water in another, and path of rocks that cut across the middle. But there was also something that looked like a couch. I decided to think of it as a sitting room – I didn't foresee us doing anything else there. We sat and ate our food.

As we ate, Teer and I talked about our lives on our home planets. Ka told me that ka came from a family of farmers. The sun was so intense on Odahi that they could only farm at night, so Teer grew up spending most of ka time under the stars and Odahi's two moons, which is why ka became an astronomer.

Ka told me about ka mother and explained that no one on Odahi knew their father. Well, we couldn't say "mother" or "father," but Teer tried dif-

ferent words until ka eventually found some that roughly translated as "egg carrier" and "fertilizer." Ka went on to tell me that mating season on Odahi was such an anonymous frenzy that the "egg carriers" didn't stand a chance of identifying any of their partners. Once the children were born, every "fertilizer" helped to raise all of the children in a village, since there was an equal chance that any one was theirs.

And then it was my turn to talk about my life on Earth. After I finished explaining that I only had two parents, a mother and a father, I told Teer about their work as teachers. I talked about sports I had played, some of my favorite movies and TV shows, and the few trips I had taken to countries around the world – though they didn't seem as exciting and exotic compared to interplanetary travel. I didn't get a chance to tell ka about Justin before ka suggested going for a walk.

We walked through Visitors' Village in silence for a while before Teer explained that on Odahi, everyone was responsible for building their own homes, so ka was uncomfortable with the overwhelming homogeneity. I suggested we explore the other tiers and ka agreed.

As we looked for an escape, I thought back to my house. More particularly, I was thinking about the bathroom and how it didn't have a mirror, so I still hadn't seen my Mowleean face. "Teer," I asked, interrupting ka description of ka house back on Odahi, "what do I look like?"

Teer turned to me and looked at me intently for what felt like a very long time. "You have huge eyes. And when you smile, you show all of your teeth, not just the top row like the other Mowleean. And your hair..." Ka ran ka hand over the strip on top of my head. "It looks like a bunch of falling rocks." Ka let ka hand fall. "Was that helpful?"

I started laughing. "Yeah," I said through the purring, "all except for that last bit. Hair can't look like falling rocks, Teer."

Teer smiled and held ka arms out at ka sides in a form of shrug. "You asked, I answered. And now it's my turn. What do I look like?"

I looked Teer up and down and tried to think of a description as good as ka's had been. When that didn't work, I decided to fall back on my go-to tone: sass. "Like a pain in my neck."

Teer laughed and we went back to our search. A little while later, we found a staircase that led to the lower tiers.

There were five tiers in total, and Visitors' Village was the smallest by far. The tier immediately below us was also residential, but the houses were noticeably smaller and closer together. They were also much more individualized, and that seemed to make Teer feel more at home.

As we walked around, we heard loud noises: banging, cracking, buzzing – sounds of things being created. It didn't take long to spot the first source of

those sounds, or the second or third. Dozens of people were building things outside their homes, and there was a pervasive feeling of quiet cheer – no, it was more like deep satisfaction – in the air. Everyone was so engrossed in their work, though, that Teer and I passed more than a few people before someone glanced up and greeted us.

Sensing that it might be a while before we got someone to notice us again, we walked over to introduce ourselves. Teer led the way. "Hi, friend." Ka reached out with both hands to grab our greeter's head. "My name is Teer."

"Denzis," our greeter responded, ka eyes widened in either alarm or surprise. Seeing this, Teer let go and stepped away.

I stepped forward to take ka place. Denzis had huge black eyes set back in a face even darker than mine and ka strip of fur was bright green but cropped very short. "My name is Dakota." Then, on a hunch, "How would you greet us?"

"You're Visitors." It wasn't a question, but Teer and I nodded anyway. "I've never greeted a Visitor before. They usually only interact with the Thinkers."

"You're not a Thinker, then." I didn't really mean it as a question, either. Denzis stood up straighter. "I am a Builder." Now that ka was standing at ka full height, I could see that Denzis was a full head taller than me – though I didn't know if that was tall for a Mowleean or not, because I didn't know how I compared to the average – and had so many muscles. Denzis was visibly more muscular than any other Mowleean I had seen this close up. That made sense considering that ka had been wielding a rather large hammer before we interrupted.

"Okay," I said, thinking through the various ways I could possibly respond and trying to decide which would make Denzis feel the most comfortable with us. "How would you greet us if we were Builders?"

At that, Denzis did look more comfortable. Ka reached out with both hands and grabbed the tops of my arms – where I imagined my biceps were. "Like this," ka said. "To feel how hard the other person can work."

I returned the gesture and gave a smile that I hoped communicated the right amounts of happiness, gratitude, and respect. Teer did the same. Figuring we had gained some of Denzis' trust, we asked where we were and if ka would show us around.

"We don't really have a name for it. This is where the Builders live." Teer and I glanced at each other; we had figured that much. "I can't show you around. I have to finish this plating, but no one will give you trouble if you go exploring." Without another word, ka picked the hammer back up and continued driving nails into a thin metal sheet. And that was the end of the conversation.

Teer and I wandered around for a little bit longer, but no one else seemed interested in talking to us. Still, the houses were nice to look at. They were beautiful in a way that made the houses in Visitors' Village seem dull by comparison. It wasn't that they were super elaborate or obviously decorated. It was that there's a beauty in practicality, in something that was built to serve a purpose and spends its entire existence serving that purpose well. That's what these houses did, and they each did it in their own way.

Before long, Teer and I noticed that it was getting quieter and we saw several people put away their tools and head inside their homes. Neither of us felt comfortable asking any of the Builders what was happening, and we were both feeling the beginnings of what we thought was hunger, so we turned to make our way back to the central staircase.

About halfway back to the stairs, Teer grabbed my arm suddenly and pulled me closer to the edge of the Builder's tier so we could see over the cliff.

"What are you doing?!" I practically screamed. I felt a flash of heat course through my body.

Teer pointed over the edge to the tier below. "Smell that!" ka said. I turned my three nostril slits toward where ka was pointing. And then I grabbed ka arm and pulled her the rest of the way to the the stairs.

The middle tier could only be described as bustling. Well, I guess it could also be described as loud, smelly, and a little bit dirty, but in my mind, all of those things are wrapped up in bustling. The middle tier had everything I had hoped I would find once I got to Iyeena: shops, food stands, people shouting at each other on the walking paths. The middle tier had the kind of culture that screamed for you to pay attention to it.

Teer and I quickly gave up hope of finding the source of whatever we had smelled on the second tier, but we really didn't mind. There seemed to be something that smelled just as delicious every five steps – and something that smelled even more revolting every step after that.

As we walked by one of the delicious smelling stalls, Teer reached out ka hand, grabbed something on a stick that smelled like some sort of barbecued meet, and took a bite out of it. All without skipping a beat or batting an eye. Ka stopped when ka noticed I was staring. "What?" ka asked, with a half-chewed meat chunk visible through ka pointy teeth.

"You just stole that!!" I said, pointing at the stick in ka hand.

"What do you mean? I didn't steal anything. It was right there, out in the open for the taking!"

"But you didn't pay for it."

Teer gave me a look that told me ka had no idea what I was talking about.

"Teer, what do you exchange for goods and services on Odahi?"

Ka swallowed and ka face wrinkled in thought. "Nothing. People on Odahi provide their own goods and services. If you find something, it is yours for the taking."

It hadn't even occurred to me that there could be successful, advanced societies that didn't rely on any type of currency. I realized I should stop and observe the actions of the people around me so I could avoid making another potentially dangerous assumption. "Well, you might as well finish that." Ka had already taken another huge bite. "But we should try and figure out how things are done here."

There was no shortage of interactions to observe. People were interacting all around us. At a food stall to our left, a Mowleean with dusty orange hair tied in intricate but messy knots down to the neck of ka shirt approached a hairless and hunched over vendor who had been yelling into the throngs of passersby for someone to look at ka wares. When the orange-haired Mowleean was close enough for the two to speak, ka reached out and clasped the vendor's hands with ka own. I looked around and saw that other people were greeting each other in this manner too, so I turned my attention back to the two to my left.

It was too loud for me to hear, but the orange-haired Mowleean seemed to be looking over the things in the vendor's cart. ka pointed to something and the vendor pulled it out, holding up three fingers on ka opposite hand. The orange-haired one bared ka teeth in a way that didn't look particularly friendly and the vendor put one of ka fingers down. That seemed to calm Orange Hair down, and ka reached into a purse that had been hidden moments before in the folds of ka clothes and produced two rough looking rocks of unequal sizes and different colors.

As interesting as the exchange had been, I was disappointed. This meant that there was a currency system on Iyeena, and Teer and I were flat broke. Still, I was hungry, and I had talked my way into a free meal more than once back on Earth. I looked around for my target, a food vendor who looked like ka was just about ready to give up hope of making a sale. It didn't take too long to spot one about ten carts away.

Ka wasn't old or decrepit like the last vendor. Ka just looked... bland and defeated. The vendors on either side of ka were yelling loudly, joking with people as they passed by, shouting the occasional well-placed and well-deserved insult. The vendor I had targeted could barely get out a "Hey!" before someone stopped paying attention to ka. Part of me felt bad about

trying to weasel the poor person into giving me free food, but after watching a few more people walk by ka without even stopping to give ka a glance, I figured I'd be doing ka a favor by talking to ka.

Leaving Teer a few steps away, I walked right up to ka and grabbed ka hands. "Hi, I'm Dakota." Ka was so surprised that ka physically recoiled from my touch. Then ka laughed in my face. The smile made ka look like a completely different person.

"You're not from here, are you?" I looked around and then down at myself.

"It's the clothes that give me away, isn't it?" My clothes were bright and fresh. The clothes on the people passing me by were brown from dust and age. Many of them had visible patchwork.

"It's a lot of things. When you grow up near the Rift, it becomes a part of you. And you don't have it in you." I must have looked properly chagrined, because the vendor took pity on me. "My name's Tinch. What are you doing talking to an old slash like me, anyway?"

I realized that I could get more than just food from Tinch. I could get information.

"Well, a few things," I began, but Tinch cut me off before I could go further.

"Look here, young thing. I want to like you, but I can tell you're about to try and sweet talk me into something. Don't bother. Just come out with it."

Looking into ka eyes, I could tell there really was no point in trying to charm my way into getting what I wanted. "Food and information."

"Hmmm. That's gonna cost you." The desperate look in my eyes must have told ka that I didn't have any of whatever passed as money here. I imagine it was a look that ka had had in ka own eyes more than once. "You can't expect me to give away anything for free! I don't get any customers." Ka gestured toward the crowd of people pushing past each other to reach their own destinations. "I can't end the day with less stuff than I started with."

That gave me an idea. "What if I got you customers? Then could I get what I want for free?"

Tinch spit on the ground and smiled. I guessed we had a deal.

I positioned Tinch by ka kart and told ka to smile. It really did make a world of difference.

My first strategy was to stand over by Teer and talk loudly about how full I was. "I'm telling you, Teer! That Tinch's stuffers are so good I ate three before I realized I had touched one. Now I can hardly move!" I did that for a little bit, and I noticed a few people actually looking at Tinch as they

passed ka stand. That was some improvement at least. But it wasn't good enough, so I switched tactics.

I went to stand next to Tinch and started calling out to people as they walked by. "Hey you! Yeah you! You look hungry. Come try a stuffer." I actually got someone to look my way, but ka shook ka head and disappeared into the crowd. "Come stuff your face with Tinch's stuffers!" I yelled. "They'll have you licking your fingers, they're so good. You, with the red spikes!" A young Mowleean with ka hair fashioned in red spikes turned to look at me. "You know you want a stuffer.

Ka actually walked up to look at Tinch's stand. "What do you want for one?" Tinch looked surprised, but recovered quickly and held up one finger. The red-haired Mowleean pulled a smooth blue pebble out of ka shoe and handed it to Tinch. Tinch reached into ka cart and handed over a stuffer, a type of flaky popover filled with spiced meat. The red-haired kid took one bite, turned to look at Tinch, then stuffed the rest of his mouth.

Tinch laughed, a harsh, grating sound. "That's why I call 'em stuffers."

The kid reached into ka shoe and pulled out another pebble. I saw my opportunity and stepped in before Tinch could pull out another stuffer. "You know, Tinch here will actually give you two stuffers for your one pebble if you go and tell a bunch of your friends how good they are."

Ka ran off, and before long, there was a line of Mowleean waving pebbles of various shapes, colors, and sizes in the air, waiting for Tinch to hand them a stuffer.

When they were all gone, Tinch leaned on ka cart, exhausted. "So, what do you say, Tinch? Do you think I earned that food and information yet?"

Tinch held out two stuffers. I beckoned Teer over and Tinch gave ka one, too. "What do you want to know?"

"First," I said around a mouthful of delicious stuffer. I was convinced I had never tasted anything quite so good before. "what did you call this place? The Rip? Why?"

"The Rift," Tinch corrected me. "This is the line between them Builders up there," ka jerked ka chin up toward the second tier, "and the good, honest Getters below." We weren't close enough to the edge of this tier to see below, but I had caught glimpses of the fourth tier while Teer and I were walking down the stairs. It had looked practically dead and empty, like a ghost town.

"So this is where the Getters work?"

Tinch laughed again. "No, dearie. The Getters work out there." Ka looked up. "They're out getting the things we need to make stuff here. Well, that and the stuff for the almighty Thinkers." Ka spit again, and not in the friendly way ka had before when we were making our deal. "No offense." I shook my head to say I hadn't taken any. "Anyway, that's why it's so quiet

down there now."

"Okay, but if the Getters are all out getting things, then who's here? I mean, all due respect, but you don't seem like a Builder."

Tinch sat on the rickety stool next to ka cart. "We're the slashes." I gave a questioning look. "People who are too old to work as Getters anymore. Or the people who are too young to work as Getters yet. Or the people who are too sick, or injured, or weak." I nodded along. "We're the slashes because we're useless. Blights on society. So we keep ourselves busy by running the Rift."

Teer stepped in, having finished ka stuffer. "Who are most of these people then? The people buying things?"

"The Rift is where all the Getters buy clothes and food and anything else they might need to survive. Most of these people are off-duty Getters. Every once in a while we get a Builder down here. You know, if ka has more... exotic tastes."

Teer and I looked at each other, equal parts understanding and discomfort on our faces.

Tinch started packing up. "Okay, that's all you're getting out of me. Go bother someone else."

We had learned in the short time since we met ka that it was better to just do what Tinch said the first time ka said it, so Teer and I said our goodbyes and walked away from the stuffer stand.

Teer said ka was tired and asked if I wanted to head back to Visitors' Village. I'd be lying if I said I wasn't feeling exhausted from the excitement of the day, but I wasn't ready to go back yet. Part of it was that I just didn't want to finish exploring before I had seen all the tiers. Most of it was that I didn't want to have to feel that uncomfortable trapped feeling again, and I knew I would feel it as soon as I set foot on the top tier. So I said no and told ka I wouldn't be much longer.

Before we separated, I touched the three middle fingers of my left hand to ka forehead and ka reached out ka right hand to shake mine.

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I made my way through the fourth tier, wandering between the homes of the Getters. It felt even more like a ghost town as I walked through it. The fourth tier was huge and flat. Bigger than maybe all of the top three combined. And yet, as I meandered by the hundreds of huts clustered around the path that led from the stairs, I saw maybe a handful of other Mowleens. I guess it made sense, given what Tinch had said. Most of the Getters were out working. Many were shopping for their families in the Rift. And the

few who weren't doing either of those things were probably sleeping because they were exhausted from having just done them.

Despite the creepy ghost town vibe, I forced myself to keep walking. I had left Teer's house with the intention of visiting all of the tiers, and that's what I was going to do. The fifth tier now seemed the most mysterious to me, anyway. Before today, I had heard of the Builders and the Getters, and I had already seen their homes. Who lived on this fifth tier? And why hadn't I heard anyone mention them?

Perhaps if I hadn't been so tired, I would have been wary of venturing alone into the territory of something completely unknown to me. But in the state I was in, all I knew was that I was curious and that walking down those steps was the only way to sate my curiosity.

After what seemed like an eternity, I came to the final stairway. I was already exhausted, but I refused to think about the fact that I would have to walk all the way back to Visitors' Village when all my exploring was done. I walked down the stairs, slowly, one deliberate step at a time for fear that I would miss one and tumble the rest of the way down.

About halfway down, I heard something coming from below. It was too faint at first to even make out what kind of sound it was, but as I got closer to the fifth and final tier, it became clear that I was hearing music. I realized it was my first time hearing music on Iyeena, and I couldn't wait to meet the people who were making it, so I ran down the rest of the steps.

The bottom tier wasn't flattened out like the others. Actually, it didn't even look like it had been carved out of the rock like the rest of them had been. I was pretty sure it was a natural valley in the rock bed, like a gorge. I couldn't see any sign of civilization, just giant boulders randomly strewn about. The music had gotten louder, though, so I tried to follow the sound, needing to meet the Mowleens who had created it.

The sound led me to a tunnel entrance on the side of the gorge opposite the staircase. The music sounded even more alien and ethereal inside the tunnel than it had outside. Out there, it had sounded reedy, but still full, the sound waves being buffeted off of the boulders on their way to my ears. Inside the tunnel, the music sounded thinner, more echo-y, like a whisper even though it was technically louder than it had been outside. But it always sounded happy.

The music warped as I inched my way through the tunnel. I eventually lost track of the turns I had taken as I chased the music, and it wasn't long before I was completely lost. The music had gotten so loud that I couldn't tell where it was coming from, because it sounded like it was coming from everywhere. And then the music stopped altogether and I realized I had no hope of finding it or my way back. I was lost and scared and hot. It was in

that moment that I knew Mowleens didn't cry, because if the fear of dying alone in a tunnel wasn't enough to make me shed a tear, nothing was.

In the height of my panic, a soft red glow began to illuminate the tunnel. The glow got more and more intense until I realized it was coming from me. It was *me*. I was glowing!

Cool as it was, I wasn't really in a mental state where I could appreciate the moment properly. I was lost, and not even my nifty new bioluminescence could fix that. So I sat and looked at the shadows that I cast on the tunnel walls.

I don't know how long I sat there – it felt like forever because there's something about the combination of silence and darkness that makes time seem like it's stretching out to infinity, even though it never actually is – but someone found me. By then, I was so panicked that I couldn't pay attention to anything other than the shadows. I might not have even registered that someone was picking me up if I hadn't seen their shadow interacting with my own.

The shadow led me away from the spot on the floor I had begun to think of as mine. A few turns later, everything was bright again, and even though I knew I must have still been glowing, I couldn't see it anymore. The shadow led me to the center of a large cavern and put something warm in my hand. "Drink this." And I did.

After a few sips, I felt more like myself again. I looked up to see what the shadow actually looked like. Ka had a squashed face. It was flat and all of ka features were really close together. Ka had a pretty unremarkable hair strip: yellow with a few silver streaks. I was slightly disappointed that my savior could be described as somewhere between homely and blah, and then ka spoke.

"Are you feeling better?" One simple four-word-long sentence. I'd heard the sentence hundreds of times before in my life. I'd probably heard the individual words millions of times. And they had never sounded as good before as they did when the shadow said them. It was more than that, though. The words *felt* good. If I hadn't already been feeling better, ka words would have done the job.

I nodded.

"Can you speak?"

I nodded, then realized that actions, in this moment, wouldn't speak louder than words. "Yes."

"Good. My name is Keeloa." Ka looked at me expectantly.

"Dakota."

"Good, Dakota. You keep drinking what's in that cup. I'll be right back."

It was only then that I realized we weren't alone. There were tents set up

all around us. Some of them had sprouted heads as Keeloa and I exchanged those precious few words. There were some people staring at us from out in the open, and some of them didn't look particularly pleased by my presence.

I tried to take my mind off of the hostility that I felt around me by paying attention to the way everything looked. There were colors everywhere! No two tents were identical because they were all wildly colored and patterned. People's clothes were just as striking, and I realized that until Keeloa had found me, I had only seen people in muted clothing, either by design or because of years of wear. But it was more than just colorful fabric that set this place apart. Almost every exposed patch of skin I saw was decorated with paint or jewelry.

Keeloa walked away to talk to one of those not-so-pleased people. I faced away from them so I could hear their conversation better.

"How could you bring one of them here? They're the reason our ancestors had to hide here in the first place!"

"Ka was lost in the tunnels. I don't know how ka got there, but ka was so scared that ka glow was almost blinding." Now that I wasn't focusing on Keeloa's face, I realized that I had heard ka voice before. Keeloa was one of the people I had overheard talking through the crack in the tunnel before I left the research compound.

I heard footsteps approaching and turned back around to see who they belonged to, hoping it was Keeloa. It wasn't.

A wave of intense heat struck me in the face. "You don't belong here, parasite! We don't want you here. Go back to where you came from and let your body have some peace." The words were being screamed at me by a Mowleean so dark I could barely make out the edges of his eyes. Ka hair strip, though, was a swirling mix of gold and copper that almost looked like it was moving.

Before I could react, ka was pulled forcefully away from me. "Leave ka alone, Pakoy. Ka's been through enough." Keeloa handed Pakoy off to someone and told them to take ka away.

Keeloa sat down next to me on the bench. "Are you okay?" Pakoy can be a little... alarming." I nodded. "Oh come on, let's not do this again."

"I'm fine," I managed to say. "Ka didn't scare me." More people were coming to join the circle. Keeloa quietly told me their names. I remembered a few of them – Akamu, Mayara, Rindell – but I doubted I would be able to guess which of the many faces went with those few names.

"Who are you all? Why are you down here?" I really wanted to ask what Keeloa had been doing in the research compound that time I overheard ka conversation, but I didn't think it was a good idea to ask in front of so many people.

Keeloa opened ka hands in a gesture to the rest of the circle, welcoming any of them to answer my question. A Mowleean with a dark green hair strip – maybe Mayara, most likely not – spoke up. "They call us the Players. We're the lowest of the low here on Iyeena." This was said with some bitterness. "We entertain. We create. We sing, dance, draw, write. They call us useless, nonsensical. So we stay here in the tunnels where no one has to see us and we can create in peace."

"That seems so wrong! Who are they?" I grew up around art. The idea of a society where art was hidden away didn't make any sense to me.

Someone else spoke, someone whose name I knew I couldn't remember. "Believe me. They've done things more wrong than calling us names." Ka looked me in the eyes and scowled so big I could see the very tops of ka teeth. I scooted away without thinking. I scooted closer to Keeloa.

Keeloa answered my question. "*They* are the Thinkers. And they can do anything they want on Iyeena. You should ask Landric about this body of yours sometime." There was a heavy silence. Its weight helped Keeloa's words really sink in.

I shook my head, hoping to push Keeloa's words further down. I didn't know what he meant, and I decided I wasn't ready to think about anything serious, so I asked if they would sing me a song instead. Everyone looked shocked, but I would have given many things to hear the music that had led me down here again.

Once they realized I wasn't mocking them and that I genuinely wanted to hear a song, it didn't take much convincing to get them to do it. It seemed like art was in these Mowleean's blood.

The song they played was beautiful. Soft and light, but with an undercurrent of pain. I followed that current. I followed it back to Earth, back to Justin and my family, my family who didn't even have the option of missing me. The current got too strong for me then, and I couldn't follow it anymore. I was being pulled by it instead, and I didn't know if I liked where it was taking me. But I knew that if I fell asleep, I might not have to see whatever was at the end.

I had one last question, though, before I fell asleep. "You said they call you Players," I said, looking at the maybe-maybe-not Mayara. "What do you call yourselves?"

"The Rememberers."

8

I Won't Go Earth

While I was at NASA, I had interviews, press conferences, and bureaucratic meetings every day. Those got very boring very quickly. When I was a young girl, I would watch the same celebrities appear on multiple talk shows for starring in one movie or pulling one charitable publicity stunt, and I would think their lives must be so glamorous and exciting. No. Answering the same questions over and over again is anything but exciting. It's literally mind-numbing, in that I eventually got to the point where I didn't bother to think about my answers because I had given them so many times before.

I was in Washington for more than a week before I learned that I wouldn't actually be travelling to Iyeena. I definitely should have figured it out on my own sooner. After all, the Mowleens who had contacted us couldn't survive exposure to our atmosphere. What made me think I would be able to survive exposure to theirs?

When I found out, I was disappointed at first. I would never walk on another planet, never touch an alien with my own hands. Then I realized that meant I could go home. Justin would eventually forgive me and everything would go back to normal.

Could I really be happy with normal after this?

I learned about the exchange process during one of the few fruitful conversations I managed to have with the Mowleens about Iyeenan solar system. We were communicating electronically, since they weren't actually on Earth. The computer I was using read their message aloud. It even assigned different voices to the different Mowleens who were talking to us, all of them male. And so even though I had no idea what the Mowleens actually sounded like, or if they would sound like anything at all to my human ears, I had formed a pretty clear – though, I knew, wildly inaccurate – image in my head. To me,

because of these computers, all Mowleens were rather large and muscular South African men. And they wore suits all the time.

"Our telescopes didn't detect any other planets in your system." I wondered for a moment what my digital voice sounded like to them.

"Iyeena is not alone. We have a sister planet." That wasn't the first time I had heard of Iyeena's sister planet, but I didn't know anything about it other than that it existed. I wasn't too surprised, though. Astronomers had known for a long time that most M-dwarf stars probably host multiple planets. "Beings from that planet were the first to make contact with us, letting us know that life existed elsewhere."

This was new information! I sat up straighter in my seat, but willed myself not to say anything. I'd learned over the last week that if I asked too many questions or sounded too excited, the Mowleens got uncomfortable and shut down.

"The Amree shared their knowledge with us. They developed the technology we will use to take your mind to Iyeena."

I had a lot of questions about the Amree and their technology, but one question was more pressing than all of the others.

"What do you mean take my mind?"

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I caught Charles off guard, a donut halfway to his mouth when I pushed my way through his door. He had stopped locking it after my third unexpected visit to his office earlier in the week. I believed it was less because he had wanted me to think I was welcome and more because he didn't want to have to keep getting up to let me in.

"What kind of liaison are you?!" I practically yelled in his face.

He sighed a long, defeated sigh. "What are you talking about this time?"

"When were you going to tell me I'm not actually going to Iyeena?"

Charles reluctantly put his donut back in its bag. I wondered for a moment if I was driving him to stress eat. Then I looked at him again and shrugged the feeling off, thinking that neither of us would be in this position if he were better at his job. "Meet me at entrance to the engineering department in half an hour," he said, shooing me out of his office.

I pinged Justin as I made my way to the elevator that would take me to the engineering department. Before he could hang up or say something in his angry voice, I said, "Wait, Justin, I really need to talk to you." The slight tremor in my voice must have persuaded him.

"What's wrong?" he asked, concern seeping through the scorn I was so used to hearing in his voice.

"Nothing's wrong. This is a happy shake. Justin, I don't have to leave! I'm not going to Iyeena." I knew going home would be hard and that Justin and I had a lot of things to work out, but I did miss my husband.

Shocked silence. "Really?" He sounded so hopeful, so excited, but so suspicious at the same time, like a child who fears his new toy will be taken away.

"Really." I said, and I could hear him breathe a sigh of relief.

"When are you coming home?"

"I'll see you on Friday," I said, hoping he could hear my smile through the phone. "I love you."

9

The Waiting Room

Iyeena

I stumbled out of my bedroom in my house in Visitors' Village, trying to figure out how I had gotten home last night. The last thing I remembered was falling asleep in the Rememberers' cave. How had they known where I lived? How had they gotten me there without anyone noticing?

Fogella was standing in what we had agreed was the kitchen. We had come to that conclusion based on three things: the large cold box in the corner of the room that held something that looked like meat, a box against the opposite wall that got hot when we pressed different buttons on it, and the stuff hanging from the ceiling that I had to assume were herbs of some sort.

Ka was rifling through one of the many other boxes arranged around the room. I knocked on the wall by the doorway and ka turned around, startled.

"What are you looking for," I asked, crossing the room to look over ka shoulder.

"Something that reminds me of home." Based on the state of the other boxes in the room, ka had been searching for quite some time. "I didn't really expect to find anything, but I wanted to make food for when you woke up because I know I was super hungry when I woke up." Ka threw down the packet of green mushy stuff ka was holding and stood up, turning to face me. "I don't know how to make any of this stuff."

I looked around. "Well, I don't know what any of this is either. Let's just pick something and experiment because you were right. I am way too hungry right now to be picky."

Cooking is really difficult in new and different places. I didn't do much travelling back on Earth, but when I did, I was almost overwhelmed by how unfamiliar all of the food was. Trying to make something that won't kill

you or make you want to throw up takes all of your attention. And so it wasn't until after Fogella and I had prepared, tasted, and thrown away three different dishes that I remembered to ask what ka had done after I left to spend time with Teer.

"Not too much. I went with a few of the other Visitors to swim in a pool the guards told us about. Then I came home and slept." Ka was placing bits of chopped meat – or whatever was stored in the cold box – in the high-tech Mowleean oven. Ka turned it onto the heat setting that we had discovered when we made our second dish, the setting that seemed to cook the meat but didn't make it catch on fire.

"So you don't know how I got home last night?" I don't think I was blushing because I don't think Mowleean blush, but I certainly felt warm. Asking the question immediately transported me through time and space back to some of my less proud nights in college.

"No," Fogella answered, pulling down one of the herb clusters hanging from the ceiling. "I only woke up a little bit before you did." Ka turned to face me, a smile on ka face. "Maybe you should ask Teer."

I knew Teer wouldn't know since ka hadn't even met the Rememberers, but I wanted to tell ka all about them. My stomach squirmed and I looked at the oven. "How much longer do you think that will take?"

"I don't know, but it probably won't be very good. I won't be offended if you go over to eat with ka."

I smiled at Fogella and started the short walk to Teer's house. When I got there, I didn't even bother knocking, but just let myself inside. Teer was cooking something that didn't smell anywhere near as good as whatever Fogella was making, but I felt a lot more comfortable with Teer than I did with anyone else on Iyeena, so it seemed like an even trade.

Ka smiled when ka saw me walk in. "You look awful! Here, drink this," ka said, holding a mug under my nose. Just the smell of whatever was inside – the smell of pine needles and snow – made me feel more awake. I took the mug and Teer returned to whatever ka had been doing before I walked in. "What happened to you after I left?"

"I met someone. I met a whole bunch of people, actually. And then I fell asleep."

Teer turned ka attention to the oven, which was the source of the smell I had noticed when I walked in. "You met someone?" Something about the way ka said it made me think of Justin and the ethical boundaries of my current situation.

I took another sip of the Mowleean coffee. "Believe me, nothing scandalous happened. At least, I'm pretty sure nothing scandalous happened."

Teer bared ka teeth in a giant smile. "Well, you can't expect me to believe

you if you don't believe yourself. Okay, this thing will beep when it's done." Ka kicked the oven. "Let's go sit and talk about what you do remember from last night."

We walked into Teer's sitting room – identical to my own – and sat on the couch. I told ka all about my encounter with the Rememberers.

"Wait, they just stay down in those tunnels all the time?"

I nodded. "Yeah, I guess so. They made it sound like they didn't really interact much with other people."

"But how do they get food? What about water? And *Landric*? Ka knows about them and just lets them stay there?" Teer was getting kind of worked up. I could feel the heat radiating off of ka body in waves.

"Well, that's what they say. Who knows if we can believe them, Teer? If they're in that cave, there's probably a reason!"

Teer sat for a moment, shaking ka head. Then ka stood up and walked to the door.

"Where are you going?!"

Ka turned back to look at me, hand on the door handle. "If Landric has a reason, I want ka to tell it to me to my face." Ka pulled the door open. "You coming?"

"Teer, do you even know how to get back to the research compound?" I hoped the question would put out some of the fire that my story seemed to have ignited.

"No," ka said, now standing on the other side of the door. "But they do."

Before I could say anything else, Teer was already striding toward the guards in the center of the plain. I sighed and followed, because I knew Teer well enough by then to know that it would be less painful not to argue.

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One of the guards stayed behind while the other led us through the circle of houses to a tunnel entrance in the rock face behind Visitors' Village. There was a kind of vehicle waiting there. It looked a bit like a golf cart, but it had three wheels: two narrow ones in the back and a wide one in the front. We all climbed in the cart and sat in slightly uncomfortable silence as the guard drove us to the research compound. Once there, we were met by another guard who lead us to Landric's office. Landric answered the door and ushered us in, sending the guard away. "What are you doing back so soon," ka asked as we settled into the couch in the corner of ka office. Ka grabbed the chair by ka desk and brought it over to sit in front of us. "We usually let the Visitors settle in for at least a cycle before we bring them back and put them to work."

Ka lips curled in what I knew was supposed to be a smile, but it seemed more predatory than jovial.

Teer was still fuming too much for me to trust ka to say anything that wouldn't offend Landric or get us into trouble.

"I met some people. The Players." I figured it would be easier to use the name that Mayara had said the rest of the Mowleens used.

"I thought you said they were called the Rememberers," Teer interjected. I shot ka a look that I hoped would get ka to keep ka mouth shut – it had been ka idea for me to tell the story, after all – but not before I saw something flash behind Landric's eyes at the mention of the name the Rememberers used for themselves.

"I am so sorry," Landric told me. "The Players really shouldn't be in your neighborhood. I don't know how that happened."

I hadn't wanted to get anyone in trouble. "No, no, no! They weren't a bother. And they weren't in our neighborhood. I was in theirs, actually."

A smile pulled at Landric's mouth, this one more genuine than the last, though ka tried to hide it. "You were in their neighborhood? How did you get there? What did it look like?"

Teer and I looked at ka, startled by ka sudden enthusiasm. Ka cleared ka throat. "I mean, what were you doing there? Could you not find something you needed in your new home?"

I could tell that Teer was getting ready to say something and jumped to answer Landric's question first. "Fogella and I have everything we need, thank you. Teer and I just wanted to explore. You know, see all of what Iyeena has to offer." I smiled my most placating smile, but I don't know how placating anyone can look when they're baring deadly fangs.

"Well, you should be careful. The Players can be dangerous." There was a deep look of concern in ka eyes.

I glanced over at Teer. *I told you we couldn't trust them* I said to ka by cocking my head to the side and hunching my shoulders. I hoped ka would leave it at that. We could apologize to Landric for taking ka time, go back to our no doubt overcooked meal, and never speak of the Rememberers again.

But, no. That would have been too easy.

"How are they so dangerous if they keep themselves hidden away in a cave deep underground?" It was much more of an accusation than an innocent question.

"We all live in a giant cave underground." I thought Landric was trying to lighten the mood with humor, but it wasn't really working.

"You know what I mean!" Teer stood up. "What could they have possibly done that's so *dangerous*?"

Landric calmly – almost lazily – allowed ka eyes to drift up to meet Teer’s. Landric was still smiling – or at least attempting to – but I could feel the heat rolling off of both of them. "They’re completely opposed to science. They’ve tried to sabotage several of our experiments."

"What do you mean?" I hadn’t heard anyone mention sabotaged experiments before. I was curious.

Landric sighed. "Follow me." Ka turned on ka heel and walked out the door, assuming Teer and I would follow.

And, of course, we did.

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We walked for a long time. It seemed odd to me that someone as important as Landric seemed to be would have an office that far away from anything. Clearly ka didn’t have as much power as Keeloa seemed to think ka had, or else all tunnels would lead to Landric’s office. At least, that’s how I thought it should work.

By the time we got to where we were going, I was lost in my own thoughts about the fact that, technically, all roads indirectly led to everywhere eventually. Teer tapped me on the shoulder to keep me from walking into Landric, who had stopped in front of a large and rather imposing door – the entrance to one of the research sectors. The door was a vibrant green with small images carved into it. I leaned closer to get a better look and realized that they were carvings of double helices! We were standing outside the biology sector. Well, Landric and Teer were standing. I was leaning against the door, so naturally that was the moment someone decided to open it.

I stumbled past the door and into the arms of the person who had let us in. I looked up to find the most empathetic smile I had encountered yet on Iyeena. "Dakota," intoned Landric from the doorway, "this is the head of the biology sector, Aleese. Aleese, this is Teer." Ka gestured to Teer at ka side. "And that one in your arms is Dakota. They’re Visitors."

If the laughter that I had heard up until then had been gurgling, what I heard coming from Aleese’s chest could only be described as bubbling. It was a giggle! Ka looked down at my face. "Are you ready to stand?"

I stood up and took a step back. I looked at Aleese. Ka had wide bright eyes that I doubted ever missed anything. Those eyes sat under a fiery red strip of hair, which Aleese ran her hand over absentmindedly while I regained my composure. "Thanks," I said sheepishly.

Aleese waved my gratitude away. "So what brings such great Thinkers down my way?"

"Dakota here ran into the Players." Aleese whipped ka attention back to me. "And Teer doesn’t believe me when I say they’re dangerous." Aleese’s

head whipped again. "I thought it would be good for them to see the Waiting Room. To see what the Players want to destroy."

Suddenly serious, Aleese nodded. "This way." Ka walked away, weaving between desks and expensive-looking pieces of lab equipment. I began to wonder if it was just a part of Mowleean culture to assume that people would follow you whenever you walked away.

Aleese stopped in front of another door. The rest of us had been following single file, so we had formed an almost cartoonish pileup by the time Aleese turned to look at us.

"Without what lies behind this door, you two wouldn't be here." Ka looked pointedly at Teer and me. "The Players have broken in here several times and tried to set fire to this room." Ka eyes weren't bright anymore. They were hard, remembering something ka would never forgive.

At Landric's command, Aleese turned ka back to us, tapped some sort of ID card to a box on the wall, and pushed open the door. Landric motioned for Teer and me to walk in first, and when we saw what was on the other side, both of our jaws dropped, but for very different reasons.

The walls were white – bright white – and padded. I blinked until my eyes adjusted. Half of the enormous room was filled with rows and rows of beds, about 50 in total. Well, they were more like cots, really. Half of the other side of the room was lined with tables. The remainder of the room was filled with what looked like exercise equipment.

We were standing on a small platform high above the room, looking down on the people below. Long staircases descended down to the ground on either side of us, but Landric blocked my way when I tried to walk down one. "We're only here to observe," ka said, holding out a surprisingly firm arm to keep me from moving.

I turned back to the railing. "Who are these people?" There were some people eating at the tables on the side of the room to our right. But they weren't sitting together. There were about 15 people eating, and they were all sitting at different tables, staring intently at the food in front of them. A handful of guards stood along the walls, surveying the room. Still off to our right but closer to the staircase leading down from our platform, there were maybe 10 people using the exercise equipment. Some were running, some were lifting weights, but each one was accompanied by a person in a long vibrant green lab coat like the one Aleese was wearing.

"These people are future Visitors," Aleese said with a proud smile on ka face.

I looked down at my body. "You mean, they're..."

"Hosts, yes. We care for them here and prepare and train them for hosting Visitors as part of our exchange program."

Teer's jaw still hadn't returned to its normal position. "They stay here all the time?" Ka looked at Landric and Aleese, ka eyes wide and wild. "They're prisoners!"

I knew from talking with Teer that Odahi was a place where everyone was granted a lot of space and independence. Seeing so many people in one space must have made ka uncomfortable, but I still felt ke reaction was a bit strong.

Landric put ka hand on Teer's shoulder. "They're not prisoners. They can leave any time. Plus, they are an essential part of a program that has helped us gain vast stores of knowledge. And they haven't just advanced technology here. They're responsible for helping a hundred planets around the galaxy." Ka pointed to the people below. "Look how well they're treated. They exercise every day. They eat the freshest food on Iyeena, taken directly from our agriculture sector. They have direct access to the most well-respected Thinkers. What more could anyone want?"

Teer rotated ka shoulder, pulling it away from Landric's hand. Ka lips were trembling, but I couldn't tell if it was from anger or sadness.

"Freedom." I didn't think anyone else had heard it, and I wished that I hadn't.

Teer refused to say anything as Aleese led us out of the Waiting Room and through the minefield of lab equipment to the main entrance of the biology sector. There was a guard waiting there who said ka had been sent to take us to the medical sector for another checkup.

Before we left, I turned to Aleese and gave ka a hug. Ka stiffened, which I kind of expected since I hadn't seen anyone hug yet on Iyeena. I stepped back and placed my hands on the sides of ka face.

"That's how we express gratitude on my planet. Thank you for showing us that."

Aleese smiled. I smiled, too, and turned to follow the guard, Teer glowering by my side.

My checkup with Lorana was pretty short. Ka monitored my vitals again and took some more fluids. I barely had time to get comfortable in the hospital chair before ka told me ka was finished.

As ka walked me to the main entrance to the medical sector where the guard was waiting for Teer and me, Lorana asked how I was settling into my new home.

"It's nice. It doesn't really feel like home yet, though." I didn't want to offend anyone by criticizing the house they had given me, but I didn't want to lie, either.

"I'm sure there are a lot of changes to get used to, but don't worry. You're here until your host body dies. It should feel like a home by then."

I hoped ka was right. We walked a while longer, and then, because I felt uncomfortable around Lorana when no one was saying anything, "At least life didn't really have to change for my family back home."

Ka stopped walking and turned to look at me. "No one told you?"

This was the first time I had seen Lorana display any sort of sincere emotion. Ka eyes softened – concern, sympathy.

"Told me what?" I knew that whatever ka was going to say next couldn't be good news.

"Your original body went into an irreversible coma after your brain was copied."

It took a moment for me to understand the full meaning of ka words. I wanted to fall to the ground and hit things. I wanted to cry, but knew I wouldn't be able to. I wanted to do those things, but I didn't, because Lorana already seemed to dislike me and I didn't think ka opinion of me would improve any if I had a breakdown in ka lab.

Ka walked me the rest of the way to the medical sector entrance and I waited silently with the guard for Teer to be done with ka checkup.

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Teer ranted about what we had seen in the Waiting Room the whole way back to ka house, but I was too lost in my own thoughts to pay close attention to anything ka was saying.

Dakota never got to talk to Justin again. She – no, I – decided to go through with the copy even though I knew it was dangerous. Did he ever marry again? Did he ever get to start the family he wanted?

I heard something crash and looked up to see what Teer was doing. Why was ka stomping around the house like tiny little fires were springing up every few feet and it was ka personal responsibility to put them all out?

"Take me to them," ka demanded.

I was lost. What had ka been talking about? "Them who?"

"The Rememberers. I want to meet them."

And I knew, then more than ever, that it would be less painful not to argue.

10

Family Glue Earth

The smell of cheddar and jalepeño omelettes wafted into my room through the cracks around the door. I looked around the room, trying to remember where I had put my shirt before I got into the shower. The room was still dark even though the sun had been up for hours. I refused to sleep with the blinds open because I was a pain to deal with whenever I had to wake up before 9. Justin was the early riser in the family.

I found my shirt and walked downstairs to eat breakfast with Justin like we did every Saturday. He runs his own graphic design and marketing business, so he works from home and often works weekends. Sometimes, when I'm writing a paper or working on small research projects, I can work from home, too. Those days are the best, when he stays in his office and I go to the small reading nook that made me want to buy this house in the first place, and we communicate with each other through songs.

But I was waiting for a simulation to finish running on my computer at work, so I had planned to spend the day doing boring adult things, like cleaning and balancing some of our finances.

Justin was already sitting at the table, reading a book, when I came downstairs. I kissed the top of his head on my way to the kitchen to make some coffee.

When I came back, I sat down and asked how work was going. I knew he was working with a particularly difficult client who kept sending back his concept drawings and demanding things be changed.

As he told me about the new sketch he had drawn up that morning, I sliced open my omellete and stuffed it full of the homefries he had put on the side. I asked if I could see the sketch and he went to his office to get it.

He sat down and put the drawing in front of me. I wiped my hands on a

napkin and picked it up to get a better look. The drawing was a silhouette of a baby holding a detailed bottle with the name of the formula company written on the side.

"It looks great, babe," I said, handing the paper back to him.

He set the paper aside and grabbed my hand. "Dakota, I want to talk to you about something."

I nodded, shoving another forkful of potato-stuffed omelette into my mouth.

"I want to have a baby."

Gulp. I coughed to dislodge the half-chewed food from my throat. "You want to do what now?"

Justin put my coffee mug in my hand and I took a drink, more to give myself something to do while my brain was racing than because I actually needed the caffeine jolt. Justin's words were more than enough to wake me up.

"It makes sense. We're happy together, we're financially secure. You'd be a great mom. I want to have a baby!"

I put the mug down and turned to look at him. "You mean you want *me* to have a baby."

Whenever Justin got really nervous or scared, his middle school stammer returned. It happened when he proposed and it was happening again now. "Well, er, I m... mean, well." He took a deep breath before he continued. "You would technically carry the baby, yes, but it would be ours!"

I closed my eyes and started shaking my head. He knew how much I hated surprises and how uncomfortable I was with big, life-changing decisions. It took me a whole week to accept his proposal!

"What happens if I have to leave my job at the observatory, huh? We'd have to move. Are we just going to do that with a new kid?"

Justin tried to grab my hand again, but I pulled it away. "Obviously that wouldn't be ideal, but we'd figure it out."

"We wouldn't be able to travel for years."

"We don't travel much now!"

"Where would be even put a baby?"

"I'd give up my office."

I knew Justin would have a response to any problem I pointed out. He planned things almost as carefully as I did, so he must have been thinking about having a baby for a while. I also knew that I would resort to petty insults once I ran out of things that could be considered legitimate concerns.

Before I could say anything I knew I would regret, I stood up and took my plate and mug into the kitchen. Leaning against the counter, I thought

about my options. I could go back into the dining room and have what would almost certainly turn into a fight, or I could leave.

I pinged a car with my tracker band. It was waiting outside in less than five minutes.

Justin stopped me on my way to the door. "Where are you going?"

"To work." I walked past him and opened the door.

"It's Saturday. You've never gone into work on a Saturday."

I was already standing on the other side of the door, trying to get myself under control so that I wouldn't slam it shut.

"And you've never shown any interest in having kids. I guess we're both trying things out today."

I didn't trust myself not to slam the door, so I left it open and walked to the waiting car.

11

History Lesson Iyeena

Having a job to do cleared my mind a little bit and I poked my head out of the door to see if the guards were still standing in the middle of Visitors' Village. There were more than there had been before we went to talk to Landric. No one had ever explicitly said that they were there to keep us from going anywhere, but I had my suspicions. And given Teer's obviously upset state, I figured that even a well-intentioned guard would stop us to ask questions. What's more, I didn't know how to lie in my Mowleean body, so I wouldn't even be able to hide from them that we were going to see the Rememberers, or the Players, or whatever they wanted to call them.

"Well," I said, turning around to look at Teer, who was smoldering in the middle of the sitting room, "looks like we we're gonna have to find a way to sneak out."

Ka stopped angrily stomping back and forth to give me a confused look.

"What, have you never had to sneak out before?" I gave a small chuckle of disbelief.

Teer's expression didn't change. "I literally don't understand what you're saying. It sounds like gibberish."

Then I realized that we were dealing with another issue of cultural barriers. Clearly, the concept of sneaking out didn't exist on Odahi. Maybe they didn't believe in lying? Or maybe it had something to do with the fact that independence seemed to be such a big deal there – no one had to sneak out because no one was ever told to stay in one place. Whatever it was, I had to give Teer a crash course on how we did things back on Earth.

"Okay, Teer. There are guards out in the middle of the plain, and I don't think they would approve of us going to talk to the Rememberers. So we have to leave without them noticing us. Nod if you understand." Teer nodded. Ka

was an alien, not an idiot.

I tried to think of a plan but found that I was at a loss. All of my sneaking strategies were specific to growing up in woodland Oregon back on Earth. There were no trees to climb out onto here. There was no nighttime to hide our actions, either. Visitors' Village was constantly illuminated by some artificial light source, probably because Iyeena's irregular rotation meant there weren't regular sleeping schedules. I looked to Teer. "So... got any ideas?"

For someone who had never had to sneak around, ka sure was good at it. It was obvious to both of us that we would have to create some sort of large distraction. It was obvious to Teer that our – and probably all the Visitors' – ineptitude with Mowleean technology was our ticket out. There was no reason for us to wait, so once we had our heist planned, we started to make moves.

Teer and I left ka house using the back door by the kitchen. Ka had no sense that we were doing anything wrong, but I had to consciously remind myself to walk normally as we made our way to the other side of Visitors' Village. Still, I wasn't fully confident in my acting abilities, which is why we were walking behind the houses, out of the guards' sight.

We walked until we came to a house that smelled like cooking meat. There was a small window that looked into the kitchen, so we took turns peeking in to see if anyone was there. I recognized the person cooking as one of the chemists who had been in our group when we explored the Iyeenan surface. The chemist eventually left the room and we waited for what felt like forever, hoping that if the ka didn't come back soon, it meant ka had gone to take a nap while the food cooked. We waited for as long as we could before we gave up and decided to go in.

None of the doors on either of our houses locked, so we knew we would have no trouble getting into anyone else's home. There was some uncertainty at play, of course. We had no way of knowing if or when the chemist would come back to the kitchen. But Teer was adamant about going to talk to the Rememberers, so we crept – well, I crept and Teer practically sauntered – in through the back door.

Whatever the chemist was making already smelled better than anything Teer or I had managed to make. I kept watch as Teer turned the setting on the oven to the one that tended to make food burst into flame. Then ka turned up the intensity so that when a fire did start, it would be big enough to get the guards' attention.

We were on our way out the back door before I realized how terrible it would be to leave a sleeping person alone in a house that we had just set on fire. I ran back in and knocked a bunch of things onto the floor, making

enough noise to wake up the heaviest of sleepers.

Neither of us knew how long it would be before the oven caught fire, so we made our way back to our house and waited for something to happen. We didn't have to wait long. When the guards ran toward the smoke, we ran across the plain of Visitors' Village to the main staircase.

Our plan was to go directly to the Rememberers' cave, but that changed when we got to the Rift and realized that neither of us could remember the last time we ate. We also knew that we still didn't have any form of currency, so our only real chance of getting food without stealing was to find Tinch.

We walked up and down the rows of vendors. Some of them were actual shops – makeshift little shacks that looked like they had seen better days, but at least they were permanent. I figured out pretty quickly that those vendors were the envy of all the people who sold their wares out of mobile carts. As we walked, our noses assaulted every few steps by a new and overwhelming scent, Teer and I commented on how empty the Rift was. I mean, there were still enough people that I couldn't put my arms out to my sides without hitting strangers, but it was practically dead compared to the last time we had been there.

There was a commotion up ahead of us and I looked up to see a blue-haired Mowleean holding a young child. My knees gave out under my weight and I nearly fell into Teer.

"What's wrong?" Ka helped me right myself and looked over me, concerned.

I hadn't told Teer what Lorana had told me. Teer's ranting hadn't really left any opportunity for me to say anything on the way back from the research compound, not that I would have if I had been given the chance. I'm not the kind of person who believes in the healing power of talking about feelings, but I do believe in comparing myself to others.

"Teer, why are you here?" Ka let go of my arms where ka had grabbed me when I stumbled.

"There was a parasite on Odahi that was killing the crops. The Mowleean left a pesticide, but I wanted to come here to find a more permanent solution." I barely heard ka, and my inattention must have shown on my face. "Why are you here, Dakota?"

My eyes wandered around, occasionally glancing off of Teer's own but never actually landing there. "I don't know anymore."

Teer didn't try to get me to say anything else, but ka clearly didn't know how to make me feel better. So after standing in the middle of the path for a while longer, ka took my arm and led me away to find Tinch.

Considering how many rows of vendors there were and the fact that Tinch operated out of a mobile cart that almost certainly wasn't in the same place

as last time, we found ka faster than we thought we would. We could tell we were getting close when we smelled the mouthwatering scent of ka stuffers.

Tinch was sitting on a stool next to the container full of stuffers. Ka wore a surly expression on ka face, but it wasn't the intentional surliness ka had worn when we first met. It was just ka face. Based on that, I guessed business had been good that day.

I hadn't said a word since I saw the Mowleeen baby, so it was up to Teer to convince Tinch to give us free food. "Hi, Tinch." I didn't hear any false cheer in ka voice, which was good because I knew it would just deepen the snarl on Tinch's face. Teer reached out to clasp Tinch's hands. "How's business?"

The snarl deepened anyway. "You want more free food." Distracted as I was by my thoughts of Justin and the life I never got to lead back on Earth, I struggled to describe how ka voice sounded. Was it gravelly? Raspy? Smoky? Some combination of all three? Whatever it was, it wasn't very pleasant. But I liked Tinch. Ka reminded me of Mr. Riley from back home. I imagined that Tinch's neighbors always complained about ka, but would be really upset if ka died.

"Yes," Teer responded. I didn't expect any trouble. Tinch was obviously miserly and frugal, but ka seemed like ka knew when ka had a debt to pay. And, whether ka liked it or not, ka owed us.

After a pause, Tinch moved from ka stool and reached into the container to pull out two stuffers. Teer and I finished them before Tinch had hobbled back to the stool, so ka handed each of us another one. I didn't really taste anything as I ate, but I knew it had been a long time since I had eaten anything, so I forced myself to finish the second stuffer.

As we ate, Tinch sold a few more stuffers to people from the crowd. Teer reached over and placed a comforting hand on my back. Once they left, Teer walked over to stand by Tinch's stool. "Why is the crowd so much thinner now than it was the last time we were here?"

"Emergence Day."

We waited for ka to offer more of an explanation, and when it became clear that none was coming, Teer asked, "What's Emergence Day?"

Tinch managed to look bored and annoyed at the same time. "It's something the Players do. Some sort of festival to celebrate our people crawling out of Lake Wiyoo."

Teer stood up to ka full height, which meant ka was towering over Tinch. "We're on our way to see the Rememberers." There was extra emphasis put on that last word, a judgmental kind of emphasis directed toward Tinch's referring to them by a name they didn't claim for themselves.

The judgment certainly didn't go unnoticed. "Why would you want to

go see them? All that singin' and dancin'. It's not productive. They're not adding anything useful to the world. They're worse than slashes."

I could see the anger building on Teer's face, so I put a calming hand on ka shoulder to remind ka that we didn't want to start a scene. Ka took a deep breath before ka spoke again. "We were in the research compound earlier and Landric said something about the Remem... Play... them. We were curious. You know how we scientists get when we want to know something."

At Teer's mention of the research compound, Tinch's face scowled more deeply than I thought was possible. I felt the space between us warm up and ka flicked out ka tongue in a gesture that I hadn't seen before on Iyeena, but I figured it couldn't mean anything good.

"Oh, I know as much about Thinkers as I need to know. We tell our children horror stories about you lot, you know. 'Be good, kids, or the Thinkers will come and take you away to use you in their experiments.'" There was a slight but unmistakable look of fear in ka eyes. "Whenever I was bad, my ma would tell me about this room where the Thinkers kept people trapped and waited for them to die so they could use their bodies for their *science*."

Ka shook ka head, leaving the fear behind. But the disdain was still fully present in ka voice when ka said, "Those are just stories we tell to keep the kids in line. But it doesn't matter if they're true. The Thinkers wouldn't know an honest day of work if it landed right on top of them."

"What do you mean?" I wanted to keep Tinch talking because it helped distract me from my own thoughts about Justin.

"I mean the Thinkers control everything. You think they have any idea what it's like to dig for rock until your hands are bloody? You think they even know what it's like down here in the Rift? Ha!"

Tinch attended to a few more customers. It was clear that the Thinkers had most of the power on Iyeena. I could see it in the way people spoke and acted. But I didn't know why. The customers left, several of them holding multiple stufferers in their hands. "Tinch, why do the Thinkers have so much power?"

"Well aren't you two just full of questions?" Ka settled in on ka stool. "I'll tell you this story if you say you'll leave me alone when I'm done. All you want to do is talk and eat my stufferers for free. It's exhausting." Teer and I each spit on the ground like ka had done before and our deal was struck.

"Alright. No questions or any other interruptions. The next word I want to hear from you is 'bye.' Got it?" We nodded. Teer and I both hunkered down to listen – figuratively, of course, because there was nowhere to sit besides the ground, which looked less than comfortable.

Tinch paused for a moment to prepare the story, and when ka spoke

again, it was like a different person was talking to us. I wondered if this was another tale that Mowleeanans in the lower tiers told their children.

"The Mowleeanans didn't always live in these tunnels. We started off underwater. Then one day, according to legend, the first Mowleeanans emerged from Lake Wiyoo. They didn't look like we look now, but there are some similarities. We still have webbing between our fingers and thick skin, and we still have breathing slits like they did, but ours breathe air now instead of water.

"Anyway, the first Mowleeanans lived off of the land on the surface. They grew crops and fished. Everyone worked together and there weren't Thinkers or Builders or anything like that. Life was simple.

"Then the Amree came. They came from our sister planet because everything was dying. The sun was pulling their planet and it was getting too hot to survive. The few Amree who made it to Iyeena said they were the only survivors and asked to take refuge here.

"Of course we agreed to let them stay. We had no reason not to. But they changed things here. They brought technology with them, and some Mowleeanans were so fascinated by it that they insisted the Amree teach them how to use and make it. They were the first Thinkers, and together they built on the technology that the Amree brought.

"After a long time, we noticed our own temperatures rising. Lake Wiyoo was evaporating and the darkness didn't come as regularly as it had before. The same thing that had happened to the Amree's planet was happening to Iyeena. And it would destroy us, too, unless we did something about it.

"Everyone turned to the Thinkers to save us and they secluded themselves to think of a plan. Occasionally, they would go back to the Mowleeanans and ask people to make something for them. They became the first Builders. But they ran out of materials before long, so they had to send people away to find more. They became the first Getters.

"It was a long time before the Thinkers came up with a working plan. Some people say it took generations, and that the roles got passed down through families.

"The plan was to build a society underground. The Thinkers planned everything out, the Builders made the equipment, and the Getters brought the supplies. Everyone else was put to work to actually do the digging.

"Once the first tunnels were done and everyone was inside, the Thinkers established themselves as the leaders. And everyone was happy about that at first. The Thinkers kept coming up with ways to improve our lives, like agriculture and medicine. And by the time people realized that the Thinkers had kept the best thoughts to themselves, it was too late to change anything."

Without another word, Tinch got out of his seat and moved to lure some

more customers to ka cart.

I thought about what Tinch had said about the Amree – how they came from their planet and pretty much established themselves as the leaders of the Mowleens. And all because their planet had become uninhabitable...

...exactly like the planet I had studied in college! The Amree's planet had become *sun pulled* – it was tidally locked, just like my research had said it would be. I hadn't been wrong – well, not back then anyway. We assumed the Mowleens were from the planet I studied because we thought it was the only one in its system.

I didn't actually know anything about Iyeena at all. My being chosen for this mission was a complete fluke. Well, fluke or not, I had a mission to complete. The Mowleens *had* to know something about how to slow down the tidal locking process.

My realization helped clear my head of the fog that had clouded it since my talk with Lorana. Sure, my choice to come to Iyeena had ended my life back on Earth, but it could save billions.

Teer pulled me away as I said my final mental goodbyes to my old life on Earth.

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It was Teer's first time on the Getters' tier, but it may as well have been my first time, too, because it looked so completely different from what I had seen before. The last time I had walked through the Getters' huts, it had seemed like a ghost town. But as Teer and I made our way across the plain to the final flight of stairs, we were joined by hundreds of excitedly chattering Mowleens.

We moved with the crowd, both because we didn't really have a choice and because we knew we would eventually end up in the Rememberers' cave if we did.

I could hear the music clearly from the stairs. It was more upbeat than the music I had heard the Rememberers play before, a combination of fast-paced instrumentals and occasional rousing vocals. I couldn't tell what they were saying, but I could tell that it was making me want to dance, and as I looked around at the crowd, I saw that other people were feeling the urge, too. I also saw that many people were dressed up. They had traded in their dusty grey Getters' outfits for more colorful ones. The colorful clothes were still dusty and faded, but it was clear that they had once been as bright as the clothes I had seen the Rememberers themselves wearing. Some had even drawn on their faces. It was a day for celebration.

When we reached the bottom of the stairs, we were met by a scantily clad Mowlean, one of dozens handing out scarves. Teer and I stared at the

cloth in our hands and then looked up to see what everyone else was doing with them. The Getters around us were using them as blindfolds, tying them over their eyes before they were led away by the scarf providers.

I leaned over to one of the Getters standing closest to us. "What's happening? Why is everyone putting on blindfolds?"

Ka answered without even looking at me, too preoccupied with trying to tie fasten the scarf around ka head. "The way to the Rememberers' cave is secret. It always has been."

Ka finished tying the scarf on and held out ka arm to be guided by one of the barely dressed attendants who I realized must have been Rememberers.

Could it really be true that no one had ever found the Rememberers' cave? I guess I hadn't technically found it. I had gotten lost and Keeloa had saved me. I secured the scarf over my eyes and grabbed Teer's hand, waiting for someone to come and lead us to the cave.

Instead we were led to a kind of vehicle. I guess the Rememberers didn't even want us to remember which turns we took to get to their cave. I chuckled to myself at the irony.

Filed with mystery and suspense though it was, the ride was anything but quiet. I could hear the Rememberers' music getting louder and the hundreds of Getters around us were talking, laughing, and trying – and failing – to sing along. I could feel the excitement of the crowd growing as we moved closer and closer to the cave.

After so many turns and bumps that I felt thoroughly lost – though not as scared as I had my first time in the tunnels – the vehicle stopped and my blindfold was removed. Once my eyes adjusted to the new light, I saw that Teer and I were standing at the mouth of the Rememberers' cave.

My plan had been to take Teer directly to Keeloa so ka could ask questions and leave. But the Emergence Day festival kind of threw a wrench in that plan. Thousands of people were mingling inside the cavern and the music was so loud that Teer and I could barely hear each other, let alone coordinate a search and find mission.

We were standing high enough above the floor that we could see almost everything that was happening below. There were different dance performances going on in different parts of the cave. A group of Rememberers seemed to be putting on a show in one corner. I saw several stations set up around the floor where it looked like Rememberers were painting on people's faces.

Teer and I looked at each other, looked back at the mass of people below us, and realized that the only thing we could do was join them and hope we got lucky.

We had barely set foot on the floor of the cavern before someone in an

outlandish and revealing shimmering blue outfit thrust a tall, thin drink in each of our hands. Ka had moved onto the the people walking in behind us before we had time to react. I looked down to see that the drink I was holding was the same color as the outfit the person who handed it to me had been wearing. I held the container up to my nose and the smell alone made me feel tipsy. When I glanced over at Teer, ka was holding the container upside down over ka mouth, shaking out the last few drops of whatever had been inside. I figured that if the smell had affected me so strongly, chugging the entire drink would hit Teer pretty hard, pretty quickly. I decided that at least one of us should be completely in charge of our faculties, so I handed my drink off to the next drunken reveler who passed by.

As we made our way across the floor, our path was blocked several times by wandering dancing troupes. The movements were graceful and fluid, and even though the various troupes were all performing completely different styles of dance, they all perfectly matched the music that was playing out over the entire cavern.

Every time Teer or I didn't have something in our hands, someone would appear in front of us and offer us food or drink. I let my nose make decisions for me, but Teer was already so drunk and so happy that I didn't think it could really hurt to let ka take whatever ka wanted. And if I'm being completely honest, the scientist in me really wanted to know how much food and drink a Mowleean body could take in before it got sick.

We were stopped by face painters and trick performers. At one point, I looked over to check on Teer and ka was gone. I panicked and looked around to see where ka had wandered off to. Then I caught a glimpse of ka cornflower blue shirt disappearing in the crowd and I ran after it.

When I caught up to ka, I saw that ka was being dragged along by someone wearing what looked like a metal-plated swimsuit. I followed them until we reached the corner of the cavern where people were putting on a show. The person in the metal swimsuit deposited Teer in the crowd and joined the rest of the ostentatiously dressed performers on the makeshift stage. The show seemed to be a reenactment of the story Tinch had told, but just as the Amree were landing on the shore of Lake Wiyoo, Teer got distracted by a dancing troupe that ka saw out of the corner of ka eye and we were off chasing them before I got to see what the Amree looked like.

I didn't know how long we had been lost in the crowd. It was long enough that even I had mostly forgotten why we had made our way to the Rememberers' cave in the first place. But it all came crashing back to me when I made eye contact with Pakoy, the first Rememberer I recognized from my first visit here.

Ka was wearing a collection of ribbons that swirled around ka body. The

ribbons, like ka hair strip, were gold and copper, and as ka danced, ka looked like fire. No, not fire – lava. The other people in Pakoy's dance troupe were similarly dressed, and together they moved slowly through the crowd. Their movements were deliberate and forceful, but hypnotizing. No wonder their dancing had dragged Teer away from the play we had been watching.

Pakoy broke away from ka dancing troupe and walked over to us. Ka was so angry that we started to feel the heat rolling off ka body when ka was still several steps away. Now ka looked and felt like lava.

"You shouldn't be here!" Pakoy was standing so close to me that I could feel ka breath on my face as ka yelled. From that distance, I could see swirls of red and orange paint all over ka body, completing the lava effect.

I don't know if Teer was too drunk to notice the hatred Pakoy was throwing our way or if ka was choosing not to acknowledge it, but whatever the reason, ka didn't seem phased at all by Pakoy's aggressive approach. "But it's a celebration! We're celebrating with you."

Pakoy shot Teer a scalding glare. "This day used to mean something. Everyone knew how to properly respect it. This is what it's turned into." Ka swept an arm out to encompass the debauchery around us. "And we wonder why everyone thinks the *Players*..." – ka said the word with such contempt that I physically had to take a step back – "...are the punchlines to every joke on Iyeena." Pakoy grabbed my shoulders and spun me around to face the crowd. "*They* can celebrate this day, even if they don't fully understand what it means anymore. But you can never be a part of this because you will never be one of us. You will only ever be a parasite."

My back went cold and I turned around to find that Keeloa had pulled Pakoy away from me yet again. The silver highlights in Keeloa's hair were accented by delicate silver designs curling across ka face. The swirls got thicker and bluer as they moved down ka body. If I stared at them long enough, they started looking like waves, so that when Keeloa walked, it looked like the ripples on the surface of a lake.

The image of Keeloa's water and Pakoy's lava wrestling a few steps away from me was so distracting at first that I almost forgot to pay attention to what they were saying as they scuffled.

"Why are you fighting me, Kee?! You know they shouldn't be here! They stole those bodies."

Keeloa managed to pin Pakoy's arms to ka sides and turned ka so that they were looking eye-to-eye. "It's not their fault, Pakoy. They didn't know. You're just drunk. Come sit down and cool off."

We were on the edge of the crowd, close to one of the walls of the cavern, and I noticed that there were chairs and couches set up along the wall, presumably for situations just like this when people celebrated a little too

hard and needed to rest for a bit.

Keeloa had doused most of Pakoy's fire, but ka was still fuming. The two walked over to the wall and sat in chairs. Keeloa beckoned one of the people walking around with drinks and whispered something in ka ear. That same person came back a few moments later carrying a cup. Keeloa held the cup out to Pakoy, who refused it at first, but Keeloa kept ka arm out until Pakoy gave in and took it from ka hands.

As Pakoy drank from the cup, I grabbed Teer's hand and pulled ka over to the wall where they were sitting. Teer had wanted to meet Keeloa, and though I'm sure ka hadn't intended to be drunk when ka did it, this might be ka only chance. Plus, I had a question to ask.

"Keeloa, this is my fellow Visitor and friend, Teer. Ka wanted to meet you."

For a moment, Teer stood frozen, eyes wide as ka tried to think of the best way to make a good first impression on Keeloa. Ka recovered quickly and reached out with the middle three fingers of ka left hand, touching them to Keeloa's forehead in an Odahian greeting. Keeloa looked surprised, but didn't flinch away and returned Teer's gesture.

"Hello, Teer."

Teer smiled, and I understood why. Hearing Keeloa's voice directed at you was like being found by a patch of sunlight on a cloudy day – even though you knew it would end any second, it made you feel warm in a way that totally made up for being cold the rest of the time.

I hated to interrupt the moment, but I had to ask my question. "Keeloa, what did Pakoy mean when ka said we stole these bodies?" I had been in the Waiting Room. I had seen the place where they cared for people until the became hosts for Visitors. Hadn't they chosen to be part of the program?

Keeloa leaned forward in ka seat and looked me in the eye. "Pakoy shouldn't have said that." Ka shot Pakoy a reproachful glance. "You didn't steal them. The Thinkers did."

"No, you're wrong." I had learned a long time ago not to put too much trust in anyone whose voice or looks could melt other people's inhibitions. And so even though it took a conscious effort on my part, I pushed back against what Keeloa was telling me. "I've seen the people who are waiting to become hosts. They're not prisoners. Landric said they could leave any time."

Keeloa opened and closed ka mouth, trying to find the right words to say. "They're not technically prisoners, you're right. But it's also not really possible for them to leave."

Ka didn't offer any more of an explanation, and I wondered if it was because ka thought there was no point in telling me any more or because ka

didn't know what else to say. Then I remembered something else Landric had said.

"If the people in the Waiting Room aren't prisoners, why did you try to kill them?"

Keeloa's stomach gurgled, but it wasn't like a laugh you give when you think something is funny. It was angry, harsh. "Is that what they call it? The Waiting Room? That sounds so pleasant." Pakoy had finished ka drink and came to stand behind Keeloa. "No, that place is more like a farm. They breed hosts there. They're born there, and never taught that they have any other options."

This was news to me. I looked over at Teer, whose drunken giddiness had been replaced by a look of righteous anger as Keeloa spoke. Clearly, ka was absorbing everything Keeloa had to say, but I couldn't bring myself to believe any of it.

"And we didn't try to kill them. A more radical group of Rememberers tried to rescue them about half a burn-through ago. They set fire to some lab as a distraction. But they didn't mean anyone any harm! We don't believe in harming others. I can't say the same of the Thinkers, though. Our people tried to set their prisoners free, and most of them died in the process."

I was trying to think of a response to that when Pakoy pushed past Keeloa and gave me a look so full of hurt and hatred that I half expected to burst into flames.

"But if killing them was the only way to make sure they'd never be violated by the likes of you, I'd kill every single one of them." Ka flicked his tongue out at me and I thought he might try to kill me right there.

I didn't have to think of a response to that. Without another word, I grabbed Teer's arm and led her out of the Rememberers' cave, starting the long trek back to Visitors' Village.

12

Why Me? Earth

The first person I met at NASA headquarters was a large man – not tall, but large – with tired eyes. He reminded me of Santa, if Santa were 20 years younger and wore power suits.

"Hi," he said, holding out his hand, "I'm Charles Kaplan." He looked like a rat, and not in the cute way – because I happen to think rats are adorable – but in the kind of way that made me suspect he would steal a piece of cheese out of my hand if I had been holding one. "I've been appointed as the liaison to the Mowleens. I assume you've been briefed on the situation?"

I shook his hand and nodded my head. After I had agreed to visit headquarters, I had received a more detailed description of who the Mowleens were and what they wanted. The aliens who had contacted us were scientists from a planet they called Iyeena. Earth was just one of hundreds of planets in the galaxy they had found with sentient life, and after observing us long enough to learn our major languages and see that we weren't useless, they wanted us to trade knowledge with them via this exchange program.

"Do you have any questions?"

I had too many questions. Most of them, I figured, would be answered later, once I actually met the Mowleens. But there was one question that only Charles could answer.

"Yeah, how did they convince people on Earth to agree to this program? You don't expect me to believe that aliens showed up and said 'Give us one of your scientists' and NASA was all, 'Yeah, that seems like a great idea!'" I stepped closer to Charles and held out a hand as if I were about to inspect his head. "They're not controlling your minds, are they?"

Charles – he didn't seem like a Charlie – backed away from my hand and glared. I knew we wouldn't get along as soon as I saw him, so I didn't think

I was losing any great professional relationship.

"No, they're not controlling our minds. We've been negotiating with the Mowleens for months. I can't speak for the Russian or Chinese governments, but we didn't agree to participate in their exchange program until they shared some very useful technology with us."

"What kind of technology?"

Charles grinned smugly. "That information is classified."

I frowned, assured of my theory that Charles and I were never meant to be best buds.

"If you want to know more, you should ask the Mowleens directly."

I nodded my head so hard I gave myself a small headache.

"Okay, then. I'll take you to the communication room. We've been using computers to communicate with them because they can't survive in our atmosphere." He started walking away.

"Wait," I called after him. He turned back, eyes narrowed in annoyance that I had dared to interrupt him. "Why me?"

Charles blushed. "Well, most importantly, the planet they call Iyeena is the planet we call EPIC 206032309." He paused to look for a spark of recognition in my eyes, and of course he saw one. EPIC 206032309 was the planet I had written my senior research thesis on in college. "You're quite literally the foremost expert on their planet."

That wasn't news. The name of the planet had been included in NASA's original letter. But I knew it wasn't enough to be selected for a mission like this. "What else?" I asked.

"Umm... Well, there's also your unique background in anthropology."

He was right. I had also studied anthropology in college, and went on to get a Masters degree in cultural anthropology before I got my Ph.D. in astronomy. But it still seemed like he was hiding something. "And...?"

"Well, you see, er, my superiors thought that this program would be an excellent, er, opportunity to follow our new... mission statement." I blinked, slowly. "You know, our new mission to increase, er... diversity."

In that moment, as I watched Charles shift his weight from foot to foot and wring his hands, I could tell he was more uncomfortable telling me the reason than I was hearing it. They wanted to make a publicity stunt out of this, out of me. I let it sink in for a second, and looked up to meet his eyes.

"Lucky you. You met your diversity quota. But you also got the best damn astronomer you could have found for this job. Now let's go talk to some aliens."

My first time talking to the Mowleeanans felt more like an interview than anything else. It probably was an interview, actually. They had to choose between three scientists from around the world. When you're running an interplanetary exchange program, you get to be picky.

They mostly just wanted to know about my science. I explained that I had studied their system in college, but they didn't seem too impressed. I talked about some of the research I did in graduate school and as a postdoc studying galactic habitable zones. None of it seemed to interest them.

Since it didn't seem like I was doing too well in the interview, anyway and I was dying to tell someone about my tidal locking results, I decided to talk about that, too. I couldn't tell anyone on Earth, but I had a feeling the Mowleeanans would be able to keep the secret.

"A few weeks ago, I ran a simulation that told me Earth might be completely tidally locked to the sun in a few thousand years."

I waited the time it took for my words to reach them in their orbit around Earth and for their response to be sent back. I fully expected their response to be as unengaged as the rest had been.

"Tidal locking? What is that?" The digitized South African voice was incapable of sounding intrigued, but it was the first time they bothered to ask me a question about the specifics of what I had done.

I explained that tidal locking was when a planet or some other satellite was affected by the gravity of its host in such a way that its "day" became just as long as its "year."

"And you discovered this effect by yourself?"

I was wary of taking full credit for something that could potentially destroy my reputation as an astronomer, but I figured it would do more harm than good to lie to the Mowleeanans.

"I didn't discover tidal locking, but I discovered that it might start affecting Earth soon."

The Mowleeanans never sent a response back. After waiting for about 10 minutes, I figured the interview was over and went to find Charles.

13

Crossing Signals Iyeena

By the time we got halfway up the main staircase, Teer had forgotten that ka was angry about something and had reached the stumbling phase of drunkenness, so I half-carried ka up the rest of the steps.

There was no commotion when we got back to Teer's house, so the fire we started must not have caused that much damage. I was glad. The last thing I wanted was for someone to get hurt because of something I did. I set Teer down in ka bed with a cup of water and some food within reach and got up to go to my own house across the plain.

"Stay," ka called out before I made it out the door.

I turned around to see ka sitting up in bed, more alert than ka had been the entire walk back from the Rememberers' cave. I didn't really want to go home, and it was irresponsible to leave ka alone in such a state. Teer's house didn't have a second bedroom like mine and Fogella's did, so I climbed into Teer's bed, clicked the light pedal, and settled under the covers.

"Good night, Teer. If you get sick in the middle of the night, aim the other way." I fell asleep to the sound of Teer faintly snoring.

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Teer woke me up by holding a cup of Mowleean coffee under my nose. "Nnnrrrgg," I groaned, batting ka hand away.

"Dakota, you should wake up. The faster you get ready, the faster we can go talk to the Thinkers." Ka pulled me up into a sitting position and put the cup in my hands.

"Why are you in such a good mood? Shouldn't you be hungover?" It was more of a grumble than anything, but Teer didn't seem to have any trouble understanding.

"I feel fine! And I'm still furious about what we learned last night." I was too tired to remind ka that we had no way of knowing that Keeloa and Pakoy had been telling the truth. "But I came here to learn things, and even if the Thinkers are terrible people, I'm going to get as much out of them as I can."

I nodded along, but started drifting back to sleep before I could respond. Teer brought the cup to my mouth and urged me to take a few big gulps. Ka helped me stand up and let go slowly, prepared to catch me if I collapsed back onto the bed.

"I'm up!" I said. It felt like I was back in fifth grade again and my mom was getting me ready for school.

"Good. Okay, then, go and take a shower, because you stink. And make it fast because the guards will be here to collect us soon!"

Teer left the room and I was alone. I didn't know if I was supposed to use the shower there or go back to my own house. I decided to use Teer's shower because I didn't trust myself to make it back to my house without falling back asleep. Plus, I didn't want to have to answer any questions Fogella might have.

When the hot water hit me, I realized how tense my muscles had gotten and I stood there for a long while, despite Teer's warning to be fast. After the third time Teer banged on the bathroom door to get me to hurry up, I stepped out of the shower and tip-toed back to ka room. I reached into the chest of clothes and put on what I pulled out without bothering to look at it.

When I finally emerged, fully clothed, Teer was standing impatiently in the sitting room.

"It took you long enough! Let's go!" Ka moved to run out the door, but I stopped ka.

"Wait, Teer! Don't you want to talk about what we heard in the Rememberers' cave?"

Ka turned around to face me. "What is there to talk about? I may have been drunk, but I heard Keeloa say that the Thinkers stole these bodies, that they were prisoners."

I sat down on the couch to show that I wasn't ready for the conversation to be over. Ka sighed, rolled ka eyes, and sat on the floor in front of me so we could face each other.

"How do you know you can trust them?" I asked.

Teer shook ka head, an almost pitying gesture. "How do you know you can't?"

I didn't have an answer to that, but I knew how important the Thinkers' work was. "Teer, the Rememberers want to end the Visitor Program. If they

had it their way, you and I wouldn't be here. You wouldn't get to learn the things you want to take back to Odahi."

"True. But if they had it their way, there would be dozens of people being held prisoner in the biology sector." Teer stood up and walked out the door before I could say anything else.

By the time I made it to the door, Teer was halfway to the collection of guards standing in the middle of the plain. I followed slowly behind. Teer glowered at me as I approached, but I ignored ka and spoke to one of the guards instead. "You're here to take us to the research compound?" Ka nodded. "Well, what are we waiting for?" I shot Teer a smile and followed the guard as ka walked toward the tunnel behind Visitors' Village.

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Since Teer and I were both astronomers, we were taken to the astronomy sector and put in different observation control rooms to talk to the Thinkers.

I sat down in a chair that was offered to me and looked at the data as it appeared on the computer screen. "Is this data being taken in real-time?"

The Thinker in control of the observation – Daveek – turned to face me. "It's as close to real-time as we can make it. The telescope taking the data is out in orbit, so there's a bit of a delay."

It was so exciting to see astronomy research being done at such an advanced level! Everything about the Mowleens' research seemed like it was way ahead of humans'. Telescope construction? They had us beat there. The secrets of planet formation? They practically knew them all. The fact that they had travelled all over our region of the galaxy meant that they hadn't just researched astronomy, they had seen it. I felt like every question I asked must have seemed so simple to them, but I was going to ask anyway.

"What kind of data are you taking?"

Daveek pointed to the graph on the screen and labeled the axes. They were measuring Iyeena's rotation and evolution speeds as a function of time. "We're monitoring the sun's pull on Iyeena."

This was my chance to ask about tidal locking. "So how long would you say Iyeena has before it becomes completely sun pulled?"

The other Thinkers in the room turned their attention to us. Daveek cleared ka throat. "We're working to make sure that never happens." Ka looked at the other Thinkers.

So they did have a way to slow down the tidal locking! Before I could ask how they were doing it, a Thinker a few seats away said, "We were told your own planet is being pulled by your sun." I nodded. "What are you doing to prevent it?"

Everyone in the room was looking at me so intently that I could almost feel their gazes borrowing into my thick Mowleean skin. It made me nervous, and I had never been very good at answering questions to begin with. "Well, I, er, I'm just taking it one step at a time, you know?"

The Thinkers all looked at each other for a long time. Were they playing some kind of game? Was there some big secret I wasn't supposed to know? I needed to break the silence. "Hey! You know what would be really cool? If you all showed me some of the equipment the Amree brought with them. I'm sure some of that has to do with sun pulling, right?"

Daveek's eyes widened. "How do you know about that?"

I felt like I was about to get in trouble and it made me even more nervous than their questions had. I could feel the space around me heating up, but I didn't know if it was because of my own nerves or whatever Daveek was feeling.

"About the Amree? The Mowleean who contacted my home planet – the collectors – told me about them." It wasn't a lie, but it wasn't the whole truth either. Given the sudden hostility in the room, I didn't think it would be a good idea to mention my adventures in the Rift.

The Thinkers just kept looking back and forth between me and each other. I didn't want to stay there any longer, and then I realized I didn't have to.

I thanked them for showing me their work and excused myself, trying to wait until I was out of their line of sight to run to the astronomy sector entrance.

As I waited for a guard to come get me, I thought about what Keeloa had said. They couldn't end the Visitor Program. It was too important. And sure, the astronomers I had just talked to were a little bit awkward, but so are lots of astronomers back on Earth. Even if what Keeloa had said was true – which I doubted – the science was worth it.

When the guard arrived, ka asked me where I was supposed to go next. "I think it's time for a checkup. Can you take me to the medical sector?"

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I was used to the checkup routine – a few taps here, a few needles there. Lorana didn't even bother explaining what ka was doing as ka did it.

When ka was done, ka helped me to my feet. "I wasn't expecting you. What made you come in?"

I looked around to see if anyone was close enough to hear us. "I have to tell you something. It's important!"

Lorana smiled and crossed ka arms. "Okay, go on. Tell me." I didn't know if ka was being serious or making fun of me, but it didn't matter. I had to tell someone what I had heard in the Rememberers' cave.

"I met the Players. And they're really dangerous. I think they're planning a way to ruin the Visitor program."

Lorana's smile disappeared and ka was all business again. "What makes you say that?"

"Well, I heard them say so. They have this leader, Kee..."

Lorana held a finger up to my mouth. "We better talk more about this in my office."

We in silence, and when we reached ka office, Lorana opened the door and gestured for me to enter first. I heard ka close the door behind me.

"Right, so their leader, Keeloa, has this pl..."

Before I could finish the sentence, I felt a pinch on the side of my neck. And then everything went dark.

14

The Copy Earth

After my call to Justin, I found myself standing with Charles a few steps inside the doorway of a large room that reminded me of a robotics lab I used to pass as I walked to class in college. It was the kind of room that I was always curious about but way too intimidated by to actually enter.

Charles introduced me to the man who walked over to greet us. "This is Gerald, the head engineer on this project."

Gerald held out his hand. "How do you do, mizz," he said with a slightly crooked smile and a length to his vowels that I thought only existed in old western movies. I liked him immediately.

"Dr. Dakota Powell," I said, taking his hand. "You can call me Dakota." I gave Charles a pointed look and he blushed, remembering the time a few days ago when he had presumed to call me Dakota and I told him that it would be best if he addressed me as Dr. Powell. Charles did not have a charming southern accent, or any other charming attributes. I did not like Charles, but I trusted him to do his job. And really, I was in no position to demand another liaison.

"Oh, you're the brave one," Gerald said. But before I had time to ask what he meant, he led us away from the door and toward the center of the room. There were several desks arranged in a wide U, each cluttered with computers and various electronics that I couldn't hope to identify.

There were two tables at the center of the U. One held giant and detailed blueprints that, upon closer inspection, I saw described the 3D holographic structure in the back of the room. I smiled when I saw that, realizing that these engineers had chosen pencil and paper over billion-dollar equipment. I could respect that.

The other table held what I imagined was the first prototype of whatever

the blueprints were describing in that language that only engineers could speak.

Gerald cleared his throat and the handful of other people in the room turned to him.

"Everyone, I'd like y'all to meet Dr. Dakota Powell. She's the reason we're building our baby here." He patted the prototype lovingly.

The other people in the room looked at me then, eyes wide in what could have been surprise, admiration, or trepidation. I gave a shy wave.

"Now, who here wants to explain what our baby does?" Gerald looked around the room and pointed to a woman standing on the outside of the U.

She was tiny – 5'2" at the most – with delicate hands, almost like a musician's, and curly brown hair that hid most of her face. She looked exactly how I would expect a female engineer working on a team with five men to look, and so I expected her to be shy, quiet, and withdrawn.

I was happy to learn how wrong my assumption had been when she walked confidently around the table and shook my hand, introducing herself as Sophie. Gerald beamed with pride when he looked at her, and then he looked at me and broke out into a huge goofy grin when he saw how surprised I was.

Sophie explained to me that the machine on the table in the middle of the room was based on a plan sent to us from the Mowleens. They weren't told what it was at first. After weeks of examining the blueprints, they contacted the Mowleean collectors and made their first guess. Sophie didn't tell me what that guess was, so I figured it must have been embarrassingly wrong. The Mowleens told them what it was and worked with them to build it from then on.

"So," I said, afraid that I had missed something important and that I sounded like an idiot for not following, "what is it?"

"Oh! Right." Sophie laughed and the rest of the engineering team laughed with her. "It's kind of like a brain copying machine. It's going to make a digital copy of your neural network."

Sophie talked so fast and without pause that I literally had to raise my hand to ask a question. "Okay, I know I'm being slow, but why is a copy of my brain helpful?"

"The Mowleens haven't been too forthcoming with the specifics, but when everything is done, we hand over the copy and they take it back to Iyeena to... install it in something there. Do you want to know how it works?"

I laughed. "Will I understand anything you say?"

"I don't see why not," Sophie started to say, but I saw Gerald shaking his head behind her, so I held up my hand to stop her before she could get too

far in her explanation.

"How many test runs have you done?"

Gerald scrunched up his face in a way that told me he had something to say, but that he really didn't want to say it.

"Two, ma'am." His drawl made it sound even more pathetic than it already was.

"And how many successful runs have you done?" I expected the worst.

"Two, ma'am," Gerald said. But he still looked like he had just kicked a puppy.

"So why won't anyone look me in the eye?!"

Charles cleared his throat. It didn't sound like the kind of throat clearing one does to get someone's attention, but the kind that someone does when they're genuinely having difficulty saying something.

"Each machine can only be used once. And we only have enough materials to build three of them."

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I sat in the café in the center of the NASA complex, eating a sandwich and thinking about my conversation with Justin. He had sounded so relieved when I told him I would be coming home. How could I take that away from him?

In that moment, I had a choice.

I could ping him back to tell him about the brain copying machine. I could tell him that it had only been tested twice before, and that only one of those times had been on a human subject. I could explain to him that if I didn't agree to go through with it, America wouldn't be sending a researcher to Iyena, because the Mowleens had chosen me and they were already getting impatient.

Or I could let him I would be home by the end of the week. After all, I probably would be. The machine had passed all of its tests.

"Is someone sitting here?" I looked up and saw a woman with long twists coiled into bun on top of her head, motioning at the seat across from me. "This is the only available."

I realized I was only staring at her and rushed to push the chair out with my feet. "No, no! Please, sit down."

We ate for a little bit in silence. I got lost in my thoughts again.

"Rough day?" she asked.

"Huh?"

She smiled. "You look like something's bothering you. Wanna talk about it?"

I did want to talk about it. And who better to talk to about deeply personal issues than a perfect stranger?

"I do, actually. Thank you." I laughed a little bit of the weight off of my chest. "My name's Dakota."

"Jedidah." We shook hands. "So what's troubling you, Dakota?"

I told her about how Justin wanted to have a baby and about the brain copying machine and its potential to fail.

"What happens if it fails?"

It was a good question, an obvious one that I hadn't thought to ask Gerald and his team. Maybe I figured none of them would know because they weren't medical doctors. Or maybe I was afraid to hear the answer. As I sat there with a perfect stranger, I realized that it was neither of those. I hadn't asked because I knew nothing they could tell me would be worse than not getting to be a part of this mission.

I smiled. "I don't know."

I stood up and thanked Jedidah for listening to my problems.

"Glad I could help!"

But I was already on my way out of the café and to Charles' office.

"I'll do it," I said, running in without knocking, slightly out of breath.

"You don't even know what the potential side effects are."

"I don't care. I'll do it."

Charles nodded. "I'm going to have to ask you to sign something to that effect."

"Fine," I said, "but I have two conditions. One, we do this today." Charles looked like he was going to pee himself with excitement. "Two, no one can ever know how dangerous it was. As far as the rest of the world is concerned, this brain copier has been tested hundreds of times and there are no negative side effects at all."

He hesitated, as if he wanted to ask why this was so important to me, but he shook the question out of his mind and held out his hand. "Deal."

I took his hand. I have never felt more satisfied or more dirty than I did in that moment.

It was Wednesday, the day I would either make history or become a vegetable. Two days before I said I would be home.

After our agreement, Charles left to get the contracts drawn up by one of the lawyers NASA keeps on retainer for moments like this. I had already said my loving goodbyes to Justin – though he didn't realize there was a chance

it could be final – so I wandered around headquarters, looking for a way to occupy my time.

Charles found me sitting at a table in the visitor's center. I returned a pamphlet I had been reading to its shelf and followed him. He was so silent, so serious, like he was leading me to the gallows. I chose to ignore him and his solemnity. No matter what happened, today was going to be one of the most exciting of days of my life.

Charles led me to a small hospital-like room. *Is there anything they don't have at NASA*, I thought to myself as I took off my jacket and set it on the back of a chair by the door. There was one bed in the center of the room. I guessed it was there for me and climbed up into it. I surveyed the room from my new position.

On a table to my left sat the kind of machine they use in actual hospital rooms to monitor people's vital signs. There were a bunch of wires ending in sticky pads already attached to the machine, ready to be attached to my skin. To my right sat the brain copier.

I really didn't want Charles to be there, but he sat down uncomfortably in one of the chairs by the door. "At least this is better than being in a real hospital." He was clearly trying to make small talk.

"Don't," I told him. "I'm not some scared child. If you need to be here because of your job, fine. But we don't need to talk."

He nodded, looking significantly more comfortable now that he knew what was expected of him, and contented himself with looking around the room.

A doctor – at least, that's what I assumed based on the long white coat he was wearing – walked into the room. "I'm Dr. Francis," he said with a warm but professional smile. "You must be Dakota. I'd shake your hand, but then I'd just have to wash them again." He paused for effect and then, "I'm kidding. I have to wash them anyway!" He held out his hand and smiled a smile that made his eyes crinkle behind his large, wire-rimmed glasses. His curly hair flopped onto his forehead and he absentmindedly flipped it away, further adding to his comforting charm.

I smiled at his joke and then leaned back on the bed as he moved to the side of the room to finish preparing.

Five minutes later, one more doctor came in and walked directly to the back of the room to join Dr. Francis. Shortly after that, Gerald strolled into the room in the slow, unconcerned way that only those raised in the south can stroll.

"Hi, Gerald." It was the first time I had smiled all day, and I realized then how nervous I had been. "What are you doing here?"

"Good mornin', Dakota," he said with a slight bow of his head. "I'm here in case my baby decides to misbehave. She has a mighty important job to

do today and I want to be sure she does it right."

"Oh we all want that." Dr. Francis had come to stand on my left as I talked to Gerald. "We're ready to start. Are you?"

I looked around at the four strange men standing around me, a little disappointed that I couldn't share the most important moment in my professional life with my favorite man in the world.

"Would it be too cheesy to say I was born ready?" Dr. Francis gave a small laugh and started attaching the wires to different parts of my body.

As he worked, Dr. Francis explained that the wires he was attaching would be used to monitor my vitals and my brain activity. When he was done, Gerald began setting up the brain copier. He pulled sticky pads and wires out of a drawer and plugged the wires into the machine. The pads felt cold on my skin, one on each temple and one at the base of my neck.

"Okay, Dakota. This should be completely painless," Dr. Francis explained. "But it will take a long time, and it will probably be pretty exhausting." I nodded to show that I understood before I remembered that several spots on my head were connected to wires that limited my range of motion.

"Gerald here is going to ask you questions about yourself. They'll be simple at first, but they'll get more and more complicated as we go on, asking you to retrieve older memories. That machine there is going to be shooting low-voltage bursts of electricity through your brain, following and recording the connections your brain cells make."

Then Gerald flipped a switch on the brain copier and a low buzz filled the space underneath the high beeps from the vitals machine. I couldn't feel any electric shocks, though, which I figured was a good sign.

"Alright, darlin'. We're gonna start real simple. What's your name?"

I answered that question and what must have been a thousand after it before I lost track.

15

Memories Iyeena

My ability to hear returned before my ability to move. "...was careful. Landric sent a guard to follow ka, thinking ka was one of us. But I used the secret passageway in my office."

I opened my eyes to see who was talking: Lorana. I don't know if it was out of fear or anger, but I bolted up and scooted as far away from where ka was standing at the foot of the bed where I had woken up. Keeloa was standing next to ka. I looked around the room, trying to figure out where I was.

I felt someone's arm's wrap around me and tried to wiggle free before I heard Teer's voice telling me to calm down, that everything was okay. "Just listen to what they have to say Dakota. They're really not dangerous. And if you can't trust them just yet, trust me."

Teer's presence brought me a little bit out of my panicked state, enough to speak, anyway. "What are you all doing here? Teer, what's happening?" I couldn't remember the last time I was so scared or confused.

Lorana was the first to speak up. "I sedated you because I couldn't risk you telling anyone else about the Rememberers' plans." There was no emotion in ka voice – no passion, which is what I would have expected to hear, and certainly no remorse. Ka was just stating a fact. "We've waited too long for everything to to be ruined by some Visitor bitch."

"Lorana, please." Keeloa put a calming hand on Lorana's shoulder. "Ka hasn't done anything wrong. And being hostile certainly isn't the way to convince ka that we aren't dangerous." Ka turned to me "If you would just come with us to our cavern, I'm sure you would see that we really are on the right side of things."

I blinked slowly at ka a few times before I started laughing so suddenly

that I felt Teer jolt in surprise behind me. "Ka just *drugged* me and you want me to go back to your cave with you?! Are you serious?"

Keeloa's mouth was frozen open – ka didn't know what to say.

I turned to Lorana. "You're the person I heard talking to Keeloa in the research compound, weren't you?" Ka nodded, once. "I need to know why. Why are you helping them?"

With the same emotionless voice ka had used to answer my first question, Lorana said, "I'm helping them because I'm one of them. My parent was a Rememberer." If ka was expecting some kind of reaction from me, ka didn't get one. "Growing up, I would watch the people in the cave dance and try to copy their moves, but I never could. I couldn't sing or draw or act, either." Keeloa was looking at Lorana with a look of pity in ka's eyes. "No, it's not sad. I wasn't good at them because I didn't enjoy them. I had more of a mind for science." I tried to picture Lorana dancing, but it didn't really work. "My parent knew I'd be happier among the Thinkers, and ka figured it could eventually help our people if we had someone on the inside of the research compound, so ka switched me with a Thinker child a little bit after my first burn-through. Mowleean children don't start developing distinguishing features until much later than that, anyway. I was raised as a Thinker, but my parent sneaked in to see me often and make sure I remembered where I came from."

It seemed like a good enough story. "What happened to that other kid, the one your parents took?"

"Parent," Lorana corrected, forever the doctor. "When Mowleean mating season comes, those who feel ready deposit their eggs in a communal location. Those who wish to rear a child retrieve the eggs they want and take them home to fertilize them. Mowleean children are only raised by one parent."

Furious, I waved ka's explanation away. "Whatever. What happened to the kid your *parent* took?"

"It's Pakoy," Keeloa answered. "And ka doesn't know."

I looked down at my hands and started picking at the webbing between my fingers as I worked my way through my thoughts. Lorana's parent believed so strongly that the Thinkers were doing something wrong that ka gave up the opportunity to raise ka's child. No matter which side I ended up choosing – and it was starting to look more and more like I would have to make a decision – the scientist in me knew it would be irresponsible to do anything before I had all the facts. And having all the facts meant going with them to the Rememberers' cave and listening to whatever they had to say.

"Alright, fine. I'll come with you. But this doesn't mean I'm on your side!" I turned to Lorana. "And if you ever stab me again, I will make you regret it." I got out of the bed and walked to the door before anyone could

point out that I had no way of backing up my threat.

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Keeloa and Lorana led us out the back of the house to a secret tunnel, which explained how they had been able to sneak me, unconscious, into Visitors' Village multiple times. Following, Teer and I looked at each other, annoyed that we hadn't found the hidden passage ourselves sooner.

No one tried to make small talk as we made our way through the maze of interconnecting tunnels, our path illuminated by Keeloa's and Lorana's hand-held lamps. I tried to memorize the turns we were making at first, but I gave that up pretty fast. Instead, I devoted my attention to studying the walls of the tunnels as we walked.

The walls were textured. Smooth grooves and bumps ran together in a pattern that told a story I didn't know how to read. I ran my hand along the wall as I walked, imagining that I was lava, powerful enough to have dictated the story almost a million years ago. That felt wrong, though, almost disrespectful, so I contented myself with being a person lucky enough to be walking through something so wonderfully natural.

I was still lost in thoughtful awe when we finally made it to the Rememberers' cave. I could feel people's eyes on me as I walked, but I tried to ignore them. Keeloa led us directly to a large tent that stood separate from the others. Ka pulled back one of the colorfully painted front flaps and held it open as everyone ducked inside.

My eyes took a moment to adjust to the light inside the tent because it was so much brighter than it had been out in the cave. When I could see again, I wondered if we had been transported back to the medical sector in the research compound. It looked just like the room I had woken up in when I first arrived on Iyeena.

"What is this? I thought you were going to tell me why what the Thinkers are doing is wrong."

"Not tell," said Lorana as ka walked to the computer on the other side of the reclining chair in the middle of the tent. "Show."

I turned to Keeloa, confused.

"When the Amree first landed on Iyeena, one of the technologies they brought with them was a machine that could make digital copies of people's thoughts and memories. One of our ancestors took one of those machines and recorded ka thoughts and memories as the first Thinkers started to take control. Ka passed the machine onto ka children, and they recorded their memories as they watched the Thinkers subjugate everyone around them. Their children, or their children's children recorded memories of the Thinkers coming to take the first hosts for the Visitor program."

Ka looked at me, eyes pleading me to understand, to agree to whatever ka was about to ask me to do.

"That was a few hundred burn-throughs ago. That's why we call ourselves the Rememberers – because a responsibility has been passed down to us through the generations to record and remember what happens here. And now we want you to remember, too."

I looked over at Lorana who was too busy fiddling with the dials on the machine – what I guessed was *the* machine from Keeloa's story – to make eye contact. Teer was standing by my side. At some point in the tunnels, I had grabbed ka hand to keep from tripping and I realized then that I had never let go. Ka squeezed my hand, offering me support as I was being asked to choose between what I saw as two rights.

"How are you going to get me to remember?"

Keeloa pointed to the chair. "We were hoping you would let us download some of our memories into your brain."

The idea terrified me. "But what will happen to *me* if I let some other consciousness inside my head?"

"It's not your head." I turned toward the voice and found Lorana staring at me.

Ka had a point. If I was so worried about what would happen to me, I should be just as worried about what had happened to my host's consciousness.

"Also," Keeloa added, "they're just memories. We're not going to download a whole consciousness into your brain."

Knowing that, plus the fact that I had already made up my mind to listen to whatever they had to tell me – or see whatever they had to show me, as it were – made my decision easy.

I looked up at Lorana as I sat down in the chair and felt a smug kind of satisfaction when I saw a look of surprise on ka face. I smiled. "I'm guessing you'll have to use some needles for this." Ka nodded. "I'll let it slide just this once." I settled further into the chair and held out my arms as Lorana got to work preparing everything for the download.

"It will be easier if you try to relax and clear your mind while it's happening. If you struggle too much, you'll just get a headache and probably pass out." I wondered what experiences Lorana was basing ka advice on, so I asked. "I went through the download several burn-throughs ago. Trust me, the memories are going to take hold no matter what. You might as well not hurt yourself in the process."

But before I could take any active measures to clear my head, Lorana inserted an IV needle into my left arm and attached several sticky patches to my head. A small pulse of electricity buzzed through my brain. I closed

my eyes and tried to breathe the way they had taught us to do in that one meditation class I took in college. I didn't know if it would do anything, but it probably wouldn't hurt, either.

It must have worked, though, because one moment I was worrying about that, and the next I was watching a series of events – other people's memories – flash before my mind's eye.

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The sun was reflecting off of Lake Wiyoo and hitting me right in the eye, so that I had to squint as I, along with my whole family, watched the unfamiliar bodies approach.

They looked weird, almost predatory in the way they hunched over as they walked. I wasn't scared, though. There was no point in being scared since I wouldn't be able to do anything if they decided to attack. Instead, I waited and watched.

I watched as a handful of people from my village walked out to meet them. They stood, far out on the plain, gesturing largely to communicate with each other.

I knew the people who had gone out to meet them. I mean, I knew everyone because there weren't that many of us, but I really *knew* the people who had gone out to meet the strangers – Ninse and Akiyo and Kikima. I trusted them. And when they brought the strangers back to our camp with smiles on their faces, I knew I could trust the strangers, too.

They didn't look as scary up close. The little skin that was left bare by the long coats they wore was thick and leathery and they had long flaps on the sides of their heads that turned back and forth whenever someone talked to them. They walked on two legs like us, but they used all four of their limbs when they needed to move quickly or if they were about to lose their balance.

Kikima introduced them as the Amree and told us to welcome them into our homes. One of them ambled over to my family's fire and stood until I motioned that everyone should sit back down. Akiyo came over to join us and I passed out the meal that we had been about to eat before all the excitement. I heard someone a few fires away start singing a song and joined in at the chorus.

Our guest, Joonaa, just stared at the food as the rest of us ate and sang. When we were done, Joonaa produced a strange device from somewhere in ka coat. Akiyo moved to sit next to Joonaa, fascinated by the device, and demanded to be told all about it.

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I was tired, the kind of tired that seeps into your muscles and your bones. The kind of tired that you get when you started digging into the ground before the sun came up and didn't stop until after it had already set.

I couldn't remember a time when my life wasn't like this. My entire life had been dedicated to carrying out a plan created by a group of people I had never met. They called themselves the Thinkers.

As I slept, I dreamed of the future, of a time when my children would be able to look at the ceiling above their head and know that I had built it so that they could escape our harsh and unpredictable sun. Not that I knew anything about the sun. I was never on the surface when it was up in the sky.

I woke up, rinsed off with the small bucket of water I had collected from the vanishing Lake, and headed to work. The people I worked with weren't my friends – you have to know things about people before you can call them friends. And our work took too much of our energy to leave any for idle conversation.

Well, I did know one thing. Our parents had passed on to all of us the words to the same old song. A song about the first time lava came to the shores of Lake Wiyoo. A song about the creation of the mountains that surrounded the plain where the Mowleean first emerged from the water. A song warning about the day when people forgot the old ways and those mountains were destroyed.

I know that because someone started singing it once, and before long we were all singing it. Anything to make the work go faster. But then one of the guards – I'd begun to think of them as the Thinkers' minions, the shadows attached to some body I had never seen – came to tell us that if we had the energy to sing, we weren't working hard enough.

We never sang at work again.

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I watched as my church was torn down, turned to scrap pieces that would be used to build the Thinkers' research compound. There was nothing I could do to stop it. I couldn't fight because I wasn't strong enough to overpower any of the guards standing off to the side of the destruction site. I couldn't reason with them to stop because in their eyes, anything that didn't lead to new knowledge was useless.

I watched as they destroyed and confiscated anything that contradicted hard scientific facts – countless books and pieces of art gone forever because they dared to offer a different point of view.

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My skin was hot as I packed up my few belongings. The Thinkers had told everyone outside of their little pack that we needed to move so they could expand their research compound, and I was angry. My great grandparents had built this place and my children had been born here. Leaving this place felt like leaving my life, but what the Thinkers said was law.

They promised our new home would be even better than this one. There was a fresh water source and more space to expand and call our own. But it wasn't the same, and they either didn't understand that, or they didn't care.

Life was hard when you didn't come from a family of Thinkers, Builders, or even Getters, and my parent wasn't any of those things. For people like us, clothes weren't things you bought, or even things that got passed down from sibling to sibling. They were things that got passed down through entire *villages*. Food was shared, too. If anyone ever had anything extra, it was a cause for everyone to celebrate, because everyone would get a little piece. And people somehow always managed to find a way to be happy. We sang or danced or played silly little games.

That was nice in a way, growing up in a community where everyone cared so much about each other. But when a parent can't properly care for ka child, it eats away at ka. It certainly ate away at mine.

One day, I came home from playing with some of the other children and I saw my parent talking to a stranger. I had never seen a stranger before because I knew everyone in our village. The stranger's clothes were brighter than any I had ever seen and they didn't have any holes in them. Whatever ka was saying was making my parent upset.

The stranger left and I ran ahead to beat my parent home. When ka saw me, ka smiled as if nothing strange had happened, but I knew it was a lie. Ka did it so well, so effortlessly, that I wondered how many times ka had lied to me before.

The next day, my parent was gone. I never saw ka again, but I found huge piles of clothes and food and a small bag full of pebbles – the real kind, not the fake ones my friends and I used when we played our games – in our house. The same thing happened to other children in the village.

A meeting was called to discuss the disappearances. The first person to speak was Tareel, a kind but introverted neighbor. "I was approached by a stranger – a Thinker. Ka offered me food and clothes and pebbles in exchange for me going away to the research compound with ka. I almost did it, too. I don't have any children, you know, but I could have left the payment to the village. But then I asked what I would have to do. What

did the Thinkers need so badly that they were willing to send one of their own all the way down to the slums?"

Ka paused for a moment, either for effect or to regain some composure. I was pretty sure it was the most words I had ever heard ka say at once.

"Apparently, they need hosts for some project they're starting. I didn't know what that meant, but then ka said that part of the agreement was that my children and my children's children would be part of the project, too. That was it for me. They could have done whatever they wanted to me, especially if it meant I'd be able to give back to you all, to my family. But I couldn't let them have my future children."

Without another word, Tareel joined the rest of the crowd and someone else with a story just as sad took ka place at the front.

I thought about what Tareel had said, about what my parent had apparently agreed to. I shivered.

At the end of the meeting, it was decided that we would leave the slums and disappear into the tunnels. No one wanted to risk being found by the Thinkers again.

When I opened my eyes, Teer was standing by my side again and Keeloa was holding a cup of some steaming liquid in front of my face.

"Drink this," ka said. I took the cup without thinking and started to drink. It started to calm my stomach before I even realized it was upset. I smiled my thanks.

After I finished my drink, Teer looked to Lorana and announced that ka wanted to go through the download, too. Lorana shrugged, stood up out of the chair ka had been sitting in, and walked over to prepare the supplies. Teer and Keeloa helped me up out of the reclining chair and over to the chair that Lorana had just left. Teer returned to take my place in the central chair.

It was interesting to see the whole thing happening from the outside. It was fast, definitely faster than it had felt while I was living it. The whole thing was over and Teer was waking up before the silence in the room had a chance to turn awkward.

Keeloa welcomed Teer back with a mug of the same liquid ka had offered me, which ka had poured from a thermos stowed in the bag ka was carrying.

I watched Teer drink the liquid. And then I watched as ka grabbed onto Keeloa's hand. Ka turned around and met Teer's intense gaze.

"I want to help. What can I do?" Teer had been on the Rememberers' side since before ka ever met them, so it wasn't surprising that ka was offering to help. But the intensity in ka words got everyone's attention.

Keeloa had been stunned into inaction, so Lorana answered. "Leave. Let your host have ka body back."

I could see Teer turning Lorana's words over in ka head. Ka didn't ask how it would be done. Ka didn't ask what would happen afterwards. Lorana's words had told ka everything ka needed to know.

"Okay. Let's do it."

That elicited another shocked silence. Again, Lorana was the first to recover.

"We're going to have to copy your brain, like they did on your home planet before you came here. And then we'll have to wipe your neural network from this physical brain. That might hurt, but the real you won't remember ever feeling that because it'll be on its way back to your planet. I'll see to that myself."

Teer nodded and settled back into the chair. "There's no sense in waiting, is there?" Lorana was already setting up the machine to make the copy.

"Wait!" I yelled. It was all happening so fast. "Has this ever been done before? Do you know it's going to work?"

"I know what I'm doing."

That didn't answer my question, and I was about to say so when Teer called me over to stand by ka side.

"Teer, are you sure you want to do this? It could be dangerous." I grabbed ka hand again.

"I'm sure that I *have* to do this." Ka squeezed my hand. "And I come from a place where it's considered more dangerous to take away someone else's freedom. I'm just trying to give it back."

"You're going to give it back before you learn how to save your crops on Odahi? That's the whole reason you came here! If you do this now, you'll have left your family for nothing. They won't be there when you get back, you know." The words were coming out faster than I could get air into my lungs, so I was breathing hard by the end.

Teer squeezed my hand and waited until I had my breathing under control to speak again. "By the time I get back, generations will have passed. I'm sure someone's figured out the crop problem by now." Ka gave a half-hearted laugh but stopped when ka saw that I wasn't joining in. "Besides, I didn't leave them for nothing. I learned things here. And I met you."

I've never been good at goodbyes. They're messy and they always go on for too long. But Teer was the best friend I had on Iyeena. In the admittedly short but intense time that we had known each other, I had started to commit to the idea that Teer would be my best friend for the rest of my life here. And now that idea was gone.

I leaned down and touched my lips to Teer's forehead. It was warm, not from fear or anger, but from excitement. "Bye, Teer." Ka smiled, and I walked out of the tent.

I waited outside for the excruciatingly long time that it took Lorana to copy Teer's thoughts and memories. Someone brought me food at some point, and I ate it without really tasting anything.

I was thinking about the choice I was going to have to make. Science or Mowleean rights? Saving an entire planet from death or granting one person ka freedom?

Keeloa came out of the tent after a while. Ka sat down next to me just as I was changing my mind for what must have been the tenth time. Ka didn't say anything or indicate in any way that ka expected me to say anything. But I said something anyway.

"I can't decide," I blurted out. "I keep going back and forth. I know I'm not ready to do that." I jerked my head in the direction of the tent. "I need time, Keeloa. I promise I won't tell anyone about you or your plans if you take me back home. But I can't be here anymore."

"I understand. You'll get your time."

Ka went back into the tent to get ka bag and to tell the others that ka was taking me home. Then ka led me silently away from the Rememberers' cave and back to my house in Visitors' Village.

16

Mid Fall Earth

"Honey, I just don't understand. What can you *do* with an anthropology degree?"

She had been yelling through the phone for 10 minutes. Some of it was *at* me, but most of it was *to* me because she was convinced yelling made the connection stronger. I had put the phone down three minutes into the rant but I picked it back up to answer her question.

"Well, mom, I'm not sure that I want to do anything with an anthropology degree. But there are lots of options. I could do research, become a professor, work in a museum."

"A professor?!" She was a professor herself, and had spent the last 15 years trying to convince me not to become one, too. "You'll never be happy as a professor."

I rolled my eyes, even though I knew it wouldn't do any good. We had been having the same conversation for a week, ever since I declared my major. "I have to go mom. I'm going to be late for class."

I hung up the phone and threw it across the room. Class didn't start for another 20 minutes, but it was the only guaranteed way to get her off the phone. Twenty minutes wasn't enough time to do anything – I couldn't nap or cry. So decided to take the scenic route to the main campus yard.

It was mid-Fall in New England. The trees were just starting to let go of their leaves, but people weren't quite willing to let go of their summer clothes yet. I watched as a group of frat bros tossed a football around to show off for the girls watching out of their dorm windows. I watched tourists wander cluelessly, occasionally stopping to ask a student for directions, only to be turned away disappointed that the student didn't know the area any better than they did. I looked at my phone and saw that, even though I had left

17 minutes before I needed to, I was still going to be late for class.

It was my sophomore anthropology tutorial. Every week, the professor began class by asking the students a question. We would spend the next hour discussing how dead white men would address the question, and the last 30 minutes sharing our own answers.

I sat down in my usual seat and waited for the professor to ask that day's question.

"Why do we want to learn about the suffering of others?"

My conversations with my mother had used up the time that I had set aside to do the reading for that week, so I stayed pretty silent during the discussion. But everyone had to give their own answer before class was over.

One girl said that she, as a supporter of human rights, felt it was her duty to know when anyone was in pain. I heard several people around the room snicker and I fought to hold back my own.

Someone else said that we learn about others' suffering so that we can feel better about our own.

We worked our way around the table, and somewhere after the fifth response, I stopped paying attention and started watching a different group of frat bros throw a football back and forth in the yard through the window.

"Dakota?"

I jumped and looked around the room, my eyes eventually landing on the professor who was looking right at me. It was my turn to answer.

"Because if we don't understand the extent and cause of another person's suffering, we can't know whether or not it's our responsibility to help them." The professor nodded, and class was dismissed.

17

Life on the Farm Iyeena

You know how amputees sometimes feel like their missing limb is still there? Or how you wake up after you moved out of your parents' house for the first time and expect to find them sitting in the dining room when you walk downstairs?

This wasn't one of those times.

I didn't feel the urge to run over to Teer's house and help ka cook. I didn't expect ka to wake me up and yell at me to get ready faster so we could go to the research compound. I knew I would never see Teer again.

It might sound like I was upset, or maybe even numb. But it wasn't that. I was in a neutral state of acceptance.

I showered while my food cooked. I put on my clothes. I ate my food.

I got tired of thinking in the first person singular.

Once all the necessities were taken care of, I walked out the door, happy to get out of the house and *do* something.

Okay, maybe I was a little bit upset.

There was still a collection of guards gathered in the middle of Visitors' Village. I knew the drill by now, so I cut through the space between two of the houses and walked to the tunnel in the back. There was a guard lounging on the three-wheeled golf cart, spaced out as if ka had been sitting there all day, waiting for someone to require ka services.

Ka sat all straight when as I approached and offered to help me into the cart. I waved ka hand away and climbed in myself.

Juleey was waiting at the end of the tunnel that connected Visitors' Village to the research compound.

"Hello, Dakota." Ka was smiling ka normal cheerful smile. I tried to smile back, and the longer I did that, the more I felt like the smile was real. "Are

you hungry? I was just about to get something to eat."

Ka took me to the hall where the guards ate. I tried to make conversation, but my heart wasn't in it, and we ended up eating in silence. I noticed that none of the other guards came to sit with us.

When we were done, we left the dining hall and Juleeay turned to me. "There are some Thinkers in a few different sectors who are available to talk to you."

The idea of talking to the Thinkers, of doing what I had agreed to come to Iyeena to do brought a little bit of feeling back – good feeling. "Are any of the astronomers free?" I knew they knew something about tidal locking! I just had to talk to more people, ask a few more questions.

"No, Dakota, I'm sorry. But you can talk to the head Thinkers in the geology and agricultural sectors."

Some of the good feeling went away, but I was sure the heads of those sectors would have interesting things to teach me, too. "How about the geology sector?"

Juleeay smiled and led the way.

Ka dropped me off at the the door of the geology sector – made of metal but decorated in strips of varying colors to represent different layers of rock and dirt. Before ka left, Juleeay handed me a small device with a little red button. "When you're ready to leave, push this and I'll come get you." I moved as if to put the paging device in my pocket before I remembered that my pants didn't have any. Ka saw my struggle, took the device back, and tapped it against the back of my wrist. bands extended from both sides and wrapped around to form a bracelet. I smiled my thanks as Juleeay walked away.

Most of the geologist Thinkers I met weren't very friendly or entertaining, but they had information I wanted. There was more to my choosing the geology sector than wanting to know about how Iyeena formed. Tinch's story about the history of Iyeena had left me with questions, and I figured the geologists would be able to answer them.

The geologist who answered the door was a rather dull looking Mowleean with empty eyes and a perpetually neutral expression who told me in a monotone voice that ka name was Verol. Verol led me through the geology lab, speaking only as much as ka had to in order to give basic answers to my questions about equipment and specimens. The tour was pretty short, as much because Verol clearly didn't know how to interact with other Mowleean as because I was getting visibly irritated. I was on my way out of the lab,

too distracted by my frustration at the fact that I barely knew more than I had when I entered the lab to remember to page Juleeay or watch where I was walking. I bumped into someone.

I looked up to apologize, expecting to meet another pair of empty eyes, but instead I found concerned ones.

"Are you okay?" The person in front of me was pale by Mowleean standards and I guessed ka must be a geologist – despite the fact that ka seemed capable of expressing emotions – because only someone who spent ka entire life underground could be so fair.

I nodded. "Yeah, I just needed to get away from them."

"Oh, I completely understand. Why do you think I work all the way over here?" Ka smiled again. "My name's Ethonee." Ethonee reached out to clasp the sides of my head.

"Dakota." I reached out, too, and used the moment as an opportunity to actually look at ka.

Ethonee was the first person, human or Mowleean, I had ever met with noteworthy posture. Most people have to try to stand to their full height, but not Ethonee. And when ka looked at me, I had a feeling that ka was looking at *all* of me – not in a creepy way, but in a way that let me know I had ka undivided attention. Looking at ka, one word came to mind: classy.

"What brings you to the geology sector, Dakota?" Ka voice was musical, but not overpoweringly so like Keeloa's.

I hesitated, trying to think of the best way to word the question so that I could get the answer I wanted without ka suspecting why I was asking. "How old are these tunnels?"

"Come with me."

I followed Ethonee to ka desk, where ka pulled out what looked like a giant blueprint. "The answer to your question is kind of complicated. Some of the tunnels formed naturally hundreds of thousands of burn-throughs ago." Ka pointed to tunnels marked *lava tubes* on the blueprint. "Early Mowleean started carving out the larger caverns about a thousand burn-throughs ago." Ka pointed to an area labeled *Research Compound* and then moved ka finger to rest over the residential cavern where Visitors' Village was. "They dug deeper and deeper into the ground as the moved away from the research compound. Once you get down to the level with the Players' cave, you're as deep as you can get without disturbing the water table." Ka worked ka finger down the staircase that ran down the middle of the residential cavern. "We've been systematically mapping the tunnels, trying to figure out where their cave is."

I tried not to think about the fact that I knew something the Thinkers had been trying so hard to figure out. Instead, I focused on what I had gone to the geology sector to learn – dates. If what ka was saying was true, and I had no reason to think it wasn't, then the Mowleean first moved underground more than 20 Mowleean lifetimes ago. It didn't answer all of my questions – I still had no way of knowing how long they had taken to put their plan together or how long before the Amrees' arrival the Mowleean had emerged from Lake Wiyoo. And I didn't actually know how long the average Mowleean lifespan was since I apparently didn't know how long it took Iyeena to orbit its sun. But I was happy to have answered any of my questions at all.

Ethonee told me that ka had to get back to work. I thanked ka, hit the button on the paging device Juleeay had given me, and moved to wait by the door.

When Juleeay arrived, I told ka I was feeling tired and asked if ka would take me back to the research compound entrance.

Fogella was standing in the kitchen when I got back to my house in Visitors' Village – it still didn't feel like home.

"Dakota! I haven't seen you in over a cycle. How are you? How's Teer?"

"Teer's sick." It was the excuse Lorana had told me to tell anyone who asked about Teer. The Rememberers didn't want the Thinkers to find out ka was gone. I shuffled past Fogella and into my room.

My bed was soft and warm – perfect for sleeping – but I couldn't get comfortable. As I laid there, I listened to Fogella move around in the kitchen and tried not to think of anything but the grooves on the ceiling.

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I followed the same routine when I woke up: shower, get dressed, go to the research compound. Juleeay was waiting for me again at the entrance and asked which sector I wanted to visit.

"Can we get food first?" I hadn't thought to make any food when I got back to my house or before I left.

Juleeay smiled. "I have a better idea."

The walk to the agriculture sector didn't seem as long as other trips I had taken in the research compound. When we reached the door – made of metal but colored a chalky red and covered in carvings that looked like plants growing out of rows of dirt – Juleeay pressed a button off to the side and turned to me.

"You take as long as you want," ka said. "Just page me when you're done." Ka tapped ka wrist and I looked down to see that I was still wearing the paging device ka had given me as a bracelet.

The lead Thinker of the agriculture sector was named Saylor. Ka hair strip was moss green with patches of brown and it fell straight down the back of ka head to ka neck. Saylor spoke loudly, both because ka had to yell to be heard over the machines in the room and because ka was a loud and confident person. Just being around ka instantly improved my mood.

Ka was listing the purposes of the machines as we passed them. "This one purifies and irrigates water to the vegetable fields." It turned out that each section of fields had its own purification and irrigation system. That made sense. If one machine stopped working, only one section would suffer. "This machine distributes fertilizer; that one can be taken out to turn the fields; that one over there can either collect crops or sow them, depending on what setting you use." It didn't seem that different from agriculture on Earth. It was just more automated, and I assumed the plants were different.

Saylor led me on a tour through the actual fields, showing me as we went how to tell when a plant was ripe, and encouraging me to taste something when I correctly identified it as ready for the picking. As a young girl back on Earth, I spent many of my summers on my grandparents' farm in California. Well, I spent most of my time in the farmhouse doing anything I could to avoid actually going outside, but I still learned the value of farm fresh produce. The food we picked didn't taste like anything my grandparents used to grow, but it was just as fresh.

"What about meat?" I asked as we were making our way through a field filled with something that looked like mini pumpkins, squished in my hands like tomatoes, and tasted like broccoli.

"I'm glad you asked. Follow me." Saylor led me out of the fields, up some stairs, and across a bridge to take me to a different lab room than the one we had entered. I was struck by how huge the agriculture sector was. Then I chided myself for being so surprised. This place was responsible for producing food for the entire Mowlean population. Of course it was big.

"Here you go." Saylor swept ka arms out, taking in the whole lab.

I looked at the room, looked back to Saylor, and then looked back again. "I don't understand. Where's the..."

I was trying to say "livestock," but the word caught in my throat, letting me know that it was another concept that didn't exist on Iyeena. Frankly, I was surprised this had only happened a few times.

"Where are the animals?"

Saylor smiled. "We stopped using animals a long time ago. Lake Wiyoo used to provide enough fish for all of our people, but evaporation and our growing population eventually made it so that the Lake wasn't a viable food source. There were a few other animals on the plane, but they were so hard to hunt and kill that it almost wasn't worth it. So now we grow it here!"

There was a struggle going on inside me. It was really cool that they had found a sustainable source of meat free from moral quandaries – or so I assumed. But deep down – okay, not that deep – I couldn't help but cringe at the idea of eating meat made in a lab, even though I knew I must have been eating it ever since I arrived on Iyeena.

"Do you want to try some?"

I tried to keep the disgust from showing on my face, but it didn't matter. Saylor was already walking over to a large freezer and pulling out two small cubes of meat. "This is one of our new ones. During a routine sweep, a team of our Thinkers discovered a fish in Lake Wiyoo that we had never seen before. We don't want to disturb the ecosystem in the Lake too much, but they got so excited and had to bring one back. And now we have this!"

Ka popped one of the cubes into ka mouth and started chewing, holding out ka hand to offer the second cube to me. Ka looked like ka was enjoying it, so I took the cube and put the whole thing in my mouth before I could back out.

It didn't taste like anything I had ever eaten back on Earth, but it didn't taste bad. Still, I was ready to leave. I asked Saylor to take me back to the door where I had entered so I could meet Juleeay. I paged ka as we walked across the bridge, down the stairs, through the fields, and up another flight of stairs to get back to the first lab. I said goodbye to Saylor and waited for Juleeay to pick me up.

I was tired again so I asked Juleeay to lead me back to the tunnel that connected the research compound and Visitors' Village.

Fogella was waiting for me when I walked into the house, holding a bowl filled with something steaming.

"You should take this over to Teer. I asked one of the Thinkers what they do when they get sick. Ka gave me this recipe."

I didn't know what to say. It was a ridiculously kind gesture, making get-well food for someone ka didn't even really know. I couldn't tell ka the truth, so I thanked ka, took the bowl, and walked over to Teer's house.

It felt empty. Teer hadn't been a very neat person, so ka mess was everywhere. I set the bowl from Fogella on the kitchen counter and went into Teer's bedroom. I hadn't even realized that Teer had a distinguishing scent, but the room smelled like ka. I laid down in ka bed and fell asleep much more quickly than I had been able to fall asleep in my own.

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Back in the research compound, Juleeay told me that some of the astronomers were available to talk to me and asked if I wanted to go to the astronomy sector.

"Actually," I said, "can you take me to the biology sector?"

I was happy to see Aleese again, and it seemed like ka was happy to see me, too. When ka opened the door and saw me standing there, ka put ka arms around me in an awkward but well-intentioned replica of the hug I had given ka the last time I was in the biology sector.

"What brings you here?"

Normally I would have been too shy to ask, but this was too important and it would have been too embarrassing to leave after insisting asking Juleey to take me there. "I was wondering if I could see the Waiting Room again."

"Of course!" Aleese turned on ka heel and took a few steps before I worked up the courage to say the next thing.

"There's more." Ka turned back around. "Can I talk to some of them? To the people waiting to be hosts?"

Aleese looked thoughtful and I could tell ka was trying to decide between telling me no and asking me why. Obviously I couldn't tell ka the real reason I wanted to talk to them, but it was clear I wouldn't be able to unless I told ka something.

"I'm trying to better understand the download process, and the Thinkers on my home planet thought that only certain personality types could be used as hosts. I want to give them personality tests to see if the Thinkers back home were right."

Aleese nodded and turned around again to lead me to the waiting room.

Huh, I thought to myself. I'm better at lying than I expected.

Aleese sat me down at one of the long tables and promised to send someone over. "Actually," I said, grabbing ka arm before ka could walk away, "could I just observe them first? That way I can pick my own test subjects. And if it's possible, could you tell the guards not to disturb me? It's a delicate process and it's best if I'm not interrupted." Aleese nodded again and left to talk to the guards standing in the back of the room.

I looked around and counted 23 people, the same 23 I had seen there before. Nine of them were sleeping in the cots on the other side of the room. Six were using the exercise equipment, each accompanied by a Thinker who was taking notes on some sort of electronic tablet. The other eight were eating quietly at separate tables.

I honestly couldn't see any of them displaying any distinguishing characteristics, so I picked one of the eating ones at random and sat across from ka.

Ka was wearing a grey outfit that looked a lot like mine. Ka cobalt blue hair strip was cut very short, just like all of the other future hosts. I tried to make eye contact, but ka hadn't even looked up when I sat down.

"Hi. My name's Dakota. What's yours?"

Eyes down, ka answered. "Dreet."

I was relieved. I had half expected that ka wouldn't answer any of my questions. "Dreet, can you look at me?"

Dreet put down the piece of food ka had been about to bite into and looked up. Ka eyes were empty, as if ka were looking through me instead of at me. It made me uncomfortable.

I hadn't really had time to form much of a plan, so I didn't know what to ask next. I didn't know what I thought talking to them would tell me, but I knew I had to do it.

"Tell me about yourself, Dreet."

Ka stared blankly at me, unblinking. I doubted ka was trying to imply that ka enjoyed staring contests, so I prompted, "Dreet?"

"I don't understand the request." Ka broke eye contact and returned to eating.

"What do you enjoy doing?" I wished Dreet would look at me. Ka didn't.

"I don't understand the request."

I ran my hands through my own hair strip, frustrated. I felt like I was talking to one of those dolls with pre-recorded responses that were so popular when I was a young girl. Actually, a conversation with one of those might have been more productive because the responses were usually designed make you feel good about yourself. Few things made nine-year-old me feel better than hearing a blonde-haired, blue-eyed baby doll tell me it loved me.

But I had to keep trying. "How do you spend your time?"

"I sleep. The Thinkers lead me through my physical exercises. I eat. The Thinkers lead me through my mental exercises." Ka continued eating. The food really did look fresh, but it didn't smell like anything. There were no spices or sauces. Ka was eating raw vegetables and plants and cooked but unflavored meat.

"What are your mental exercises?" I could see people doing everything else on Dreet's list. Ka was quiet for longer than was usually considered acceptable. I broke the silence to ask ka to look at me.

Ka looked up and I got the impression that ka wasn't really seeing me again. I decided that I wouldn't ask ka to look up at me anymore because feeling like a ghost was worse than having to watch ka stare at ka food.

"We do maths. Solve puzzles."

"Do you know why you do these mental exercises?" It was a long shot, but I was curious.

"Only the strongest brains make the best hosts." It sounded more like a reflex than an actual response, like a schoolchild mindlessly reciting the national anthem because it's what they had always done. Part of me wondered

if ka even knew what ka was saying. I certainly hadn't when I was in school.

But beyond that, I wondered at the meaning of what ka had said. I had gone through a download before. Granted, Keeloa implied that it wasn't as intense as the full-consciousness downloads that the hosts had to go through, but it was a download nonetheless. And Lorana said it was best not to fight the process. That didn't seem like an act of strength to me.

Then I realized that the actual words Dreet had used were important. The strongest *brains* make the best hosts. The Thinkers weren't strengthening minds. They were strengthening the physical brains, building connections and expanding neural networks.

To be a good host, you needed a strong brain and a weak mind.

I thanked Dreet for ka time, but I don't know if it really made any difference. I conducted similar interviews with some of the other people who had been eating when I walked in and with one person who had been sleeping. They all gave me the same empty, almost soulless impression.

Keeloa was right – these people weren't being kept prisoner. They didn't need to be. None of them would ever try to leave because none of them knew anything else existed.

I paged Juleeay as a guard led me out of the Waiting Room – no, Keeloa had been right about that, too, and it was more like a farm. I said bye to Aleese on my way out and ran out into the hall, needing to get away from what I had just seen as quickly as possible.

When Juleeay came to pick me up, ka asked if I was tired.

"No, I need to see Lorana."

Juleeay frowned. "Lorana's not in the research compound right now."

I slumped to the ground. What was I supposed to do? I couldn't do nothing after talking to the people in the farm.

A moment passed, and Juleeay kneeled so that ka eyes were level with mine. "I can take you."

I met ka eyes. "Take me where?"

"The Rememberers' cave."

18

The Lustbader Complex Earth

Senior year of college is not a good time to start a relationship. There are only a few ways it can end – and trust me, it will end. Best case scenario, it crashes and burns in fits of hysterical tears around graduation. Worst case scenario, you make and follow through on plans for post-grad life, and then it dies a slow death as you both grow to resent each other for missed opportunities, like air being let out of a balloon because the knot wasn't tied tight enough.

At least, that's what I thought until I met Alex.

Alex and I met the spring of our senior year, after I had already applied to grad school, but before she had started to apply for jobs. I was eating alone in my college dining hall, my computer open so I could at least pretend that I was being productive, and she sat down diagonally from me in the only empty seat in the whole room. I don't remember who said hi first, but in the coming weeks, we ate together almost every day. By the time grad school acceptances came out, we had already started making plans for the next year. By the time I made my decision, she had been offered a job as a secretary at an architecture firm in New York. We started looking for apartments together.

Alex's job wasn't the kind that sends a lot of work home at night, so she had nothing to do while I stressed over homework or teaching responsibilities or research. Instead of letting that make her bitter, she spent the time exploring the city. She found places where she could be happy by herself and places where we could be happy together. Some of our cutest date nights were spent doing things and going places she had discovered on her solo adventures.

One day after work, she stopped in a coffee shop on her way to a museum

one of the people in her office had told her about. Alex was never a very graceful person. It was one of the things I loved most about her – that she could so easily laugh off trips and blunders that would leave me blushing furiously from embarrassment. That day in the coffee shop, after getting her tea, she turned around and promptly knocked a drink out of the hand of the man who had ordered before her. She bought him a replacement and they ended up going to the museum together. His name was Jonathan.

Alex came home that evening after I had finished grading problem sets for the class I was a teacher's assistant for. She told me all about Jonathan as she made dinner. I didn't meet Jonathan until weeks later, but she described him as "one of those well-meaning white boys who was always involved in one social movement or another." He was vegan and spent most of his free time helping to organize events for the local PETA chapter. He didn't sound like someone I would particularly enjoy spending time with, but I was happy that she had met someone. I was starting to worry that the difference in our schedules would turn us into one of those deflating balloon couples I had feared becoming so much in college.

She started seeing Jonathan more and more often and eventually he persuaded her to go to some of his animal rights meetings. By the second semester of my first year in grad school, Alex had converted to vegetarianism. And I do mean converted as if it were a religion, because that's the way Jonathan talked - no, preached – about it.

Seeing that it was so important to her, I agreed to attend one of the meetings.

I was going to be late because I was coming from class, so Alex said she'd meet me outside the community center and lead me to the room. Walking up to the building, I saw her before she saw me. It was late February in New York City, so I was wearing three heavy layers and two scarves. But Alex never really felt the cold. She stood on the steps of the center, looking comfortable in a faux-leather jacket. As I watched her, she smiled the kind of smile that someone only wears when their life is full and happy. I marveled for the thousandth time how happy I was that she had sat across from me that day over a year ago.

Her smile widened when she saw me and I ran to meet her at the top of the steps. I kissed her on the cheek and she took my hand, leading me into the building.

We sat in the back row and listened to some guy at the front of the room talk about factory farming. I saw that Alex was completely focused, so I paid attention too, and it wasn't long before the guy's words started to really affect me.

He showed pictures of animals held in captivity, kept in unbelievably

close and dirty quarters. He showed pictures of slaughter houses. He showed pictures of assembly line-style packaging plants.

My first reaction was nausea. My second was anger. I gripped Alex's hand, hard. When we went home that night, I sorted through all the food in our fridge and threw away all the meat.

I started getting more involved – going to meetings whenever I could and even attending some protests. It definitely wasn't my primary focus in life. I was still in grad school and I didn't want to impinge on Alex's space. But she didn't seem to mind. She always had a smile on her face whenever she asked if I would be able to come to a meeting. She even helped me grade a few times so I could finish in time to go to a protest. I was happier then than I had ever been in my life.

One day that June, Alex told me Jonathan had invited her to participate in some sort of mission with him and some of his more hardcore activist friends to liberate some animals. She didn't know any details, but Jonathan had implied that it might be less than legal. I had never been comfortable with breaking rules or disregarding protocol. The idea of doing something illegal made me uncomfortable, but the idea of letting Alex do something illegal without me there to protect her made me feel even worse, so I went along.

We crammed into a van, the kind they used to show in after school specials about avoiding creepy strangers. Some guy named Kale drove us to a laboratory on the outskirts of the city. Alex and I were sitting in the very back, listening to music.

Kale parked the van and Jonathan opened the door in the back to let us out. I looked up at the building looming over us. The sign in front read "Lustbader Complex for Animal Testing."

I stopped in my tracks, letting go of Alex's hand as she kept walking toward the door.

"What's wrong?" She turned back to look at me.

"You didn't say it was an animal testing facility." Until that night, I had only ever gone to demonstrations that had to do with animal cruelty in the food, fashion, and entertainment industries. It just never occurred to me that Alex was also against animal testing for medical research.

"Dakota, I literally said we were going to liberate animals. What did you think we would be doing?"

My head was so full of possible responses that I was rendered speechless. I could have reminded her that the methods used to help send her mother's breast cancer into remission existed because of animal testing. I could have reminded her that the inhaler she used every time she exercised or got too excited existed because of animal testing. I could have reminded her that the

makeup she put on every morning was tested on animals.

But I didn't remind her of any of those things. I knew Alex well enough to know that it wouldn't change her mind.

"I don't know, but I didn't think we would be doing this! I can't go in there, Alex."

The guys had noticed that we had stopped walking and were coming back to check on us. "What's the holdup, girls?" Kale was one of those guys who thought that having a goatee and a greasy man bun, shopping at local farmers markets, and going to slam poetry readings automatically meant he was one of the good guys, no matter how misogynistic his behavior was. I didn't like Kale. I didn't like kale either, but I bet he loved it.

"The *holdup*, Kale, is that what you're about to do can have real negative impacts on important scientific research."

Alex grabbed onto my hand. "Yeah, but Dakota, baby, what those monsters are doing is having real negative impacts on the lives of important animals. If you would just come inside and see them..."

But I didn't want to go inside and see them. I wanted to go home. "I'll see you at home, Al." I pulled my hand out of hers and walked back toward the main road, pulling my phone out of my pocket to call a cab. And that was the last time I ever did anything with the animal rights group.

I don't want to say that that was the thing that ended our relationship, but it was definitely the thing that loosened the knot. We talked less and yelled more. I got annoyed when she left dirty dishes in the sink. She got annoyed when I forgot to clean my hair out of the shower drain. I started working from my office at school and she started spending more time at Jonathan's apartment. A month later, I was sleeping on the couch every night. By the time school started up again, she had moved in with Jonathan and I had a found new roommate online.

I met Justin three months later, and when he asked me out on our first date, I made sure he wasn't a vegetarian before I said yes.

19

Falling Rocks Iyeena

Juleeay told me to wait until after we were out of the research compound to ask questions.

Ka took me on a route that I didn't recognize, and when I asked about it, ka said there were secret passageways in every sector. Then ka shushed me and said that if I asked another question before ka said it was okay, ka would sedate and carry me just like Lorana had done. That shut me up.

Once we were out of the compound, I asked the obvious question. "Why?"
"Dakota, have I ever told you about my family?"

I shook my head.

"My parent was a Getter. I don't really have memories of spending time with ka when I was young because ka spent so much time working. ka worked so much that when ka died in a routine digging mission, I barely noticed ka absence. You saw the Rift?" I nodded. "I practically grew up in the Rift. People there fed me and looked out for me when my parent was gone. And my story isn't special. That's what life is like as a Getter. You work until you die, and because that's so common, the community gets together to raise any kids who get left behind."

I started to fidget as we walked, made uncomfortable by the personal tone our previously friendly and professional relationship had taken.

"I was lucky, though. Do you know how people become guards in the research compound?" I shook my head again. "When a Thinker has a child who isn't 'smart' enough to become a Thinker, that child grows up to be a guard. These roles get passed down through families. There are no opportunities to move up in the world on Iyeena. You will have what your parent had, and that's all you'll be able to pass on to your own children, if you're brave enough to produce any."

I had to clear my throat before I could ask my question. "How did you become a guard, then?"

"My parent died before I saw my third burn-through. Eventually, I stopped being cute enough for the people in the Rift to take pity on me, but I wasn't strong enough to start working as a Getter yet. So I ran away." Ka paused to listen to something and continued walking after a few tense breaths. "I left through the Getters' door to the surface, but I got lost and eventually found the Thinkers' door, the one I showed you before. A Thinker found me wandering the research compound and was going to have me sent back to the Getters, but something stopped ka. Maybe I said something smart enough to impress ka, or maybe ka just had a sense of basic Mowleean decency. Whatever it was, ka took pity on me and raised me as ka own. Rumors spread about me, so I couldn't become a Thinker, but I could become a guard, and I did."

There was a long stretch of silence. I realized that Juleeay was waiting for me to say something. "So you're saying you owe your life to the Thinkers?"

Juleeay shook ka head. "No, I'm saying I owe my life to that single Thinker. But my life before that, and the lives of thousands of people on Iyena can only be described as miserable because that's how the Thinkers made it. I owe them nothing but hatred and revenge."

Ka eyes went hard and cold, but only for a moment. When I looked again, Juleeay was wearing ka usual smile. "So that's why I'm helping the Rememberers. To bring an end to the system of inequality the Thinkers created."

We found Lorana and Keeloa cooking over a fire. When Keeloa saw us approaching, ka stood up to greet us. Lorana stayed sitting. Juleeay reached Keeloa first, and when they met, they touched foreheads and held the stance for the space of a breath or two. Then it was my turn. I moved awkwardly to touch my forehead to Keeloa's, aware the entire time that I had never been so close to another person's face without kissing them. Keeloa ended the embrace before I had really had a chance to get comfortable with it and went back to tending the fire, gesturing for us to sit down.

"So, Keeloa, I came because..."

Ka held up a hand to stop me from finishing the sentence. "You want to talk about the Thinkers." It wasn't a question, but I nodded anyway. "It can wait until after we've eaten." I was going to protest until I looked up to see Juleeay shaking ka head slightly. I shut my mouth and took the bowl that Keeloa handed me. Smelling the food – some kind of heavy stew – I couldn't

deny that my stomach had been tightening from hunger since before I went to the farm.

Keeloa sat across from me in the circle around the fire. Juleeay was sitting far to my left, Lorana far to my right. Both of them were staring intently into their bowls.

In the moments that followed, everyone was too busy actively eating and enjoying their stew to try to force conversation. It had been so long since I had experienced a comfortable silence that I had forgotten how refreshing it could be. Keeloa had been right – again – in insisting that we wait until after eating to talk about anything important.

We all finished our stew around the same time. Keeloa collected our bowls and took them into ka tent. Once ka left, the atmosphere turned sour. Juleeay and Lorana were looking anywhere but at each other.

I wondered if asking questions would break some of the tension. "Juleeay." Ka turned to look at me. "How did you get involved with the Rememberers? You told me why, earlier, but not how."

Before ka answered, Juleeay looked at Lorana for a long time. Lorana refused to meet ka eyes. Ka turned back to me.

"Lorana was one of my first friends in the research compound. I thought it was a coincidence for a long time, until ka told me ka life story. Ka knew mine before we ever met and made it ka business to get to know me, the guard who grew up among the Getters. I guess ka figured we'd get along, or maybe ka just got tired of being around people who were born into that kind of life, you know?" Lorana glanced up, but looked away before Juleeay could notice. "Whatever it was, we grew close pretty quickly. It wasn't long before ka introduced me to ka parent. Together, they taught me about the Rememberers, gave me productive ways to channel my frustration. Lorana used to be really good at that." Juleeay smiled a wistful smile. Lorana made a sound in ka throat like ka was choking on something. "At calming me down. Now our frustrations just feed off of each other."

"What changed?" I looked back and forth between the two of them.

Lorana answered before Juleeay could. "My parent died. Ka was in the group of Rememberers who tried to free the people from the farm. And I never got to say goodbye because doing so would have meant revealing my true identity. Everything my parent had sacrificed for would have been ruined." By the end of the story, Lorana's voice was dripping with bitterness, but ka eyes were sad.

I didn't know what to say. Should I express sympathy? Change the subject? I was afraid the former would seem empty and the latter disrespectful. Instead, I said nothing.

Before long, Keeloa emerged from ka tent. Juleeay called out to ka before

ka reached the fire circle. "Dakota talked to the people at the farm."

Ka words caught the attention of a few people in the surrounding area and some of them came over to see what we were talking about. Pakoy, much to my dismay, was one of them.

Soon, the circle around the fire was full. Everyone was staring at me, waiting for me to say something. I desperately hoped most of them would leave.

"What did you learn at the farm, Dakota?" Keeloa asked from across the circle. Beside ka, Pakoy was flicking ka tongue in and out of ka mouth in the Mowleean sign of disgust. I wondered briefly what it would take to make ka not hate me, but honestly, it wasn't anywhere near the top of my list of priorities.

I looked around the circle nervously. "I was kind of hoping I could just talk to you. I'm still working through what I saw and heard."

"Whatever you have to say to me concerning the farm or the Thinkers, you can say in front of everyone here. It's their struggle, too."

I hesitated to say anything and Juleeay left ka place in the circle to come sit by me. "How about you just start by telling them what you saw. Stick to the facts. It's easier," ka whispered.

I took a deep breath and recounted the tale of my visit to the farm. I doubted any of them had ever actually been inside the research compound, so I started by describing the room. A few people around the circle grimaced when I did that, and I couldn't blame them. Now that I knew the future hosts – the person to my right told me they were called Plants by some people in the cave – never left, I had to admit that it seemed like a pretty miserable existence. Then I repeated my conversation with Dreet, if it could be called that.

No one asked any questions when I finished talking. Everyone looked too lost in their own thoughts. I guess it's one thing to hear your whole life that other people lead a sad existence and another thing entirely to have that existence described to you in detail.

Keeloa was the first person to speak. "So what do you think of the farm now?"

I met ka eyes over the fire and tried to think of a poetically righteous response. But I'm not a particularly poetic person, and that kind of language is really only necessary when you're trying to rouse a crowd. The people in that circle had been roused their whole lives. "I think you were right. They're prisoners."

I looked around the circle. People were nodding their heads to what I had said. Even Pakoy seemed to approve of my assessment. Soon, people started holding their own side conversations. I didn't know if any of them

were about the farm, but I was happy that no one's attention was focused on me anymore. Well, not no one. Keeloa walked from ka side of the circle to stand behind me and asked if we could talk in private. I nodded and stood up to follow ka away from the fire circle.

We walked until we could no longer hear the conversations around the fire pit. Then I stopped, realizing that I couldn't hear anything at all. I looked around, surprised. Every time I had been in the Rememberer's cave, it had been full of music. Songs from different corners of the huge space echoed off the walls until the whole place was filled with the most pleasant cacophony.

"Where's the music?" I asked.

"Most people are asleep," ka said and continued walking.

The quiet was just starting to feel normal when ka asked, "Has your time on the farm helped you make your decision?"

I didn't know how to answer. There's a broad line between knowing that doing something is wrong and being willing to let go of the way you benefit from that wrongdoing. Had I crossed that line yet? I didn't think so, and that's what I told Keeloa.

I couldn't tell if ka was upset, or if ka even understood why I felt the way I did. Ka just nodded and said, "There's someone you need to meet." Ka stopped in front of a tent and held up the flap for me to go inside.

The tent was as colorful on the inside as it was on the outside. Piles of pillows were arranged in various spots on the floor and all of the other furniture – a desk, an open chest with clothes hanging haphazardly out of the top, and a stand full of art supplies – sat very close to the ground. A couple of candles on the desk threw shadows on the walls of the tent, but instead of looking threatening, they made the place look warm and homey.

Once inside, Keeloa pointed to a far corner of the tent and I realized that there was a person sitting there on the floor, painting something on an easel that was facing away from us. The person stuck ka head out from behind the easel and I gasped.

It was Teer.

Keeloa was standing behind me so that when ka whispered, I could hear everything perfectly. "Dakota, this is Rossem. I think you two should talk. I'll be outside."

Of course it wasn't Teer. Teer had been sent back home. Rossem was Teer's host.

I walked across the tent toward, making a list in my head of all the ways I could foresee our interaction going. Maybe ka would be like Dreet, empty and non-responsive. Or maybe ka would be angry that I had interrupted ka solitary painting time. Or maybe ka would just be really confused by my presence in ka tent.

"Hi, I'm Dakota." I kneeled next to ka and braced myself for what would come next.

"I know," ka said, smiling.

I rocked back so that I was sitting on my heels. That was not one of the scenarios I had been expecting.

Rossem laughed at my reaction. It was Teer's laugh.

I spoke around the lump that was forming in my throat. "How did you know that?"

Ka picked up the paintbrush ka had been using before I walked in and started painting again. "I remember you."

I didn't know what to say to that, so instead I just watched ka paint. Ka was painting some sort of landscape. There was a wide field full of crops with mountains in the background. After watching ka work for a while, I asked, "What are you painting?"

"A memory."

I didn't understand. If ka had grown up on the farm with all of the other Plants, how had ka ever been outside? Dreet hadn't said anything about taking field trips. I was starting to wonder if the people on the farm left it every once in a while after all, until I looked more closely at Rossem's painting.

A white circle at the top of the paper must have been the sun, and there were two crescents outlined on the far side of the page. All of the plants were a light purple color – violet. In fact, the whole painting had a slight purple tint to it. It all seemed so familiar to me, and then it suddenly hit me why.

When Teer and I were first getting to know each other, we spent a lot of time talking about our respective home planets. I remembered Teer telling me that Odahi had two moons and that its star was really bright and hot, hotter than Earth's sun. Ka never said anything about the color of the plants on Odahi because we both knew that our perceptions of color had changed when we got put in our new Mowleean bodies, but violet plants made sense. Iyeena would look red to my human eyes because its sun was cooler than Earth's. Maybe Odahi looked purple to Rossem's Mowleean eyes because its sun was hotter.

I looked around and saw that Rossem had painted other things as well. Many of them were scenes I didn't recognize. But I recognized the Rift. And I recognized the image of Keeloa and Pakoy wrestling at the Emergence Day festival. And I recognized myself.

Teer had been right. My hair strip, wavier than most others I had seen, was a mottled grey. As it fell from the top of my head to the nape of my neck, it really did give the impression of rocks falling down a wall. Or at least that's how Rossem had painted it.

I turned my attention back to Rossem. "You paint really well. Did you do much painting back on the... I mean, where you were, you know, before?"

Rossem laughed that all too familiar laugh again. "You mean on the farm?" Ka put the paintbrush down again. "No, The Thinkers would never let us do anything so fun, so... unproductive."

"So you started painting here?"

Ka nodded. "Keeloa thought it would help me sort through all the things that were going on inside my head. It has."

"What do you mean? What was going on in your head?"

Rossem thought for a long while before answering. "Have you ever been in that space between awake and asleep? That space where you can still hear some of what's going on around you, but it sounds like it's coming from another room or like you're underwater, and you can't respond?" I nodded. "That's what being a host is like. Sometimes, you're vaguely aware of what's happening around you, but you have no control over what you do or what you say. Other times, it's like you're asleep."

My feet started to go numb and I moved so that I was sitting cross-legged on the floor. "So, when you... woke up, what was it like?"

"The doctor who did it... What was ka name?"

"Lorana."

"Right, Lorana. Well, ka explained the science behind the procedure to me, but I didn't understand any of it. Basically, ka tried to extract everything that belonged to the last Visitor from my brain, but ka had to be careful. Some of Teer's memories were so deeply embedded that getting rid of them would have meant getting rid of my own." Hearing Rossem say Teer's name sent a shiver down my back and a wave of nausea through my stomach. "Because of that, when I woke up, I had memories of things that I had never seen or done. There were remnants of feelings that I had never felt." Ka swept ka arm across the tent and all of the paintings ka had made. "When I paint them, it forces me to think about each memory. It helps me decide if it's really mine or not. I wish some of them were mine." Ka eyes met my own and held them. I was the first to look away.

"Anyway," ka said lightly, as if the air hadn't been heavy with emotion just a moment before. "Keeloa and the other Rememberers have been helping me find things I enjoy doing since I woke up. Painting is fun. I can't dance at all." Ka laughed, a genuine and completely un-self-conscious laugh. I couldn't help but smile. "I never had the chance to do this type of exploring back on the farm."

I don't know how long Rossem and I talked to each other. Ka asked me questions about what I liked to do back on Earth. I told ka about the tiers outside of the cavern. Ka had some vague memories of what the Rift

looked like, but ka didn't know anything about Tinch. Those stories made ka laugh. We talked about the Rememberers' music, about food, about how much more extravagant the Rememberers' clothes were than the Thinkers'. By the time we were done talking, the candles were significantly shorter than they had been when I walked in.

I stood up to leave and ka stood up, too. There was a moment after I said bye but before I actually left where I didn't know what to do. I couldn't touch ka forehead with my three fingers because that was an Odahian gesture, but I couldn't think of any other gestures appropriate for the situation. Then, as I stood there with one hand on the tent flap that led to the cave outside, Rossem took two steps toward me, leaned down, and kissed me gently on the forehead. "Bye, Dakota."

Outside the tent, I looked around for Keeloa and found ka sitting on the ground a few paces away, arranging a pile of pebbles in some sort of pattern. "How'd it go" ka asked as I settled myself on the ground across from ka.

"Ka acts so much like Teer, but at the same time, not. Ka is ka own person." The Plants in the farm should get the chance to be their own people, too. "Look, I know you introduced me to ka because you want me to agree to be extracted from my host, but I..."

"No, Dakota. I introduced you to Rossem because I thought ka needed to meet you. Many of Teer's most strongly embedded memories involved you. I thought it might help Rossem to meet the person ka can't stop thinking about."

"Oh, okay." I looked down at the design ka was making. It was a triangle with a vertical line running down the middle. "I've seen that before."

Keeloa straightened out the lines. "It was the symbol for the diggers who built most of these tunnels and caves. They would stamp it on the entrance to every section they completed. And then it became the symbol for the radical faction of Rememberers who tried to break into the farm. But now people associate it with vigilantism and violence and death."

Then I remembered where I had seen it. It was the symbol I saw etched into the door to the Iyeenan surface from the research compound. "So why are you making it with pebbles on the ground?"

"I've been thinking a lot recently about those Rememberers. About whether or not it's fair to call wanting to give other people their freedom 'radical.'" I tried to meet ka eyes, tried to read ka face, but ka was looking everywhere but in my direction. "But they didn't just want to free the Plants, you know? They wanted to renegotiate the entire social hierarchy. That's what was so radical about them."

"Is that what you want to do? Renegotiate the social hierarchy?"

Ka eyes met mine. "No. It's what I'm going to do."

It was the kind of moment that would have given me goosebumps back on Earth, but Mowleens don't get goosebumps. Instead, I could feel my hair strip bristling. But it wasn't enough to just say provocative sentences. If Keeloa wanted me to agree to help the Rememberers, ka needed to put together a plan. Ka needed to understand the consequences of that plan. I wasn't sure ka had done either of those things.

"What about the Thinkers' research? They're making important and life-saving discoveries."

Ka stopped moving the rocks around and looked up at me, ka eyes crinkled, confused. "They can continue doing their research. We know how necessary their work is."

Then it was my turn to be confused. "But I thought you were anti-science. You don't even cook with ovens!"

Keeloa laughed. "I don't cook with ovens because I think food prepared over a fire tastes better. There are some people in this cave who couldn't start a fire if their lives depended on it."

"Oh."

Ka reached across the pebble structure to grab my hand. "Dakota, listen. Just because we're against this single application of science doesn't mean we're against science altogether. And just because we're interested in reshuffling the social structure doesn't mean we're going to subjugate the Thinkers the way they've subjugated us. That's not what being a Rememberer is about."

What Keeloa said make sense, but there was still one obstacle standing in the way of my supporting the Rememberers in their efforts. "Keeloa, I really want to say that I support freeing the Plants, but the Visitor program is such a crucial source of knowledge, both for the Thinkers here and the Visitors' home planets. You can't do what you want to do without ending that program and cutting off that source."

Keeloa was nodding along as if ka had expected me to make that point. "That's actually not true. I bet Landric didn't tell you this, but they have other options for hosts. Since the program first started, they've made advancements in robotics and artificial intelligence. It's just that they already had the farm and the Plants, and using those other methods of hosting Visitors would cost them more time and resources."

Landric hadn't told me any of that.

"Keeloa, I'm not ready to leave Iyeena. There are so many things to learn here. Things I can use to save my planet when I go back." A look of disappointment flashed across ka face before ka got it under control. "But, I

would like to support you however I can in your mission to free the Plants."

A small smile broke Keeloa's carefully guarded neutral expression. "We can't – and we wouldn't want to – force you to go through the extraction process. And I don't know how much you can help us otherwise, but I'm glad we have your support."

I held out my hand, offering it for a handshake. "So we have a deal?"

Ka looked at my hand, unsure what to do with it at first. Then ka extended ka own right hand and gripped mine. "We have a deal."

Keeloa stood up and pulled me up after ka by our clasped hands. "Now we just have to finalize our plans. Let's go find Juleeay and Lorana before they kill each other, or before they..." Ka glanced sideways at me. "Yeah, before they kill each other."

Before we walked back toward ka tent, Keeloa used ka foot to scatter the pebbles, erasing the symbol, but not the sentiments that it had once represented.

I sat in the sitting room of Teer's house in Visitors' Village, rocking back and forth on the couch as I tried not to think about the Rememberers and their mission. Many of the Rememberers hadn't been comfortable with the idea of me being involved in the mission that could potentially alleviate hundreds of cycles' worth of pain and oppression. And I couldn't blame them. Theirs was not my fight. I had no right to be a part of the solution.

Still, I had insisted on helping in any way I could. It was actually Pakoy who suggested I act as the Rememberers' liaison to the other Visitors. Ka didn't say it in such a nice way, of course. It was more like "Why don't you let that parasite deal with the others? I don't want to talk to them any more than I have to." But the gist was the same.

So I was stuck at home while the Rememberers engaged in a potentially life-threatening mission, waiting for them to give me the sign that they had been successful and it was time for me to lead the other Visitors to the cave. I paused my rocking to wonder briefly if that was what 1950's housewives felt like as they waited for their husbands to come home – you know, if their husbands happened to be international spies.

Keeloa sent me back to my house with a young Rememberer soon after my role was decided, so I never got to hear what their plan for rescuing the Plants was. After ka left, I walked over to Teer's house. Even though I was sure I wouldn't be able to fall asleep, I was knocked out cold before the drink I prepared had finished warming up in the oven. When I woke up, I had no idea how long I had slept, but Keeloa assured me that I would know when it was time to gather the Visitors, so there was nothing for me to do but wait.

Directly across the room from my position on the couch was the small flower garden. Looking at it, I couldn't help but think of the Plants, and by extension, the farm and the Rememberers' mission. I walked over to the garden and kneeled in front of it, reaching out a hand to touch the dirt. It was chalky, disintegrating into a fine powder in my hands. The flowers that grew there were the same violet as the plants from Rossem's painting. Calmly, meticulously, I ripped every single one of them out of the dirt, carried them into the kitchen, and dumped them into the oven. I turned it to its highest setting and walked, satisfied, back to my spot on the couch.

A while later – I was so lost in my thoughts that I couldn't tell if it was a long or a short while – I heard a commotion outside. I ran to the door and pulled it open to see that all of the Visitors had done the same. I turned toward the noise and saw a mass of screaming Mowleens charging up the main staircase, forming a wall and rushing at the guards in the center of Visitors' Village.

One of the guards yelled for backup and I saw other guards streaming through the spaces between the houses. It made me wonder if there had always been concealed guards back there, constantly watching us and reporting back to Landric. All of the guards ran toward the charging line of Mowleens, leaving all of us Visitors completely unattended.

I realized as I watched the guards run that this must be the sign Keeloa had told me to look out for. If I didn't gather the Visitors and lead them to the Rememberers' cave before the guards got everything under control, I would be failing at the only job I had been given, and all of the punishments that the rushing crowd of people would undoubtedly face would be for naught.

The Visitors were all looking back and forth between each other and the mess that was unfolding before them. Many of them looked afraid and all of them looked confused, the perfect combination for an easily manipulated crowd.

"This way! There's a secret tunnel over here!" I called out to the Visitors. "We can make it to safety!" Slowly at first, but then more quickly as my words started to sink in, they followed my voice. Then they were all following me as I led them through the secret tunnel down to the Rememberers' cave.

∞∞∞∞

Keeloa met us at the entrance to the cave. I turned around to see how the Visitors were reacting - not well. They had started to murmur and grumble amongst themselves a little while back in the tunnels.

Keeloa saw it too and called out to the crowd before murmurs had a chance to escalate. "I know you all must have questions. But I promise that, if you come with me, you'll get the answers you seek."

I could see the gears turning in the Visitors' minds. Some took longer than others, but they all eventually ended up at the same conclusion: what other choice did they have?

Keeloa led the way through the cave and I brought up the rear. As we made our way through the tents, I could see and feel Rememberers' eyes on us. For many people in the cave, we Visitors were the physical embodiment of the Thinkers' subjugation of them and their ancestors. And yet, I didn't sense much hostility. I didn't feel like I was in danger. I felt like I was joining them on the precipice of some giant and long-awaited change.

I had spent enough time in the Rememberers' cave to have a fuzzy understanding of where everything was, so I stopped thoughtlessly following and started actually paying attention to where we were going. I realized we were heading to what I had come to think of as the medical tent.

Inside the tent, the reclining chair was still set up in the middle of the floor next to a table full of machines and medical equipment. Lorana and Juleeay were standing on opposite sides of the chair, Lorana's face stony and emotionless, Juleeay's face open with a warm smile. It was hard to imagine the two of them together, but I guess I didn't know enough about Iyeena to make those kinds of judgements.

There were more chairs set up around the perimeter of the tent and Keeloa motioned for everyone who wanted to take seats to take them. And then ka started speaking, the lilting cadence of ka voice easing people into a receptive calm.

"We are the Rememberers. If you've heard of us at all, which is pretty unlikely, you've almost certainly heard us called Players." Ka paused to see if anyone recognized the name. No one did. "There is so much history wrapped up in what I'm going to ask of you, but if you let us, we can give you most of that history. The basic idea is that the bodies you're in right now, the hosts that the Thinkers have supplied... They are not willing hosts." Predictably, a mutter rippled through the group. "And once you know more about that – if you agree to learn more about it – I'm going to ask you if you want to give your host ka life back." Another mumble. Keeloa waited until it was quiet again to continue. "We will not force you to agree to this. It is entirely up to you, and we are happy to answer any questions you have. But as scientists, you should know the importance of having all the facts before you come to any conclusions. Right now, you are living without all of the facts. And I'm offering you the chance to change that."

I looked around the room as Keeloa finished speaking. Most people were giving Keeloa all of their attention – they seemed open to the idea. Some were avoiding eye contact – they had their doubts. No one was grimacing or yelling – signs that they were flat out opposed to what Keeloa was proposing.

"What do you mean, give us the facts?" I couldn't tell where the voice had come from.

"By that, I mean Lorana here – some of you might recognize ka from the medical sector of the research compound – will download memories of Rememberers past and present into your brains. It's quick, painless, and incredibly informative, isn't that right, Dakota?" I nodded, shy once everyone's attention was focused on me. "So, does anyone want to go first?"

There was a moment of silence where everyone looked at everyone else.

"I do," said the same voice. Keeloa breathed a sigh of relief and swept ka arm toward the chair.

"Thank you. What's your name?"

"Fogella."

I hadn't seen Fogella since ka handed me the soup to give to Teer. We locked eyes as ka walked to the chair and ka smiled at me, a comforting smile.

Fogella climbed into the chair and listened as Lorana explained that it was best not to fight the memories. Ka nodded and sat back as Lorana inserted the needle in ka arm and attached the sticky conductor pads to ka head. I saw ka body tense and then relax. And in less time than it had taken Keeloa to deliver ka speech, Fogella was opening ka eyes.

Keeloa handed Fogella a cup filled with the same liquid I drank after I was downloaded with the Rememberers' memories. "How do you feel?"

Fogella took a few sips from the cup and slowly sat up. "Dizzy. And a little...buzzed. I can feel my entire body tingling." Ka lifted up the cup as if saluting Keeloa. "But this is helping."

Juleeay helped Fogella to ka feet and led ka to one of the seats lining the side of the tent. Juleeay leaned down to touch ka forehead to Fogella's before walking back to stand behind the chair in the middle. I stared at Fogella, trying to will ka to meet my eyes, but ka was looking out into the distance at nothing in particular, obviously lost in thought.

The next person to volunteer was a Visitor I had never spoken to named Botroas. Lorana performed the same procedure, Keeloa offered the same drink in a different cup, and Juleeay led ka back to ka seat before leaning down to touch their foreheads together.

I watched as each Visitor underwent the same process, and then sat in the tense silence that settled once the last volunteer returned to ka seat.

Fogella was the first person to recover and say something. I nearly jumped from surprise when I heard ka voice. "You said we could give the hosts their lives back?" Keeloa nodded. "How?"

Keeloa explained – with help from Lorana – how their memories and personalities would be copied and then extracted from their hosts' minds.

No one seemed to have trouble understanding the technical side of things, but more than one person had a question about the consequences of the extraction.

"What happens to our consciousnesses after the extraction?" That came from one of the chemists who toured the Iyeenan surface with me – I couldn't be sure, but I thought it was the one whose house Teer and I had set on fire – named Eeyamon.

Lorana stepped forward, away from the medical equipment. "I will personally see to it that your brain drives are sent back to your home planets."

Eeyamon shook ka head. "No, after that. What will my home planet do with it? Put it into someone else? That's no better than being in this body."

Lorana opened an closed ka mouth, struggling to put together a response. Juleeay stepped up next to ka. "We don't have an answer for you. When the collectors took you from your planets, they didn't leave behind instructions for how to manage your return. The officials on your planets were responsible for coming up with a plan."

Lorana nodded. "And they will have had more than a sufficient amount of time to do so before you arrive."

Eeyamon sat back in ka seat and hunched ka shoulders, retreating inward with ka thoughts. I found myself wondering how Earth would deal with my own return should I choose to be extracted from my host.

"What happens if we don't accept your offer?" I didn't know the Visitor who asked that. I turned to Keeloa to see how ka would respond.

"You mean if you decide not to go through with the extraction?" The Visitor nodded, and Keeloa started shifting on ka feet, glancing back and forth between Juleeay and Lorana. "We can't force you to do it." I saw several of the Visitors' shoulders relax. "But I also can't guarantee that the rest of your time on Iyeena would be the same as these last several cycles. Things are about to change here, and those changes might make being a Visitor on Iyeena difficult."

I knew it wasn't the Rememberers' way, but I almost would have preferred to be threatened. *Be extracted or die!* That's the kind of decision I could make easily, but I wasn't that lucky.

Another Visitor asked what the the hosts' lives were like before they became hosts. Juleeay started to describe the farm, but I didn't want to be reminded of what the Thinkers had done, so I got up and sneaked out of the tent.

I wandered around the Rememberers' cave – or rather, I thought I was wandering – until I found myself standing outside Rossem's tent. I knocked and waited for a response. When none, came, I went inside.

It was almost too dark in the tent to see anything. I stood still and waited

for my eyes to adjust before I lit some of the candles sitting on a low table near the center of the tent.

It looked much like it had the last time I had been inside. Rossem's sleeping pallet lay in one corner, ka easel in another, and ka paintings were everywhere. I walked over to ka easel to see what ka was working on.

The painting was based on one of Teer's memories. It was our goodbye, the last moment we spent together before ka let Lorana extract ka consciousness from Rossem's body.

Except, instead of me kissing Teer's forehead as ka sat in the chair, ka was kissing mine, and I was getting ready to go through with the extraction.

I stared at the painting for a long time, thinking about Teer and what ka would have wanted, about what ka would have said I should do. I thought about the family I never got to build with Justin. If Teer were there, ka would have reminded me that my chance to build that family was gone even if I stayed on Iyeena. And ka probably would have added that any family I did have would be disappointed in me for being so selfish.

Except I wasn't being selfish! I wanted to stay on Iyeena so I could save Earth. *Is that really the reason?* Teer's voice asked in the back of my mind. My simulation results had only said that it was possible Earth could become tidally locked to the sun in a few thousand years. I wondered if anyone had confirmed or disproved the results while I was away. My collaborators had almost certainly gained access to my simulation code after I left for NASA.

So what was keeping me on Iyeena? I didn't have any close friendships. Not since Teer left. Was I just afraid of going back to a world that I didn't recognize? Or worse, was I afraid that I wouldn't even have the chance to try to recognize anything – that Earth had forgotten about me while I was gone and my digital consciousness would be returned to a planet that didn't have a plan for me? *But that had been the deal from the very beginning.*

Something moved beyond the easel and I stood up to see Keeloa come into the tent. "Are the Visitors still asking their questions?"

Ka nodded. "Most of them. Some have already decided what to do."

"What did they say?" There was hope in my voice. Maybe my choice would be easier if I knew what others had done.

But Keeloa didn't want my choice to be easy. "It doesn't matter what decision they made. What matters is whether or not you have made yours. Have you?"

I nodded, looking down at Rossem's painting and hoping I wouldn't regret what I was about to do.

"Lorana moved to another tent and is setting up the equipment to perform the first extraction. Will you come?" Ka offered ka hand.

I took it.

Appendices

Appendix A

Habitability Test of EPIC 206032309

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A.1 ABSTRACT

In the search for habitable exoplanets, astronomers' primary criterion is that the planet's equilibrium temperature is such that it could hold liquid water. Using photometric data from the K2 mission, we analyze the transit light curve of EPIC 206032309 (from here on, called EPIC), a single-planet system located ≈ 220 pc away. In this paper, we report the stellar, planetary, and orbital properties of this system. We assert that, with an equilibrium temperature of $978 \pm 49K$, EPIC does not reside in the habitable zone of its host star.

A.2 INTRODUCTION

One of the primary goals of exoplanetary research is to discover Earth-like habitable planets elsewhere in the galaxy. A major criterion for habitability is a planet's ability to hold liquid water. This criterion is met only when a planet orbits close enough to its host star that water wouldn't freeze, but far enough away that it wouldn't all evaporate.

Beyond simply having a semimajor axis that places it in the habitable zone of its host star, in order for a planet to maintain its liquid water, it

must stay in the habitable zone for the entire duration of its orbit. For this to happen, the planet's eccentricity – a measure of how round its orbit is – should be close to circular ($e = 0$).

The vast majority of exoplanets are found using the transit method, which uses photometric data to detect the shadows of planets passing in front of their host stars. Since its launch in 2009, *Kepler* has used the transit method to find more than 1000 confirmed exoplanets. In May of 2013, the second of four reactor wheels on the spacecraft failed and the spacecraft had to be repurposed.

More than a year after *Kepler's* second wheel failed, K2 began operation in June of 2014. The K2 mission is organized into "campaigns," or sequential periods of ≈ 75 days during which the spacecraft observes a single field of sky. Each field lies along the ecliptic plane so that the spacecraft can use a system of thrusters and the remaining two reaction wheels to balance itself against the radiation pressure from the sun. The reduced exposure time on each field results in a factor of 3 to 4 decrease in raw photometric precision from the original *Kepler* mission (Vanderburg and Johnson, 2014).

While the primary objective of the original *Kepler* mission was to find Earth-like planets in the habitable zones of sun-like stars, the physical limitations of the K2 mission extend its objectives. All K2 targets are proposed by members of the scientific community to explore a range of topics of interest to exoplanetary and stellar astronomers. The objective most relevant to this project is that to find potentially habitable planets around M-dwarfs in the solar neighborhood.

This paper is structured as follows. In § A.3, we will describe the data and the methods used to process it. In § A.4, we will describe the methods used to analyze the data. In § A.5, we will report the stellar, orbital, and planetary parameters constrained. In § A.6, we will discuss the implications of the parameters reported in § A.5 and what work we plan to do in the future.

A.3 DATA

We use photometric data taken during the third campaign of the K2 mission. The data were taken over a span of 69 days from 14 November 2014 to 23 January 2015.

K2 data is dominated by noise caused by the telescope's pointing jitter. Andrew Vanderburg removed this noise using the methods described in Vanderburg & Johnson (2014), which recover $\approx 50\%$ of the precision difference between *Kepler* and K2. The resulting light curve (see Figure A.6) was sent

to me for further analysis.

A.3.1 Detrending

K2 data is taken in "campaigns," which are ≈ 75 day-long periods of time during which the telescope takes its data. At the end of each campaign, the telescope moves on to its next target field, propelled by the Sun's radiation pressure and two (of four original) reaction wheels. Over the course of the campaign, the telescope wanders, and the average observed flux increases (See Figure A.6). This increase is clearly not an accurate representation of what is happening in the field of view. We call it an "instrumental trend" and it needs to be removed from the data before analysis can be done.

We use the Median Filtering method of detrending the data. With this method, we designate a "window size" and move that window along the time axis. We take the mean of the flux values in each window, which provides an array of values that describe the instrumental trend. The actual flux measurements are found by dividing the raw flux measurements by the instrumental fluxes.

To determine the window size, one must know the duration of the planet's transit. In the case of multi-planet systems, the window size is determined by longest duration. EPIC has a transit duration of ≈ 1.5 hrs. A window size smaller than the largest transit duration would eliminate transit signatures (they would be divided out), so we select a window size of ≈ 3 times the longest transit duration to be safe. We use long cadence data, which has an integration time of 30 minutes, so we use a window size of 13 points.

A.3.2 Removing Outliers

An outlier is a point that is so far away from the average of the other points that we can tell it isn't actually a reflection of what's happening in our target system. It might be the result of an instrumental error, or a strange spike in stellar luminosity, or a number of different things. Even if the event that resulted in an outlying data point is astronomically interesting, it wasn't a transiting exoplanet, so we do not want to include that point when we do our analysis.

To remove the outliers, we first have to separate all of the data points into two categories: points that occur in any of the planets' transits and points that occur outside of all of the transits. This is done with prior knowledge of each planet's orbital period and transit duration. Outliers are then taken from the out-of-transit data. (See Figure A.2.) Because outlier removal is

done using a sigma clipping method, removing outliers from a data set that includes the transit data would remove many of the transit points.

We remove points that occur more than 3.764σ from the mean flux value.

A.4 ANALYSIS

A.4.1 Exofast

To get preliminary parameters for EPIC, we used Exofast. Exofast is an online program written in IDL and designed to fit planet light curves and radial velocity plots (Eastman, Gaudi, and Agol, 2013).

The program uses a Differential Evolution Markov Chain Monte Carlo (DE-MC) code to constrain the physical parameters for the system and associated uncertainties. The code finds the best fit light curve to the data by exploring the parameters – semimajor axis, planet radius, stellar features, etc. – that contribute to the shape of the light curve. Every time it produces a new set of test parameters, the code generates a model light curve and calculates the χ^2 likelihood that the model curve would produce the observed data. If the new step is more likely or has a lower χ^2 than the old step, it is accepted and the code should continue in that direction along that parameter axis. It does this over and over again until the code minimizes χ^2 . The best fit light curve is shown in Figure A.3.

The difference between a DE-MC program and an MCMC program is the inclusion of a genetic algorithm for numerical optimization – the differential evolution. Programs to fit exoplanet light curves are actually exploring several parameters in real parameter space. A DE-MC program is able to explore along every axis in the multi-dimensional parameter space by choosing which parameter to explore under each iteration.

We present values obtained from Exofast’s best fit in § A.5.

Exofast requires that the user inputs stellar parameters including effective temperature, stellar radius, and surface gravity (which depends on stellar mass). At the time, we did not know what the stellar parameters of EPIC were, so we used average values for M-dwarfs. In addition, exofast’s library of stellar models does not include stars with temperatures of $3000K$, which is around the average temperature for an M-dwarf.

Given these two conditions, we were not confident in the results produced by exofast.

A.4.2 MultiNest

As a comparison for our results, we used a fitting algorithm called MultiNest. MultiNest is a publicly available Monte Carlo program that uses Bayesian techniques to calculate posterior probabilities. This is more accurate and computationally inexpensive than traditionally-used transit fitting programs that do not include Bayesian evidence in their calculations.

In addition to including the Bayesian framework, MultiNest also allows multiple modes to be found in parameter space (hence the name *MultiNest*).

MultiNest works by casting "active points" throughout parameter space and calculating a likelihood at each point. The point with the lowest likelihood gets demoted to "inactive" and a new point is cast. In this way, the program explores parameter space, always moving toward points with higher probabilities.

The program produces lists of posterior probabilities that can then be analyzed to find the mean and $\pm 1\sigma$ values. Some of the parameters, such as $\frac{R_p}{R_*}$, are found with respect to stellar properties. The values were converted into absolute units using the stellar parameters we found according to the methods detailed in § A.4.3 We present those values in § A.5.

A.4.3 Our Program

Light Curve Fitting

We wrap BATMAN, a light curve modelling code (Kreidberg, 2015) in our own DE-MC program written in Python.

BATMAN produces a model light curve from a set of input parameters: mid transit time, orbital period, $\frac{R_p}{R_*}$, semimajor axis, inclination, eccentricity, and argument of periastron. Both $\frac{R_p}{R_*}$ and semimajor axis are in units of stellar radius.

Our DE-MC program operates in much the same way as the program described in § A.4.1, except instead of minimizing χ^2 , our program aims to maximize likelihood. The code uses numpy's random number generator to randomly choose which parameter to vary during each iteration. That parameter is varied by a "jumpsize," which is randomly chosen from a distribution centered around a value set by the user. That value can be individualized to each parameter.

Some of the parameters – eccentricity and $\frac{R_p}{R_*}$ – that BATMAN uses to produce the model light curve are limited to certain values because of their definition. Both must be between 0 and 1.

If either of these parameters are chosen and the jumpsize varies the value

such that it moves outside of those bounds, the model light curve produced by BATMAN will just be a flat line. This should produce a low likelihood that the model would match the observed data and thus discourage the code from continuing to move in that direction along that parameter axis. However our data were very noisy even after detrending and outlier removal. Therefore, it's possible that the code could continue to explore parameter space outside of the physical bounds.

To eliminate this possibility, we include statements in our code that catch every time the jumpsize would take one of the aforementioned parameters outside of their physical bounds. When this happens, the code reverses the jumpsize so that the parameter is altered in the opposite direction.

The best fit light curve is shown in Figure A.4.

We present parameters from the best model fit to the observed data in § A.5.

Stellar Parameters

To find the stellar mass, we wrote an MCMC program that tested the likelihood of a test mass producing an [r-J] color that matched the observed [r-J] color of 2.951. The test mass was used to produce an absolute J-band magnitude according to a polynomial relationship in Johnson et al, 2011 (Eqn. 3). That absolute J-band magnitude was used to produce a model [r-J] color based on a linear relationship we fit to the values in Table 1 of West et al, 2005. A distribution of masses is produced by the MCMC code and we report the highest likelihood mass and the 1σ deviation.

We found the stellar radius using the polynomial relationship between stellar mass and radius for single star systems in Boyajian et al, 2012 (Eqn. 10).

We found the effective stellar temperature by using polynomial color-temperature relationships in Boyajian et al, 2013. We used three different photometric colors ([g-z], [g-r], and [g-i]) from the Pan-STARRS database, and averaged their resulting temperatures.

A.5 RESULTS

There are three parameters that can be measured directly from a transit light curve: orbital period, transit duration, and transit depth. From these, we can derive the parameters listed in Table A.1.

A.5.1 Habitability

We determine habitable zone boundaries – distances from the star within which the temperature on a planet would be just right for holding liquid water – using Eqn. 3 in Kopparapu et al, 2013.

The relationship requires knowledge of the stellar temperature (described in § A.4.3) and luminosity (found using the star’s absolute J-band magnitude). Many claims about habitability rely on a planet’s equilibrium temperature – the temperature it would have if it absorbed all of the incident flux from its star and re-emitted it as heat. Instead of relying on equilibrium temperature, Kopparapu’s relationship relies on instellation, or the amount of flux the planet receives from its star. It establishes instellation cutoffs where a planet would receive too much flux (inner boundary) and too little (outer boundary) to hold liquid water. Given the stellar parameters, and assuming various types of planetary atmospheres, the relationship results in distances for the inner and outer bounds.

We use the coefficients in Table 3 of Kopparapu et al (2013) that correspond to optimistic (widest) habitable zone boundaries. Under such conditions, the inner edge of the habitable zone lies at $0.342AU$ and the outer edge lies at $0.881AU$.

To further test habitability, we reference Rogers et al, 2015 to determine whether or not the planet is rocky. Rogers, 2015 reports that most planets larger than $1.6R_{\oplus}$ are not rocky. She comes to this conclusion by doing a statistical analysis of the compositions of planets discovered by *Kepler*. The analysis reveals a relationship between planet radius and density, and shows that $1.6R_{\oplus}$ planets are not dense enough to be comprised primarily of the iron and silicates that form rocky planets.

Based on the values for semimajor axis and planet radius presented in Table A.1, EPIC is likely a gaseous planet residing far interior to its star’s habitable zone.

A.5.2 Eccentricity

Our DE-MC program constrains an eccentricity value of 0.8965, which is unrealistically high. A subsequent examination of the eccentricity values explored by the program revealed that the "walkers" bounced back and forth between the physical limits defined within the code.

Our test program, MultiNest, also returned an eccentricity value that nearly matched the prior expectation input.

Based on these ill-constrained values, we determine that EPIC’s transit light curve does not carry sufficient information about the planet’s eccentric-

ity to report our own value. Instead, we choose a more realistic eccentricity value from an example in our own solar system: Mercury, with an eccentricity of 0.206. The temperature values at periastron and apoastron were calculated using this eccentricity.

A.6 DISCUSSION

In this paper, we argue the case that EPIC is a gaseous planet interior to the habitable zone of its host star. We make this claim of habitability based on the single, most popular criterion that a planet must be able to hold liquid water in order to be habitable. There are other criteria that must be considered, however, before habitability can be definitively claimed.

A planet's albedo – a measure of how reflective it is – influences the planet's climate. A more reflective surface would indicate water or clouds, which help to stabilize a planet's temperature. If we were interested in whether or not a planet can hold human-like life, knowledge about the planet's atmosphere is essential. Unfortunately, EPIC is too small and its star is too dim for modern technology to be able to learn about its albedo or atmosphere.

Future work on this project would include running our DE-MC program with more iterations. This analysis was done using 50,000 iterations. Ideally, we would have run at least 500,000. We would also like to explore different limb-darkening parameters. Stars are not uniformly illuminated across their surfaces. From our perspective, the edges or limbs of stars appear to be darker than the centers. Our DE-MC program assumed a uniform stellar brightness, but a more accurate light curve fit could be accomplished by exploring different limb-darkening models.

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Figure A.1: Trended K2 data for EPIC

Figure A.2: Plot of detrended data with outliers in blue and “good” data in red

Figure A.3: Exofast's best fit to the data

Figure A.4: Most likely fit to the data produced by our DE-MC program

Table A.1: Table of parameter values

Parameter	Exofast	MultiNest	Our Program Best Fit
Stellar Parameters			
Mass (M_{\odot})	$0.135^{+0.031}_{-0.025}$	\Rightarrow	0.398 ± 0.040
Radius (R_{\odot})	$0.194^{+0.029}_{-0.025}$	\Rightarrow	0.383 ± 0.035
Density (cgs)	$26.2^{+14}_{-9.1}$	\Rightarrow	10.324 ± 1.748
Temperature (K)	3010 ± 200	3505^{+128}_{-90}	3615 ± 182
Planetary Parameters			
Orbital Period (Days)	$4.11038^{+0.00047}_{-0.00046}$	4.11047 ± 0.00055	Fixed at 4.1123548
Semi-major Axis (AU)	$0.0257^{+0.0019}_{-0.0017}$	–	0.0121 ± 0.0011
Radius (R_{\oplus})	$0.9652^{+0.1844}_{-0.1518}$	$1.91^{+0.31}_{-0.26}$	1.8070 ± 0.1677
Temp at Periastron (K)	470 ± 41	715 ± 164	1122 ± 149
Temp at Apoastron (K)	353 ± 37	457 ± 64	902 ± 95
Orbital Parameters			
Eccentricity e	$0.28^{+0.34}_{-0.21}$	0.2066 ± 0.1502	0.206
Inclination i	$89.35^{+0.44}_{-0.58}$	–	88.0972
Argument of Periastron ω	–	2.7946 ± 2.0205	85.3130

Appendix B

Thirty Meter Telescope Conflict

Native Hordes is meant to metaphorically portray centuries worth of colonization on the Hawaiian Islands and the current conflict that exists between the scientific and local communities. Astronomers plan to build a telescope on top of Mauna Kea on Hawai'i Island and have been met with protests by a group of people calling themselves the Mauna Kea Protectors. In this appendix, I will provide the historical¹, technical², and ethnographic background necessary to better understand the conflict and the metaphor in the book.

Captain James Cook's arrival on the Hawaiian Islands in 1778 is often cited as the point of first contact between Hawai'i and the Western world. Four decades later in 1820, the native population had been reduced to a small fraction of its original size by disease and violent interactions with foreigners. Local practices, religions, and even the language were outlawed by missionaries who claimed they wanted to "civilize" the natives. Land and resources were taken from people whose families had worked them for generations and given to wealthy westerners.

Over the next several decades, the sugar industry exploded in Hawai'i. More than 100,000 acres of farmland were devoted to sugar farms. In 1875, the United States and the Kingdom of Hawai'i signed a treaty establishing free sugar trade between the two nations. Nearly a decade later, after the U.S. showed little interest in renewing the treaty, tariffs were applied to sugar exports from Hawai'i to the mainland. Native Hawaiians protested and western planters called to the U.S. to take control. In 1887, U.S. Marines

¹Silva, Noenoe K. *Aloha Betrayed: Native Hawaiian Resistance to American Colonialism*. Durham: Duke UP, 2004. Print.

²"Thirty Meter Telescope." About TMT. N.p., n.d. Web. Mar. 2016.

invaded Hawai'i to squash the rebellion, establishing a massive U.S. military presence in the Kingdom.

In 1891, Queen Lili'uokalani assumed the throne and attempted to return power to the monarchy by writing a new constitution to replace the Bayonet Constitution, which her brother, King Kalākaua, had signed under force in 1887. The new constitution would have disenfranchised many of the wealthy western residents of Hawai'i, upturning the power structure on the islands. In response, Lorrin Thurston led a conspiracy that ultimately resulted in the house arrest of Queen Lili'uokalani.

When President William McKinley took office in 1897, the wealthy settlers who overthrew Queen Lili'uokalani had an ally in the White House to spur the annexation of Hawai'i to America into action. Many Hawaiians protested and Queen Lili'uokalani pleaded with the American government not to go forward with the annexation. Yet, after decades of British imperialist rule, occupation by the American military, and the systematic oppression of Hawaiian sovereign power, the U.S. annexed Hawai'i as a territory in 1898.

For 60 years, the people of Hawai'i lived as residents of a U.S. territory, treated like American property but denied citizens' rights until Hawai'i became the 50th state in 1959.

Forty years later, in 1970, the first telescopes were proposed for construction on top of Mauna Kea. Around this time, the Hawaiian Sovereignty Movement started to speak out against the wrongs that had been committed against the Hawaiian people and their land. It is now 46 years later. Hawai'i is still an American state and 12 additional telescopes have been placed on top of one of the islands' most sacred mountains.

In 2009, the Thirty Meter Telescope (TMT) became the 14th telescope to be proposed for construction on Mauna Kea through a collaboration between Caltech, the University of California, the National Astronomical Observatory of Japan (NAOJ), and organizations in China and India. Two other sites were proposed – Baja, Mexico and Chile – but both were ultimately ruled less favorable than Hawai'i. Weather conditions in Baja were less ideal than on top of Mauna Kea and other large telescopes were already planned for construction in Chile, so there was a surplus of coverage in the southern hemisphere. Three factors contributed to the choice of Hawai'i as a superior location.

- The presence of 13 other telescopes on the mountain provide an existing infrastructure. There is already a visitor's center, housing for visiting scientists, and support systems in place in case the telescopes malfunction.

- Mauna Kea’s summit sits high in the atmosphere at 14,000 feet, where the air is thin and dry, which are perfect conditions for collecting high-quality data.
- Hawai’i is easy to travel to from Japan, which enticed the Japanese partners to join the project.

The TMT was advertised as a groundbreaking telescope, capable of probing a range of redshifts up to the very early universe. The telescope dome would be 18 stories high and over 200 feet across. (See Figure B.1.)

Figure B.1: Artist’s rendering of the Thirty Meter Telescope. Photo Cred: TMT

On December 2, 2015, plans to construct the telescope were suspended when the Hawaiian Supreme Court ruled that the permits obtained in 2010 were invalid. The TMT Committee awaits the new Supreme Court decision, however the ruling was just the latest and most judiciary obstacle to the telescope’s construction.

The groundbreaking ceremony for the TMT was scheduled to happen on October 7th, 2014, but a blockade of people on the road up to the summit prevented the trucks from reaching the construction site. Protests continued, gaining attention worldwide with the help of celebrity support (See Figure B.2.) and social media. The people protesting call themselves the Mauna Kea Protectors.

Figure B.2: Picture from Jason Momoa's twitter feed showing his support of the Mauna Kea Protectors. Momoa plays Khal Drogo on the popular show Game of Thrones.

The conflict reached peak popularity on social media in Spring of 2015 after several people were arrested for blocking construction crews. I first learned about the TMT conflict in May of 2015 after an email from Sandra Faber, a professor of astronomy at the University of California in Santa Cruz, sparked outrage in the astronomical community and on my Facebook newsfeed. In the email, Faber says that the TMT is being "attacked by a horde of native Hawaiians." (See Figure B.3.) Faber's email was forwarded to the rest of UCSC's faculty by her colleague, Alex Filippenko, who prefaced his forward by saying "I support what [Faber] says."

After her initial email received such negative attention, Faber released a statement to the community apologizing for her language, but not the sentiment behind it. (See Figure B.4.)

Sandra Faber's support of the TMT and vilification of the Protectors is merely the most public of the claims made by TMT proponents. For weeks, astronomers posted articles and opinions about the conflict on the *Astronomers* Facebook page, which included thousands of astronomers from around the world. (The page has since been abandoned and replaced with an *Astronomy* page, which places an emphasis on the original purpose of the first page: discussions about astronomical research.)

One common question asked by TMT supporters on the *Astronomers* page was: Why are they just protesting now? Their point was that if the mountain and the life that exists on it is so important to native Hawaiians, protests would have begun when the first telescopes were proposed for Mauna Kea in the 1970s. People who use this argument often try to represent the Protectors as contrarians, as youths who joined the movement because they needed something to do³. In my own interactions with the Protectors, I saw that this was not the case. The Protectors claim that people *have* been protesting the telescopes since the 1970s, but without the help of the internet, news about those protests rarely left the islands.

In September of 2016, in an effort to work through my opinions of the TMT conflict, I wrote a blogpost⁴ about the Protectors and their movement. A Hawaiian woman commented on the post and said that the TMT's (and other telescopes') presence on Mauna Kea has only helped the people of Hawai'i. It increased revenue on Hawai'i Island, provided access to cutting edge research opportunities, and continued the traditional Hawaiian connection to astronomy that dates back to fishermen and travelers navigating by the stars. Everything she said is true. In the current state of Hawaiian affairs, building the TMT on top of Mauna Kea can really only have a net positive effect on the local community. But I would also encourage her and people who agree with her to think about why the TMT's presence has these benefits. If Hawai'i had not been subjected to the wrongs committed by foreign settlers for 200 years, would it need to rely on foreign scientists to stimulate the economy or provide limited research access?

When considering these points raised by supporters of the TMT, it is important to remember that scientific research is not done in a vacuum. Whether people recognize it or not, decisions like the one to put the TMT on Mauna Kea cannot be separated from the history of colonization and injustice that exist in so many spaces around the world. That history and

³From a conversation with a haole (foreigner of European descent) man who currently lives in Hawai'i. I had this conversation on the plane on my way to Hawai'i on the Harvard senior trip.

⁴McTier, Moiya A.S. "Hordes Are Made of People Too." *AstroMo*. N.p., n.d. Web. Apr. 2016.

the question of how power influences scientific policy are the reasons I wanted to learn more about the TMT conflict. I was given the opportunity to spend time on Mauna Kea and learn more about the conflict thanks to the Harvard Astronomy Department's senior trip to the observatory.

We stayed on the mountain for three days in August of 2015. While I was there, I took the opportunity to meet the Protectors – some of whom had been peacefully occupying the mountain since the planned date of the groundbreaking ceremony – and learn their stories and motivations for opposing the construction of the TMT.

Over the three days I spent on the mountain, I saw the Protectors welcome supporters of the movement from New York and places around the Midwest. Many of them identified as Native American and therefore felt connected to the Protectors and their cause. I also saw the Protectors supervise and consult on a sketch for (what they described as) a local satirical show. I learned that they have no central organizing structure and that they do not plan who will spend time on the mountain at which times. The movement is solely propelled by the participation of people who devote whatever time and resources they can to protect the mountain.

When I first approached the Protectors' tent, I was welcomed immediately. They greeted me with a traditional greeting – touching foreheads and sharing breath – and offered me food. When I explained my thesis to them, they were eager to answer all of my questions.

My first day on the mountain, I asked all of the Protectors why they had joined the movement. Many people said they joined because they had concerns about the environmental impact the telescope would have. Several species of plants and animals are native to the mountain and continued settlement on the mountain endangers them.

Many more Protectors cited religious reasons for opposing the TMT, saying that the foundation for the telescope would disrupt a sacred lake and burial ground on top of the summit. Mauna a Wākea – often shortened to Mauna Kea – is a sacred mountain located on Hawai'i Island in Hawai'i. In Hawaiian mythology, the mountain is the site where the Sky Father and the Earth Mother met to conceive the world and the islands were borne from the mountain. Because of this belief, the mountain was the site of many traditional Hawaiian practices. Mauna Kea is also an important feature in the Hawaiian skyline, used by ancient sailors to help guide their way back home.

Others still cited *kuleana*, a sense of personal responsibility, in this case for continuing the fight their ancestors started during the anti-annexation protests in the 1890s.

I spent the rest of my time with the Protectors on that first day talking

to one man, L, who answered most of my questions about the Protectors and the movement. L told me about the philosophy of the movement, a philosophy that focuses on *aloha*, or love – love for people and love for the land. When I asked what the grossest misrepresentation of the movement was, he said it was the idea that they are advocating for the abolishment of science. "We're not saying it's culture versus science," he says, "but that it should be culture *and* science."

The second day I was on the mountain, I spent time with an older married couple, S and J. They led me on a long walk around the mountain, telling me about shrines and plants as we encountered them. They told me that their involvement with with the Protectors had contributed to ending life-long friendships. The issue really is a contentious one among Hawaiian communities.

On the third day, I met a woman, K, who worked as a farmer – she made it explicitly clear that she didn't believe anyone could *own* land, but she was willing to look after that particular patch until other people started to see it the same way – near the base of the mountain. K told me that she supported the Protectors because the foundation of the TMT would interfere with a natural aquifer she used to irrigate her farm.

The Protectors are still occupying the mountain and will continue to do so until the Hawaiian Supreme Court decides not to grant a permit to the TMT committee or until the organization runs out of money and can no longer support construction. Unlike the representatives from the TMT I talked to at the American Astronomical Society meeting in January of 2016 who were uncertain of the fate of the TMT, the Protectors have no doubt that their movement will be successful.

I am not Hawaiian. Neither I nor any of my ancestors have ever lived in Hawai'i. And as someone who has no personal or familial connection to the space, my opinion when it comes to the TMT honestly does not matter. And so the purpose of this book is not to persuade the reader to agree with me. My goal in writing this book and providing this context is to persuade the reader that the TMT conflict is not a question of *which* is more important – science or culture – but is rather a question of *why* are some people in a position where they can say that one is more important.

----- Forwarded message -----

From: **Alexei V. FILIPPENKO**

<afilippenko@berkeley.edu>

Date: Mon, Apr 20, 2015 at 3:02 PM

Subject: Petition to support the Thirty Meter Telescope

To: "everyone@astro.berkeley.edu"

<everyone@astro.berkeley.edu>

Cc: "Alexei V. FILIPPENKO"

<afilippenko@berkeley.edu>

From Sandy Faber (but I support what she says):

Dear friends:

The Thirty-Meter Telescope is in trouble,
attacked by a horde
of native Hawaiians who are lying about the
impact of
the project on mountain and who are
threatening the
safety of TMT personnel. Government
officials are supporting
TMT's legality to proceed but not arresting
any of the
protestors who are blocking the road. you
can learn
more at:

<http://www.huffingtonpost.com/news/thirty-meter-telescope/>

Please take a minute to visit this website and
sign your
name to support TMT.

<http://www.gopetition.com/petitions/wesupporttmt/sign.html>

Thanks so much, Sandy Faber

Figure B.3: Screenshot of Alex Filippenko's email forwarding Sandra Faber's message to a wider subset of the astronomical community. Taken from Hawaii Public Radio website

Dear Colleagues,

On April 20th, I circulated an email describing the recent protests against construction of the Thirty Meter Telescope on Mauna Kea, and encouraging people to sign a pro-TMT petition originated by a high school student in Hawaii.

It is very unfortunate that my email contained some inflammatory and insensitive language. I sent this message with the intent of spreading the word about the pro-TMT petition. I regret that I sent it in a hurry, without thinking through how the message was written or how it would be interpreted. This was a mistake on my part, for which I sincerely apologize.

I deeply regret the language that I used to describe the protestors. I have great respect for the special nature of Mauna Kea, and profound regard for Hawaii's culture, environment and people. Like many astronomers who use the great telescopes on Mauna Kea, I have participated personally and joyfully in ceremonies to celebrate the profound cosmic understanding that comes from joining ancient Hawaiian navigator traditions with the techniques of modern astronomy. I am committed to an open and respectful dialog with all stakeholders about the future of astronomy on Mauna Kea.

I continue to enthusiastically support the construction of the Thirty Meter Telescope, and I hope that my regrettable email message does not reflect negatively on TMT.

Sincerely,

Professor Emeritus Sandra Faber
University of California at Santa Cruz